

**THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRESERVICE
TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE
AND IDENTITY THROUGH IMMERSION IN A
SCHOOL COMMUNITY**

Andrew Leichsenring

Bachelor of Arts (The University of Queensland)

Bachelor of International Business (Griffith University)

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KEYWORDS & DEFINITIONS

community of practice - a shared domain of learning that preservice teachers engage in with members of their school community during their learning of teaching and development of a teacher identity

immersion pathway - a structured pathway of professional engagement for preservice teachers giving them the opportunity to immerse themselves in a school community over the duration of the fourth-year of their Bachelor of Education (BEd) degree in addition to their usual coursework of attending classes and completing the mandatory Field Experience placements, as with all other preservice teachers in their program

preservice teacher - a teacher candidate who is participating in teacher education and intending to graduate and become a qualified professional teacher

professional experience - a broad based experience of working (unpaid) in a school to gain skills and knowledge to become a qualified teacher in an authentic work setting; this can go beyond class practicum to include other school-based activities

sociocultural theory - a philosophical construct that all human mental functioning is inherently situated in cultural, historical, and institutional settings

teacher identity - a self-attributed notion constructed through teaching experiences and knowledge about teaching

ABSTRACT

This case study research explored the professional teacher identity development of six fourth-year preservice teachers through a process of socialisation which involved their participation in a year-long immersion pathway in schools. Common attributes that have been associated with the notion of identity are that it is dynamic, multidimensional, and shifts over time due to the negotiation of both internal and external factors that occur in the daily lives of individuals. These negotiations of concepts, ideas, theories, and experiences create the accounts of teacher identity development as shared by the participating preservice teachers.

The utilisation of an interpretivist epistemology in this research was viewed to include not only the understanding of meanings from human actions but also the consideration of their experiences and histories. For example, preservice teachers bring past life experiences as members of previous school communities: as school students, as preservice teachers on prior Field Experience placements, or through previous employment experiences to their current situation. By including an understanding of the past histories and experiences of preservice teachers, a richer analysis of the development of preservice teacher identity evolves than might be afforded only by viewing preservice teachers through their immediate day-to-day experiences. Case study is described as especially good for getting a rich picture of a particular sociocultural situation by looking at it from many angles. Case study design is flexible allowing the researcher to select a topic and determine the boundaries of the issue or problem to be researched. To date, there is a dearth of research that specifically explores preservice teachers' teacher identity development in a year-long immersion pathway.

Data were collected at several data collection points from the beginning, mid-point and end point of the preservice teachers' immersion pathway experience using semi-structured interviews and postings on a closed online discussion board. Because it was important to include contextual aspects of preservice teachers' voices it was deemed that semi-structured interviews would provide them with the best way to present their views. The questions that were asked of the preservice teachers over the course of the

year allowed the researcher to compare responses for professional teacher identity development over time. Analysis of the data after each interview set informed the development of the questions for the next set of interviews. The conversational group oriented online discussion board on Google+ (n.d.), was set up for group participation. This site, available only to the research participants and the researcher, was intended to provide a channel of communication for personal journal writing and sharing of information among the participating preservice teachers in the immersion pathway and the researcher throughout the year.

Thematic analysis was used to identify meaningful themes throughout data collection as a quasi-constant comparative method of analysis where incidents or data are compared to other incidents or data during the process of coding. This method of data analysis uses a systematic and rigorous approach to inductive analysis of discourse used specifically as the literature on communities of practice (CoPs) has set identifiers as to what constitutes a community, such as identity and practice (Lave & Wenger, 2000).

Deductive coding revealed an overarching focus: *Teacher Identity Development* which was connected with the most significant theme of *Sense of Belonging*. Inductive coding then revealed that the major theme of *Sense of Belonging* was divided into three broad themes: *Relationships*, *Teaching Practice*, and *Philosophy of Teaching*. The theme of *Relationships* was further divided into six subthemes that indicated relationships with school principal and deputy principal, supervising teachers, other school staff, fellow preservice teachers, students, and parents. The theme of *Teaching Practice* was further divided into the subthemes of classroom management, behaviour management, and teaching duties. The theme of *Philosophy of Teaching* was further divided into the subthemes of current teaching and future teaching.

The research data revealed that such a transformation of teacher identity development is enhanced when preservice teachers feel that they have been accepted as members of the school's CoP. The findings of the research suggest that there is merit in having preservice teachers engage with school communities as volunteer participants over an extended period of time. Being immersed in a school for an extended period of time allowed the preservice teachers opportunities to test out the teacher behaviours they observed experienced teachers enacting. These opportunities led the preservice teachers

to hone their own teaching skills and to present themselves to others as a teacher rather than as a preservice teacher. Being perceived by others as ‘a teacher’ rather than as a preservice teacher had a positive impact on their developing professional teacher identity and sense of belonging within the school community.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AITSL - Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership

APST - Australian Professional Standards for Teachers

ASD - Autism Spectrum Disorder

BEd - Bachelor of Education

CoP - Community of Practice

C2C - Curriculum to Classroom

FI - Final Internship

HSW - How Science Works

ICP - Individual Curriculum Plan

IP1 - Immersion 1 Day per week

IP3 - Immersion 3 Days per week

IT - Information Technology

ITE - Initial Teacher Education

LBOTE - Language Background other than English

LOTE - Languages Other Than English

LPP - Legitimate Peripheral Participation

MIP - My Immersion Pathway

MYCEETYA - Ministerial Council on Education, Employment, Training, and Youth Affairs

PD - Professional Development

PEP - Professional Experience Practicum blocks

QCT - Queensland College of Teachers

SWD - Students with Disabilities (Centre)

UK - United Kingdom

US - United States (of America)

TV - Television

WWE - World Wrestling Entertainment

ZPD - Zone of Proximal Development

STATEMENT OF ORIGINAL AUTHORSHIP

The work contained in this thesis has not been previously submitted to meet requirements for an award at this or any other higher education institution. To the best of my knowledge and belief, the thesis contains no material previously published or written by another person except where due reference is made.

Signature: Andrew Leichsenring
[QUT Verified Signature](#)

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Chapter 1: INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

This qualitative case study research explored teacher identity development as a process of socialisation in a year-long ‘immersion pathway’ in schools for six fourth-year Bachelor of Education (BEd) preservice teachers in a large Faculty of Education in a Queensland university. As the six participants in the current research were female, the researcher used ‘she’, ‘her’, and ‘herself’ when referring to them individually throughout the thesis. Incidentally, the researcher was male and used ‘he’ and ‘his’ when referring to himself throughout the thesis. Then, the respective university refers to this school-based experience for preservice teachers as an ‘immersion pathway’ and the researcher follows this naming throughout this thesis. Preservice teachers’ identity development grows through their involvement in university-based and school-based teaching and learning experiences (Allen & Peach, 2007; Pridham, Deed, & Cox, 2013). In this thesis it is argued that such a transition in identity is enhanced when preservice teachers feel that they have been accepted as members of the CoP (Wenger, 1998) of teaching. Volunteering in an immersion pathway provided opportunities for preservice teachers in the study to develop a sense of belonging in a school community and, in the process, contribute significantly to their developing teacher identity. To date, no studies have been located that explore the development of preservice teachers’ professional teacher identity and practice through their participation in a year-long immersion pathway. This research fills that gap.

Teacher identity is not fixed but is rather transformative as it changes preservice teachers’ perspectives about themselves as teachers; therefore, it is something that is constructed rather than ready-made. It should be acknowledged that teacher identity is difficult to define. Indeed, Beijaard, Meijer, and Verloop (2004) identified that in much of the research, teacher identity is *not* defined. According to Harlow and Cobb (2014) teacher identity is a ‘self-attributed notion’ that is constructed through teaching experiences and knowledge about what it means to be a teacher. The current research utilised this definition of teacher identity as the focus was on exploring preservice

teachers' perceptions of self as developing teaching professionals. The case study design utilised in this research allowed for an in-depth exploration of how participation in a year-long immersion pathway assisted preservice teachers' professional teacher identity development. To date, no studies have been located that explore the development of preservice teachers' perspectives of their developing teacher identity as it occurs in a year-long immersion pathway. The current research goes some way in filling this gap.

This chapter introduces the research by first identifying the context in which the study occurs (section 1.1). In section 1.2 the purpose for the research is discussed with the main research questions outlined in section 1.3. The significance of this study is argued with reference to the importance of researching the ongoing process of preservice teachers' identity development through immersion in school-based learning communities (section 1.4). The chapter concludes with an outline of the structure for the thesis (section 1.5).

1.1 CONTEXT OF THE RESEARCH

It has long been acknowledged that initial teacher education (ITE) must include school-based experiences for helping preservice teachers build the identity and practices of teaching and these experiences are generally in the form of mandated practicum (Darling-Hammond, 2006; Korthagen, 2010). In a broad sense, and depending on the academic discipline, the 'practicum' has traditionally appeared in many forms, for example, field experience, cooperative education, sandwich program, internship, clerkship, clinical practice (Ryan, Toohey, & Hughes, 1996), experiential learning, work-integrated learning, and teaching practice (Le Cornu, 2015). There are several different names for describing school-based experiences. Currently in Australia it can be called practicum (sometimes called *prac*), supervised professional experience (University of the Sunshine Coast, n.d.), or professional experiences (The University of Sydney, n.d.). In the current research the term *professional experience* was used to describe the learning experiences preservice teachers had in schools as this is the preferred term used by teacher educators in Australia, as noted by the Australian Institute for Teaching and School Leadership (AITSL, 2015). Professional experiences are generally co-supervised between the university and the school staff and provide

preservice teachers with opportunities to experience the practical applications of theory and other coursework they have learned to the real-world context of schools. Professional experience is a mandatory component of any ITE qualification; it is designed to be developmental over time in that preservice teachers gradually take on more teaching experiences and responsibilities the further they progress in their course.

In recent times, a number of Australian university-led programs have been responsive to the need for educators to become critical, reflective change agents through the productive pedagogies of teacher education (Gore, 2002). With the advent of a national approach to program accreditation which outlines requirements to ensure high quality ITEs (AITSL, 2011), that is, the *National Professional Standards for Teachers*, currently each professional experience placement is connected to the Australian Professional Standards for Teachers (APST). At the time of the current research the coursework for the preservice teachers was in transition in order to align with Queensland College of Teachers (QCT) standards. (A copy of these professional standards is included in Appendix A). Participation in the immersion pathway for preservice teachers in the research aligned with the APST standards with particular reference to Standard 6: *Engage in professional learning* and Standard 7: *Engage professionally with colleagues, parents/caregivers and the community* (AITSL, n.d.). Before explaining the immersion pathway, it should be noted that participation in the immersion pathway differed from formal professional experiences in two significant ways: 1) assessment; and 2) kind of commitment. These two differences are described below.

Professional experience placements in schools are incremental and assessable, each building on the previous placement through the course toward graduation. In the current research the participants were all enrolled in a BEd (Primary) four year degree. In this final year of their course they had to complete two mandatory, assessable professional experience blocks of four weeks at a school plus a final four-week internship placement (evaluated as satisfactory/unsatisfactory) at the same school. In the BEd program referred to in the current study the preservice teachers were required to complete 80 days of professional experience and a 20 day internship. These professional experiences occur as per Figure 1.1 below. There is a general agreement that if preservice teachers are not exposed to the full range of teaching work and

responsibilities they can develop unrealistic understandings of what it means to be a teacher (Grudnoff, 2011). Having teaching experiences in schools provides preservice teachers with real world knowledge, learning and skills of what it means to be a teacher. Therefore, participation in school-based experiences is not only mandatory but is vital for preservice teachers to learn how to behave like teachers, think like teachers, and to think of themselves as teachers.

While there is no doubt that mandatory professional experiences are a core part of teacher education, educators have considered alternative school-based experiences, identifying the need for more flexible learning opportunities for preservice teachers to develop their professional selves (Darling-Hammond, 2006; Korthagen, 2004). There has been a call for stronger working relationships between teacher education institutes and schools and a rethinking of how much time preservice teachers should spend in school and how the roles and responsibilities of each of the stakeholders helps to support preservice teachers (AITSL, n.d.). The current thesis advocates that a year-long immersion placement in a school can provide such an alternative but with caution that such a placement needs clear guidelines for all stakeholders to abide by in order to support the development of preservice teachers' teacher identity and practice. It is proposed that participation in a year-long immersion pathway allowed preservice teachers time to explore their understandings of who they were as teachers in more depth than provided through four-week professional experience placements, as well as allowing them to develop and practice their teaching skills and gain an overall understanding of what it means to be a teacher. An outline of the immersion pathway is described below.

The Immersion Pathway: The Immersion Pathway in the current research was structured to allow preservice teachers the opportunity to immerse themselves in a school community over the final year of their BEd (Primary) degree. The immersion pathway was offered as an addition to their usual coursework of attending classes and completing the mandatory professional experience placements that all students in the BEd program must complete. Participation in the immersion pathway was offered as a voluntary option. To participate in the immersion pathway, preservice teachers had to apply for a placement in Semester Two of their third year of study. Therefore, preservice teachers needed to be proactive in planning for participation in the

immersion pathway during their fourth-year of study as their placements began at the beginning of the school year, which starts before the commencement of their university coursework. Those students who were successful in their applications were then partnered with a school where they volunteered to work at the school for the entire year. Overall their commitment of professional experience for these particular preservice teachers in the fourth year of study included participation at the selected school in several ways: 1) their voluntary immersion pathway, 2) their two professional experience blocks (mandatory for fourth-year preservice teachers), and 3) their final internship. In other words, these preservice teachers completed the same course progression as their peers but also included the year-long voluntary commitment to participate in the immersion pathway. Approximately thirty students applied to be placed in the immersion pathway for the 2015 school year; six of those preservice teachers agreed to participate in the research.

In the immersion pathway, the ideal of preservice teacher involvement with the school community was not expected to be as a classroom teacher (as they were obliged to be on mandatory professional experience). Instead they were to engage as an all-rounder assistant in whatever capacity the school community required. The idea of not having these preservice teachers in schools teaching lessons was to give them an overview of the complexity of teaching to help them appreciate that teaching is more than simply standing at the front of the class delivering a lesson. Involvement in the immersion pathway started on the first day of the school year for teachers, before students officially returned to school, in what is described as professional development ‘student-free’ days. ‘Student free’ days are part of the Queensland school calendar where teachers prepare curriculum(s), may attend professional workshops or seminars, and prepare their classrooms in advance of students arriving back for the beginning of a new school year after their summer holidays. Having preservice teachers attend these initial preparation days for the school year allowed them to observe the ‘behind the scene’ work of preparing for a new year of teaching while interacting with their supervising teacher(s) (Broadley & Ledger, 2012) and other school staff.

Over the weeks that followed, preservice teachers had opportunities to observe how the setup of a classroom from the beginning of the year contributes to student learning and how the classroom culture including establishing rules and routines were

established. Preservice teachers attended the school for three days a week from the beginning of the school year until the university semester started. School visits were then reduced to one-day per week until commencement of the formal, mandatory professional experience period. A view of the school year calendar (divided into 4 school terms) is provided below (Figure 1.1). The figure shows the initial 3-day per week engagement (IP3) in the immersion pathway in pink, the 1-day per week participation (IP1) over the year in blue, the professional experience practicum (PEP) blocks in green, the final internship (FI) in yellow, completed by all BEd preservice teachers, and the student free days.

School Term 1										
Student free days	Wk 1	Wk 2	Wk 3	Wk 4	Wk 5	Wk 6	Wk 7	Wk 8	Wk 9	Wk 10
IP3	IP3	IP3	IP3	IP3	IP1	IP1	IP1	IP1	IP1	IP1
School Term 2										
	Wk 1	Wk 2	Wk 3	Wk 4	Wk 5	Wk 6	Wk 7	Wk 8	Wk 9	Wk 10
	IP1	IP1	PEP	PEP	PEP	PEP				
School Term 3										
	Wk 1	Wk 2	Wk 3	Wk 4	Wk 5	Wk 6	Wk 7	Wk 8	Wk 9	Wk 10
		IP1	IP1	IP1	IP1	PEP	PEP	PEP	PEP	
School Term 4										
Student free days	Wk 1	Wk 2	Wk 3	Wk 4	Wk 5	Wk 6	Wk 7	Wk 8	Wk 9	Wk 10
IP3	FI	FI	FI	FI						
Legend										
<u>Immersion pathway (IP3)</u> 3 days per week in school (initial engagement before university begins)			<u>Immersion pathway (IP1)</u> 1 day per week in school (year-long engagement once university begins)			<u>Professional experience practicum blocks (PEP)</u>		<u>Professional experience final internship (FI)</u>		

Figure 1.1. Immersion Pathway & Professional Experience School Calendar 2015

The immersion pathway accommodated in-classroom and out-of-classroom school-based experiences. Examples of engagement included: observation and recording/reflections of classroom routines, teaching strategies, behaviour management, playground supervision procedures, time tabling, and exploring school policies. The university's requirements for preservice teachers' successful completion

of the immersion pathway and professional experience, including a Service learning component, two practicum block placements, and a final internship placement, were communicated to schools and the supervising teachers via coordination and correspondence between the university's placement office and the school site coordinators. It was expected by the university coordinator of the immersion pathway that preservice teachers would engage in extracurricular activities at their schools, such as coaching sporting teams, organising fundraising events, and similar activities that teachers do. Preservice teachers also assisted the classroom teacher as required or negotiated assisting in working with small groups of students, participating in the supervision and organisation of different school clubs and activities, and attending school meetings or other professional activities when invited.

While on immersion, preservice teachers were not expected to plan lessons; however, they did observe and participate in teaching and learning practices as requested by their supervising teachers. These experiences were then reflected upon and discussed with other preservice teachers and their tutors during their regular tutorial sessions at the university. The immersion pathway is in contrast to mandated practicum where preservice teachers are expected to prepare and deliver lessons as a formal requirement of their degree, and in contrast to their internship where they are expected to take a 50% teaching load. The immersion pathway is a preservice teacher education initiative that is distinctly different from the traditional school-based model that places preservice students in schools only for their class-based teaching and learning practicum. From Day One of the school calendar year, preservice teachers in the immersion pathway were engaged in becoming members of their school community, acting in several different capacities that they might not have had the time or opportunity for on a practicum block placement or a final internship placement. The purpose of the immersion pathway was to provide preservice teachers with opportunities to experience the subtle but necessary work of teaching that can be missed when they are on professional experience for evaluation. Preservice teachers' perceptions of how the dynamics of the school community stakeholders (preservice teachers, supervising/mentor teachers, other teachers in the school, students, school administrative staff, teacher educators, parents, and other community members) contributed to their professional teacher identity development was a key element of the current research.

As a result of the experiences that preservice teachers had through their immersion in a school-based setting it is proposed by the researcher that they developed their professional identity, beliefs and practice as emerging teachers in unique ways. Wenger (1998) described that in a CoP it is the members who produce meaning in what they learn and practice in an open process of discovery, rediscovery, and reproduction. Being immersed in a school community for a year the preservice teachers in the current research were able to engage in this process of discovery through their participation in a range of teaching events and practices across the school community and, thus, were able to make meanings that have influenced the development of their professional teacher identity in a much broader and deeper level than they might have done through participation in only the mandatory school experiences.

The school community was a social context of learning for preservice teachers. The current research explored the ways in which the preservice teachers in the immersion pathway perceived they were legitimately accepted within their school communities and to what extent peripherally (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1998, 2000). The school communities included teachers, other school staff, school students, parents, fellow preservice teachers not in the immersion pathway, and other members of the wider school community. Social practices in the schools included: observing and enacting the roles of teachers, understanding school policy and regulations of the school, communications that were documented or represented, particularly through reflection and feedback to the preservice teachers and through the social conventions of schooling. Through their immersion in the professional learning community of a school, preservice teachers were able to share experiences with others at the school, and gain knowledge about their profession by developing meaning from these social interactions and experiences. Beyond the school communities, the participating preservice teachers in the current research interacted with each other informally and met either socially outside of the immersion pathway or during their continuing university coursework and engaged with each other in conversations about teaching and learning. Learning to become a teacher can be viewed as interplay between social competence and personal experience where competence is determined by the ability to engage and be a trusted partner in these interactions (Wenger, 2000). The utilisation of social interactions with teaching staff and professional artefacts and behaviours

connected the preservice teachers with members of the teaching community. The theoretical background of the research is explored in more depth in Chapter 3. Below the specific purpose for the research and the research questions for such an exploration are described.

1.2 PURPOSE OF THE RESEARCH

The aim of the current research was to explore preservice teachers' developing professional teacher identity through participation in a year-long immersion pathway. While it must be acknowledged that preservice teachers generally do develop a teacher identity over their four-year program (Allen & Peach, 2007; Brouwer & Korthagen, 2005; Coffey, 2010; Compton, Davis, & Correia, 2010; Le Cornu, 2010), it is posited in the current research that participation in a year-long immersion pathway contributed in developing teacher identity in nuanced ways not always possible through the four mandatory professional experience placements in a BEd program. School-based professional experiences are described as integral to preservice teachers' transition into emergent professional teachers (Allen & Peach, 2007; Brouwer & Korthagen, 2005; Coffey, 2010). Research has found that preservice teachers begin to shape their teacher identity during their professional experience in schools, particularly in regard to psychological factors, such as values, commitment, efficacy, emotion, knowledge, and beliefs (Darling-Hammond, 2006; Korthagen, 2004). In contrast to preservice teachers who have yet to engage in their school-based professional experiences, those who have completed them exhibited less idealistic views about the teaching profession but had more realistic views of what it means to be a teacher (Chong, Low, & Goh, 2011a). While there is much research on preservice teachers experiencing four-week professional experience placements (Allen & Peach, 2007; Brouwer & Korthagen, 2005; Chong et al., 2011a; Coffey, 2010; Decker & Rimm-Kaufman, 2008; Hong, 2010) there is little research on the perceptions of preservice teachers' identity development through their participation in a year-long immersion pathway. The current research addresses this gap. Not only is there limited research in this field, but this thesis argues the position that immersion is a valid approach to better prepare preservice teachers for the demands of the teaching profession and their personal identity within the profession.

The current research also differs from existing research on the development of preservice teacher identity as it considers the formation of professional teacher identity in relation to the situated learning through participation in the CoP of schooling (Lave & Wenger, 1991). While Staton (2008) observed that preservice teacher professional development occurs through a process of socialisation in schools, evidence of how this specifically occurs through the perceptions of preservice teachers immersed in an ongoing professional experience has been under-researched.

Timostsuk and Ugaste (2010) described that teacher professional identity development was significant in regards to the relationships in which preservice teachers engaged. These encounters, when positive, elevated preservice teachers' sense of identity as a teacher. Negative experiences, while emotionally draining, were also considered to be opportunities where supervising teachers could support preservice teachers in their identity development. In the current research the preservice teachers negotiated many different kinds of relationships with their supervising teachers, their students, the school administration staff and other teachers, with parents, and with fellow preservice teachers. Each of these relationships provided different perspectives on meaning-making about teaching for the preservice teachers. How preservice teachers in the study negotiated these relationships was a focus for the current research as it is through these social interactions that identity is formed.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The current study explored the development of preservice teacher identity development through the context of fourth-year preservice teachers' engagement in an immersion pathway. The overarching research question was:

What experiences do preservice teachers perceive as providing insights into the profession and in developing an identity of belonging in the profession?

There were two sub-questions to explore preservice teachers' identity development:

- 1. How do preservice teachers develop an identity as a teacher through their immersion in a professional community?*
- 2. How do preservice teachers develop professional practice through their*

immersion in a professional community?

The research questions were addressed through semi-structured interviews; through a private moderated online discussion board in which preservice teachers posted comments about their individual experiences and told stories of their professional experiences; and the collection of profession-based artefacts that were meaningful to the participating preservice teachers. Further description of the research design is provided in Chapter 4 of the thesis.

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The current research is significant for the following three main reasons: 1) there is limited research on preservice teachers' perceptions of developing a professional teacher identity and practice through participation in an immersion pathway, 2) findings from the research will contribute to understanding how participation in an immersion pathway shapes teacher identity for future teacher education program planning, and 3) this study explored preservice teachers identity development in the under-researched area of CoPs. These three reasons are explored in more depth below.

First, there is limited existing research on preservice teacher identity development that explores the perceptions of preservice teachers engaged in a year-long immersion pathway. In their exploration of the development of preservice teacher identity spanning a general four-year teacher education course, Chong, Low, and Goh (2011b) found that there was some evidence of an emerging professional teacher identity among the preservice teachers; this identity development was considered to be in its infancy at the end of the preservice programs. Graham and Robert's (2007) study of preservice teacher identity and the social interactions of preservice teachers with others in their school-based communities revealed that preservice teachers required social awareness and professional skills to succeed in their professional role as teachers. It is considered in the current research that such social awareness and the development of professional skills came about through preservice teachers' participation in the many and different opportunities and interactions with various members of the school community over time. Hong's (2010) study of preservice and beginning teachers' professional identity involved researching participants who were involved in different

stages of a preservice teacher program study or beginning teacher practice and, not unexpectedly, found that teacher identity development evolved with greater exposure to the community of teaching. The current research recognised the importance of researching the ongoing process of preservice teachers' interpretations and reinterpretations of self as teachers during their professional experience by exploring professional identity development of preservice teachers on a continuous basis over the course of a one-year immersion in a school community. Teacher educators with school teachers and other school staff will benefit from the findings of the research in that they can identify the strengths of such programs according to the perceptions of those undergoing the change in identity. What matters to preservice teachers in relation to their professional development must be taken into account in any innovation in teacher education programs.

Second, this research offers insights into understanding what experiences enhance preservice teacher immersion into the teaching profession and how these experiences shaped the depth such immersion provided for teacher identity and teaching practice development. Traditional models of preservice teacher education are identified as university coursework with school-based block practicums occurring at either side of university semesters (Graham & Thornley, 2000). In contrast to practicum experience, preservice teachers can learn unique aspects of teaching in a real-world context throughout a year-long engagement (Hudson, 2009). The argument considered in the current research is that preservice teachers gained in preparedness for their future teaching careers through their participation in the immersion pathway by gaining a broader and deeper understanding of what it means to be a teacher. Evidence suggests that teachers who are fully prepared through their teacher training stay in teaching at much higher rates than those who lack key elements of preparation (Darling-Hammond & Bransford, 2007). Additionally, a recognised way to retain teachers in the school system is to support them in a context that fosters positive relationships (Waddell, 2010). The current research contributes to this literature by providing an insight into the experiences that enabled and/or constrained the development of professional identity and practice of preservice teachers as they transition toward becoming graduate teachers.

Third, the research explored teacher identity development through the lens of situated learning in a CoP (Wenger, 1998). The researcher has not been able to find any other research that utilised situated learning as a theoretical basis for exploring preservice teachers' identity development in a year-long immersion pathway. It has been found that preservice teachers who value school community-based relationships during their professional experience gain positively in relation to the development of their professional identity (Joseph & Heading, 2010; Mutton, Burn, & Hagger, 2010). It is important to understand, from the preservice teachers' perspectives how immersion in the schools has helped them to learn and develop their teacher identity and practice, including the influences that enabled and constrained their development over time.

Findings from the current research are expected to benefit several parties. The academic community will benefit through the contribution to literature on preservice teacher immersion programs as they support development of preservice teachers' professional identity and practice. Preservice teachers who are or will be engaged in professional learning experience may find the insights of other participants in this study to be useful comparisons for their own journey of developing a teacher identity and practice in school-based settings. University lecturers, supervising/mentor teachers, school administrators, and the wider school community will better understand the personal and professional needs of preservice teachers during their engagement in professional learning experience. Also, the findings may assist the development of preservice teacher education programs and contribute to an improvement in the quality of teaching and learning experiences, particularly for preservice teachers, their mentor teachers, and their school-based students. An outline of the thesis is provided below indicating the process taken for the research.

1.5 THESIS OUTLINE

In this chapter, the research problem was established: there has been no identified research that has explored the development of preservice teachers' professional teacher identity and practice through their participation in a year-long immersion pathway. This research fills that gap. The context for the research was described: the research followed the six preservice teachers' experiences in relation to their involvement in

becoming part of a school community for their final year of study. This immersion pathway offered preservice teachers an extended period of time for developing their professional practice which included a variety of learning experiences both in and out of the classroom. The significance of this research was outlined: as far as the researcher knows, there has been limited research that has drawn on situated learning theory in relation to the exploration of preservice teacher professional development and the formation of teacher identity during engagement in an immersion pathway.

In Chapter 2, the sociocultural theoretical and conceptual foundation of the study is presented. In particular, situated learning within a CoP (Wenger, 1998, 2000) is described as the key theoretical framework used to understanding the perceptions of participating preservice teachers. The influence of preservice teacher professional identity formation through professional experience is presented as well as a discussion on the role of professional artefacts, reification, and tools upon the formation of teacher identity is described. The chapter also considers the literature describing the several different relations of a school CoP that have an impact on preservice teachers' developing teacher identity such as: with supervising teachers, with students, between the school and the university, and with the larger school community.

Chapter 3 presents the theoretical framework for the research: Lave and Wenger's (1991) and Wenger's (1998) notion of situated learning in a community of practice. The 'situatedness' occurs primarily in the school settings but also refers to the school-university connection that contributed to preservice teachers' identity development.

In Chapter 4, the research design is discussed in terms of the methodology informing the study and the research methods, the justification for the case study design, and a discourse about the use of an interpretive-based approach to analyse the experiences. Data collection methods employed in the research included: semi-structured one-on-one interviews, semi-structured focus group interviews, the collection of professional artefacts, and an online discussion board. The method of data analysis is described as well as ethical considerations undertaken to complete the research.

Chapter 5 reports the findings of the research in relation to preservice teachers' participation in a year-long immersion pathway and changes over time in the development of their teacher identity and sense of belonging.

Chapter 6 presents a discussion of the research findings in relation to the theories and former research described in Chapter 2 to situate the research in the field. The discussion centres on the significance of preservice teachers developing relationships in a school community to enhance their development of teacher identity, appropriate teaching practices, and philosophy of teaching.

Chapter 7 discusses the major findings from Chapter 6 under themes derived from the data, accounts for limitations in the current research, provides the conclusions of the study, and makes recommendations for future research in the area.

Chapter 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

INTRODUCTION

The current research explored how preservice teachers form their professional teacher identity through participation in an immersion pathway in a school-based CoP (Wenger, 1998). This chapter provides a literature review describing key influences that contribute to preservice teachers' professional teacher identity development and practice for the preservice teachers in the current research. The chapter begins with a focus on teacher identity (section 2.1) including the potential for identity development to inform and shape preservice teachers' teaching philosophy. Of importance to the current research in teacher identity development are preservice teachers' developing self-images as a teacher (section 2.1.1) and how they are related to their developing philosophy of teaching (section 2.1.2). The next section (2.2) explores different kinds of immersion programs that allow preservice teachers more time in schools to engage and become members of the school community which, consequently, allows them more time to develop their teacher identity and practice. Of particular importance for the current research is immersion in CoPs (section 2.3). Section 2.4 is a review of literature describing the significant relationships within these school communities. Significant relationships include those developed between preservice teachers and their school supervising teachers (section 2.4.1), the relationships between preservice teachers, their university supervisors and school staff (section 2.4.2), between preservice teachers and school students (section 2.4.3), and the impact these relationships have on developing a teacher identity and practice. This section of the chapter also considers the effect of personal characteristics of preservice teachers on relationships (section 2.4.4). Section 2.5 provides the conclusion of the chapter. The chapter begins by describing how the various aspects of learning and experience are incorporated in the development of teacher identity and practice.

2.1 TEACHER IDENTITY

The focus for the current research was exploring preservice teachers' professional teacher identity development and practice through engagement in an immersion pathway. As stated in Chapter 1, there is no consensus on what researchers mean by the concept of teacher identity (Beijaard et al., 2004). Common attributes that have been associated with the notion of identity are that it is dynamic, multidimensional and shifts over time due to the influence of both internal and external influences which occur in the daily lives of individuals. Individuals continually engage in an ongoing process of negotiating and renegotiating their identity as it is continually shaped and reshaped by experience (Beauchamp & Thomas, 2009; Poulou, 2007; Wenger, 1998). Olsen (2008) described that preservice teacher identity development is fluid and is formed by way of ever-changing contexts and relationships in which the preservice teacher is engaged. Beauchamp and Thomas (2009) described that consideration needs to be given to the link between teachers' personal and professional selves and that teachers' stories of identity formation grow within the continually changing context of schooling. Farnsworth (2010) concurred with this idea and extended it by suggesting that identity can serve as a bridging concept to explore the dynamic relationships between individual learning and socially situated learning, such as school communities; and is negotiated with respect to preservice teachers' lived experiences and culturally informed reflections on those experiences.

There is growing research that considers first-year preservice teachers' feelings of preparedness for teaching (Daniels, Radil, & Wagner, 2016; Swabey, Castleton, & Penney, 2010). In particular there is growing research identifying a need to focus on supporting preservice teachers' knowledge and understanding of working with diverse learners to improve attitudes toward inclusive education (Forlin & Chambers, 2011; Taylor & Ringlaben, 2012). This research has found that preservice teachers' attitudes toward teaching have a strong and direct bearing on their levels of confidence to teach and their developing teacher identity and that there was a need for better support for preparing preservice teachers to become classroom ready. At present there is little research that considers fourth-year preservice teachers' developing teacher identity in a year-long immersion pathway and no studies have been located by the researcher

that consider this focus within a theoretical framework of Lave and Wenger's (1991) situated learning in relation to preservice teachers' perceptions of feeling and being classroom ready. The current research fills this gap in our understanding of teacher identity development.

The individual's perception of who they are and how they are situated in a community can be considered to be central to identity formation. Burke and Stets (2009) suggested that identity is a set of meanings that define who one is as an occupant of a particular role in society, a member of a particular group, or when one claims particular characteristics that identify her as a unique person. Identity can be constructed through the individual's moment-to-moment negotiation of her acting with mediated meanings (Wertsch, 1998). Mediated meanings occur when the individual interacts with others to gain an understanding of who she is within a particular situation. A preservice teacher will have many different experiences that occur through her engagement with other people in the many and varied school settings (for example, the classroom, the staff lunch room, the school playground) and through various tools in relation to her practice (for example, lessons, resources for teaching and learning), all factors that need to be considered in relation to understanding preservice teachers' identity development. A perspective on the meaning of teacher identity encapsulated by Harlow and Cobb's (2014) description of it being a self-attributed notion constructed through teaching experiences and knowledge about teaching was the starting point for exploring the development of a professional teacher identity for preservice teachers in the current research.

A nascent teacher identity: It has been suggested that preservice teachers enter ITE with a nascent teacher identity formed through preconceived ideas about what teachers are and what teachers do; however, these identities are often based on erroneous assumptions and may be quite unrealistic (Darling-Hammond, 2006; Korthagen, 2004). For example, preservice teachers may have idealised images of themselves as teachers nurturing student learning. In this idealised vision of themselves preservice teachers may not also consider the everyday work of sourcing information for preparing lessons, controlling student behaviour, and working within a system they have little control over that are the realities of an everyday school life as a teacher. In a study by Beltman, Glass, Dinham, Chalk, & Nguyen (2015) of

preservice teachers' professional identity development, the authors posed the question of what kind of teacher those individuals hoped to become. This Australia-based study of 125 preservice teachers, who were in the first year of their four year undergraduate course and had not yet undertaken a formal field placement in a school, found that the participants represented their 'future teacher self as positive, confident, capable and happy' (2015, p. 242). Yet, Beltman et al. argued that while the preservice teachers in their study presented an image of themselves as future teachers, they seemed to offer no hint of potential future challenges that might destabilise these individuals' positive emotions as they encounter the realities of teaching. The kinds of constraints that preservice teachers may face when they enter the teaching profession have been described by Pillen, Beijaard, and Den Brock (2013) as being connected to tensions about their wanting to: care for students versus being expected to be tough; invest in a private life versus feeling pressured to spend time and energy on work; and experience conflicts between their own and others' orientations regarding learning to teach. Pillen et al. suggested that these tensions were often bound by negative feelings, like feelings of insecurity or feelings of helplessness. While preservice teachers may not have developed perspectives of their future teacher self in relation to the realities of their teaching lives, they do have past experiences of teachers which have value in the early stages of their development of a professional identity.

There is research available which suggests that preservice teachers often decide upon teaching as a career pathway because of prior positive experiences of schooling, for example, learning with a favourite teacher that they had and developing a desire to be like that favourite person (Calderhead & Robson, 1991; Flores & Day, 2006). Flores and Day (2006) found that preservice teachers wanted to become teachers who could emulate the positive student-teacher relationship that they remembered having in support of their own learning. Their study identified that preservice teachers relied on their historical knowledge of teachers to determine who they did and did not want to be as teachers. In particular the preservice teachers in Flores and Day's study wanted to be like their former teachers who were liked and respected and wanted to avoid any negative student-teacher relationships they may have experienced as a student so that none of their students would have to go through what they perceived to be a poor learning experience. This theme of connecting prior knowledge and experiences of schooling to current preservice teachers' identity

development is a common one in the literature (Chong et al., 2011a; Furlong, 2013; Trent, 2011) and can be described as connecting to the historic practices of teaching.

Some researchers (Battey & Franke, 2008; Wenger, 1998, 2000; Wertsch, 1989, 1997) have described that historic practices can occur in the form of past educational and work experiences, and that school-based experiences play a significant role in the personal and professional beliefs that preservice teachers hold about teaching before they actually engage in a school community as a preservice teacher. Beattie (2000) noted that many preservice teachers initially understand teaching as showing, telling, and performance, partly due to their limited time in school communities before they graduate. In a study conducted in Ireland, Furlong (2013) explored the influence of life histories in shaping preservice teachers' professional identities. In this study fifteen postgraduate preservice teachers completed a short questionnaire and participated in an interview describing their identity development from being a student to becoming the teacher they envisioned themselves to be in the future. The preservice teachers recalled former teachers they admired as students. How closely the preservice teachers perceived their supervising teachers as meeting their idealised standards had an impact on how they saw their future selves as teachers and was a significant element in how they perceived good or bad teaching and themselves as potentially good teachers. For these preservice teachers, good teachers earned respect from their students and fellow teachers whereas bad teachers did not have that respect in the classroom. The preservice teachers expressed a desire to be a good teacher who was remembered and who made a difference in students' lives; they also described a need to have a balance between being a teacher who commands respect but is also one who is fondly remembered. Furlong found that these preservice teachers relied on memories of their own schooling and applied these memories to what they observed, experienced, and learned in their training to become a teacher. The participants also had to deal with how some of these memories were challenged by what they saw in the classroom against what they desired to become and do as teachers. Sometimes what they expected and wanted to happen did not happen. The preservice teachers then had to work through this conflict between expectations and the reality of teaching to better understand what it meant for them to be a teacher.

The development of a preservice teacher's professional teacher identity is a paradoxical struggle for the individual which is influenced by her history and her contemporary experience. This conflict is described by Trent (2011) who conducted a Hong Kong-based study of 6 participants training to be English teachers. This study found that while identity formation is a 'becoming' that reflects an ongoing and flexible process of construction, it is done so against already formed ideas of who preservice teachers believe they are and who they believe they should be. As Furlong (2013) found, the preservice teachers in Trent's study described good teachers they had from their memories of being students, describing how they wanted to be like these teachers and wanted to make a difference in students' lives once they became teachers. These preservice teachers wanted to inspire students as they had been inspired by innovative teachers they had in the past but felt frustrated by what they perceived were the rigid and traditional teaching practices of their current supervising teachers in schools.

With consideration given by the researcher to the notion that preservice teachers tend to enter teacher education with an idealised image of teaching, yet with little knowledge of the everyday realities of a teacher's life, further studies were explored to understand the formation of preservice teachers' nascent teacher identity. In agreement with the argument put forward so far, Correa, Martinez-Arbelaiz, and Guteirrez (2014) described that the formation of a professional identity was a process of personal maturation that begins informally before preservice teachers begin their teacher education. Correa et al. advocated that preparing and placing preservice teachers in school settings helps them develop such understandings, particularly if the partnerships are viewed as communities of learning. In these communities, preservice teachers learn how to become teachers partly through experiencing what these researchers described as 'critical incidents' of teaching (Tripp, 1994, 2012). The authors described that learning through negotiation of actions to resolve critical incidents is significant in allowing preservice teachers to test out, interrogate, and negotiate their teacher identities further. In Correa et al.'s (2014) study one preservice teacher found that her idealised perception of being a teacher had to be suppressed in deference to what she thought she should be as a teacher as learned in her coursework and through expectations of her school placement. In this described critical incident, the preservice teacher wanted to comfort a student who was being bullied with physical affection but had learned in her coursework that it was not appropriate or acceptable

for her to have physical contact with children. This event left her angry and frustrated because she wanted to champion the cause of the child but also wanted to behave as she perceived she was expected to behave as a preservice teacher. The preservice teacher was left conflicted; it appears that she did not seek the support or guidance of her teacher because she observed that the other teachers in the schoolyard did not react to the child's distress. She interpreted this as the accepted behaviour of teachers and thus felt that she had missed the opportunity to interrogate how such a teaching situation should or could be managed as she had anticipated it should be.

The purpose of participation in a school community is to provide preservice teachers with many and varied opportunities to learn the practice of teaching and to understand how to work through such critical incidents. In a UK-based qualitative study of 25 student teachers who had completed their initial teacher training, Mutton et al. (2010) found that while all of the student teachers learned from their school-based experiences, the depth of that learning varied considerably depending on the expectations of, and responses to individual experiences at school sites. Learning for student teachers was considered in relation to how well they perceived it supported or constrained their development as teachers. Effective support ranged from targeted feedback provided by their mentor teachers to making student teachers feel welcomed and part of the school community. Constraints to learning occurred when student teachers felt that they were not made fully aware of the expectations of them in a particular setting, situations with which they demonstrated a lack of knowledge or expertise in the teaching-learning scenario, and when they felt a lack of power and a pressure to conform to situations that they did not fundamentally agree with. Mutton et al. concluded that learning is more than likely to be context specific in nature and that a proactive and experimental approach to learning is conducive to student teachers learning successfully and transforming in their identity from a student teacher to a beginning teacher. These authors suggested that student teachers need to come to an understanding that while the act of teaching is important, equally important are the attitudes with which student teachers approach their learning experiences.

The literature reviewed so far clearly indicates that preservice teachers need time and guidance on how to make connections between their preconceived ideas of teachers and teaching and the realities of being a teacher. It appears that preservice

teachers need to make a transition in their thinking to understand that developing perceptions of themselves as a teacher is different from their early perceptions of teachers gained when they were students. The intersection between idealised memories of teaching and the realities of teaching has been described by Wenger-Trayner and Wenger-Trayner (2015) as a ‘boundary’ within a ‘landscape of practice’. In these early stages of their teaching careers preservice teachers are somewhat protected in that they do not have the full responsibilities of a teacher. Nevertheless, being now part of the teaching community if even only on the periphery (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1998), preservice teachers’ identities are undergoing a transformation as they continually learn more about teaching and what it means to be a teacher through their coursework and through practice in school placements. A suggestion from the above studies indicates that preservice teachers may need more opportunities to understand the real-world dynamics of teaching as an everyday practice through their coursework training to dispel some of the idealisation of being a teacher (Castellanos Jaimes, 2012; Chong et al., 2011a; Pellegrino, 2010).

Wenger-Trayner and Wenger-Trayner (2015) suggested that while crossing these boundaries within communities is not unproblematic, the process is unavoidable and holds the potential for unexpected learning. Through the sharing of knowledge and experiences in both their teacher training courses and school placements preservice teachers have many and varied opportunities to challenge their preconceived ideas about teaching and gain new insights and understandings of what it means to be a teacher. Therefore, preservice teachers need to learn to accept that they will be transformed in their thinking and actions through their teacher training. There is a growing area of research that has explored the transitions from idealised and abstract images of teachers to the development of preservice teachers’ self-image as a teacher, as described below.

2.1.1 Developing a Self-image as a Teacher

Research has found that self-image and self-confidence can influence the perceptions that preservice teachers have of their school-based experiences and reciprocally, that school-based experiences can influence preservice teachers’ self-image and self-confidence as teachers (Church, 2010; Hagstrom & Wertsch, 2004;

Izadinia, 2015). It can be argued that a 'clear self-image and ownership of an emerging professional identity' are conditions that help preservice teachers to apply knowledge acquired from teacher education programs into professional practice in the future (Bennett, 2012, p. 55). Yet, the perceptions that preservice teachers hold in relation to their developing teacher identity can be challenged when they are confronted by new or conflicting experiences. Chong et al. (2011a) noted that preservice teachers can be greatly influenced by what they perceive to be the intrinsic value of teaching and learning that becomes a motivating factor for them to initially enter into the teaching profession but that these perceptions need to be continually revisited at the various stages of teacher identity development. In this sense, developing a professional teacher identity is likely to be an ongoing process of interpretation and reinterpretation based upon how the preservice teacher sees herself and how others see her. Perceptions will change as she spends time in collaborative learning communities with continuous associations with university lecturers and tutors, professional experience school-based mentors, other teachers, and other professionals in those schools. O'Neill and Stephenson's (2013, p. 45) research revealed that on the whole preservice teachers left teacher training 'only moderately prepared' to manage classrooms near the end of their coursework with decreased levels of confidence in their abilities to manage disruptions to classroom routines and noncompliant behaviour compared with when they began their teacher training. This study found that a lack of confidence had the potential to undermine preservice teachers' willingness to try out new teaching strategies and impacted on their perceptions of self as a teacher.

As previously discussed earlier in this section, the development of one's identity is influenced by self-perception which is shaped and reshaped by experience (Beauchamp & Thomas, 2009; Poulou, 2007; Wenger, 1998). Of significance to the current research was Day and Kington's (2008) tridimensional perspective of how preservice teachers identify themselves as teachers. The first dimension 'professional' identity refers to the social and institutional influences of what a good teacher is and the educational ideals of a teacher. An example of professional identity is the expectation that a preservice teacher should participate in professional development seminars and workshops alongside teachers in the school community as that is what is expected of teaching professionals. King and Lau-Smith (2013), for example, described a program of reflection on learning and practice for preservice

teachers. In this program teachers and teacher educators supported preservice teachers in developing their personal and professional growth through attendance in bi-weekly meetings, developing a portfolio, and attending seminars. Preservice teachers were provided with guidance on how to identify their personal strengths, differentiate between internal and external obstacles, and describe how they could use their core qualities to achieve their ideal goals as teachers. Combined, these activities helped to support preservice teachers' professional identity development. Grundnoff (2011) suggested that if preservice teachers are not exposed to the full range of teaching work and responsibilities they can develop unrealistic understandings and expectations of what it means to be a teacher.

The second dimension 'situation-oriented' identity refers to the identity of a preservice teacher within a school or classroom and the influences of the surrounding environment on the preservice teacher. For example, at the start of a lesson, a preservice teacher stands before her class group, initiates a greeting and the students reciprocate with a mutual greeting and the lesson ensues. In this situation, the preservice teacher exhibits the identity of being a leader and facilitator in the classroom situation. Lamote and Engles (2010) found that with more experience preservice teachers became less focused on managing teaching tasks such as teacher-controlled behaviour management to a more student-focused approach to teaching. The authors postulated that over time the preservice teachers would become more aware that teaching involves more than only teaching lessons and that they must respond to sometimes unexpected situations in the classroom. According to Daniel, Auhl, and Hastings (2013) preservice teachers need time to rehearse the core skills of teaching in classroom situations. In the current research, that engagement in the year-long immersion pathway allowed the preservice teachers the needed time to develop these skills.

The third dimension 'personal' identity refers to influences located beyond the school environment, such as family and friends. An illustration of personal identity can be a preservice teacher enjoying a weekend lunch with friends. Although the preservice teacher can be identified by her professional ambitions, she is also a member of society and a friend among peers outside of a professional setting, as well as a teacher-in-training. Family, friends, and colleagues can affirm her status as a

teacher-in-training and, thus, contribute to strengthening her self-identity as a teacher (Olsen, 2010; Trent, 2011). It is considered in the current research that these three dimensions played a role in assisting preservice teachers' teacher identity development.

Identities can be understood as being multiple and cultural products, that is, products of a cultural environment, such as a school community. With this context in mind, these identities serve as a motivation for action and are socially constructed in the various domains of an individual's everyday life (Holland & Lachicotte, 2007). An example of multiple identities for a preservice teacher would be that they and others recognise them as being a student, being a preservice teacher on professional experience, being a friend, a colleague, a sister, a mother, and so on. Danielwicz (2001) suggested that preservice teachers need to engage in a process of self-reflection about their growing professional identities based on their observations and experiences to provide a lens through which that individual can develop an understanding of who she is within her multiple roles and how others see her. This view is echoed by many other researchers (Freese, 2006; Walkington, 2005). Danielwicz theorised that identities are created through recursive representation, that is, through a process of representing and re-representing the self to others in the form of actions and/or behaviours and that these representations are embedded in the flow of social interactions in specific contexts.

Preservice teachers' negotiation of their multiple identities was explored in a study by Dang (2013). In this Vietnam-based study, two preservice teachers who were sharing a practical placement discussed the multiple identities they developed through their interactions with friends, and while being students and preservice teachers. These preservice teachers had to cooperate in their planning and teaching with their preservice teaching partner and this close collaboration revealed a strong need for flexibility to work as a team member. The divergent approaches of the two preservice teachers to teaching indicated that the diverse histories of the two participants resulted in each bringing different perceptions to the planning and teaching sessions. Both preservice teachers drew on their own histories in shaping their professional identities but in order to work harmoniously they needed to consider the history and experience of the other. Their different approaches came in a large

part from who they perceived a teacher was, based on their prior perceptions of teachers when they were students. The one participant, for example, who was focused on content of teaching, was trying to do what she perceived teachers do while the other participant had moved beyond this stage to begin thinking like a teacher and so was focused more on interactions with students to engage them in learning: that is to say, not what a teacher does but who a teacher is.

The above section has identified that identity is a multifaceted concept that is formed partly by an individual's self-perceptions and partly through an individual's social interactions. The literature suggested that developing a professional teacher identity begins before preservice teachers engage in teacher training and is continually shaped and reshaped in the various social contexts of their training as they progress through their course - through the dynamic influences of their coursework, their school placements, and their personal selves.

The research reviewed also indicated that preservice teachers generally keep some kind of reflective practice about their teaching experiences; however, these reflections are not a shared artefact between teacher education coursework and on-site placements in schools as part of their coursework. One manifestation of reflection on their teacher identity that appears to be a common activity for preservice teachers worldwide, however, is the articulation of their teacher identity through a written declaration of their teaching philosophy (Caires, Ameida, & Vieira, 2012; Cattley, 2007; Haymore Standholtz, 2011). A teaching philosophy is meant to encapsulate preservice teachers' identities as graduating teachers professing themselves to be school-ready. Through their philosophy of teaching statement preservice teachers have the opportunity to formally demonstrate the many ways they are ready to be a teacher, as described below.

2.1.2 Philosophy of Teaching

As part of the process for teacher registration in Queensland, graduating teachers must submit their philosophy of teaching as part of their employment application (QCT, n.d.-b). The preservice teachers in the current research were all in their final year of a four-year BEd program and so developing a teaching philosophy was a requirement for them. This being so, it is important to consider the purpose of writing

a philosophy of teaching and how such writing may contribute to preservice teachers' developing teacher identity. To date, there is scant literature that specifically defines what is meant by one's teaching philosophy. A review of the literature identified a study by Moseti Ongaki (2014) which found that the development of teaching philosophy can be variously described or interchanged with terms such as teachers' beliefs, values or teachers' reflections on their knowledge of teaching. A danger that comes with this lack of clarity, Moseti Ongaki suggested, is that the writing of one's teaching philosophy can become a generic activity done simply to complete a course requirement needed to gain employment. Indeed, it has been suggested that without explicit guidance on its purpose the document itself cannot explain in any depth how preservice teachers' pedagogical philosophies are related to epistemological beliefs or preservice teachers' perceived future effectiveness as teachers (Moseti Ongaki, 2014; Sung, 2007). There is a dearth of literature that provides light on whether preservice teachers, as part of their teacher education, are being taught how to write their teaching philosophy in a way that will clearly articulate what they want to convey about themselves as future teachers.

Several studies have pointed to the development of one's teaching philosophy as being dynamic in nature and evolving over time through the individual's participation in educational settings. McDermott (2008) described that developing a teaching philosophy is a complex process and, therefore, not a static 'thing'; instead it shifts over time and in relation to preservice teachers' engagement in different contexts and the different relationships made along the way that contribute to shaping their beliefs. These beliefs and ideals are continually being filtered through the context of coursework and teaching practice in schools; however, it appears that preservice teachers are apt to describe what they believe they are required to describe but may not actually understand how to document what they have learned in their teacher education course as a profound expression of their teaching philosophy.

Preservice teachers' ability to align their knowledge of teaching with their philosophy of teaching during teaching practice emerges as a potentially significant enabling or constraining influence on the development of one's teaching philosophy. Castellanos Jaimes (2012) found that preservice teachers are not always able to connect theory to their own beliefs and understanding. When preservice teachers were

taught about student-centred learning, for example, they could describe the benefits of this learning approach orally in tutorials and in their written essays; however, when they were in schools many of the preservice teachers' teaching approach did not align with their idealised vision of teaching but was instead a teacher-centred approach they had described they did not want to do. This finding is problematic because it clearly demonstrated that the preservice teachers were providing a kind of 'lip-service' about their teaching philosophy rather than deeply internalising what their real philosophy was.

The implications of these findings for teacher educators is that preservice teachers need explicit guidance in understanding how to make the connections between their teaching beliefs and experiences and their teaching philosophy. Preservice teachers need guidance on how to critique teaching and learning theory on more than just a surface level and make connections from this learning to their teaching practices (Arrastia, Rawls, Brinkerhoff, & Roehrig, 2014; Castellanos Jaimes, 2012). Simmons et al. (1999) described this process as 'making explicit our implicit beliefs as well as our assumptions and values of our worldview' (p. 932). When preservice teachers are guided on how to reflect on their teaching philosophy they are able to gain a better insight about their beliefs and reveal inconsistencies in those beliefs, particularly in relation to their teaching practices. Simmons et al. suggested that preservice teachers develop their pedagogical philosophies through their perceptions of their social experiences. These experiences are filtered through the Vygotskian (1978) notion of symbols, particularly through the symbol of language as it is through the medium of language that members of the school and education community construct, exchange, and negotiate shared meaning.

Several studies have found that school-based professional experiences can influence preservice teachers' developing philosophy of teaching. Preservice teachers' perceptions on their first contact with teaching practice while studying to become teachers was explored by Caires et al. (2012) who conducted a quantitative study of 295 Portuguese high school preservice teachers enrolled in a graduate program. One month before the end of their teaching practice participants were asked to describe their perceptions of their teaching practice experience. The preservice teachers described their growing levels of autonomy, self-confidence and trust about the

quality of the skills, and knowledge that they acquired during teaching practice. While participants felt that teaching practice was a stressful and demanding period involving an increasing sense of weariness and vulnerability, the data in this study also revealed preservice teachers' positive perceptions of their growing knowledge and skillfulness, their increasing sense of efficacy, flexibility and spontaneity in their performance, and interactions as classroom teachers. In another study, Haymore Standholtz (2011) researched teaching practices of 290 preservice teachers enrolled in undergraduate and graduate programs who completed seventy hours of professional experience in either primary or secondary schools over a twelve-month period. Throughout the program, the preservice teachers were required to write their reflections-on-practice to develop a sense of awareness of their teaching practice. This study found that the factor the preservice teachers most commonly linked to effective instruction was student participation. The preservice teachers recounted various strategies for involving students, highlighting the use of visual representation, games, and hands-on activities. A third of the participants described a detailed account of student understanding and they discussed factors such as building on students' prior knowledge, connecting to students' experiences, checking for understanding, and addressing needs of all learners. In this study preservice teachers frequently expressed the need to align their teaching with their professional teaching standards and to cover established curriculum during a set time frame. Preservice teachers in the current study were not required to take on a teaching role in the immersion pathway; however they were required to align their teaching with the AITSL (n.d.) during their professional experience placement in preparation for writing their philosophy of teaching statements.

Engagement in self-reflection can influence preservice teachers' development of a philosophy of teaching. Gilbert (2009) described preservice teachers' writing of philosophy statements as tools to critique their lesson planning and teaching practices with their teaching beliefs. In a small scale Australia-based qualitative study by Cattley (2007) preservice teachers were required to engage in reflective writing exercises in order to consider their responses to, and observations of, various elements of the teaching environment such as daily classroom interruptions, parent liaison episodes, and staff room activities. Findings indicated that completing reflections provided preservice teachers with a more thorough understanding of the

breadth and complexity of the teacher's role in professional teacher identity formation. In the current research the preservice teachers, as fourth-year students, were thinking about their teaching philosophy for teacher registration at the end of the year. Participation in the year-long immersion pathway contributed in part to how they saw their teaching philosophy develop over the course of the year and so the current research contributes to the wider research in this area. The experiences shared by the preservice teachers in the current research, about their teaching practices, their successes and failures, and their self-reflection on professional practice was integral to developing an understanding of their evolution as emerging teachers through their involvement in the immersion pathway.

2.2 PRESERVICE TEACHER IMMERSION PROGRAMS

It has been suggested that teaching experience for preservice teachers combines educational theory and real-world in-school activities and relationships with experiential knowledge as the heart of professional development (Harris, Jones, & Coutts, 2010; Korthagen, 2004, 2010). It should be noted that while all teacher education courses include professional experience at the heart of the program, the amount of time dedicated to these placements varies considerably from university to university and may vary in length and the content covered depending on the stage of enrolment in the course. For example, preservice teachers in the initial stages of their course may spend as little as two weeks in school placements whereas in their final year they may spend several concurrent weeks in a school placement. The lengthened time in schools at the end of their teacher education is an acknowledgement that the preservice teachers have learned enough to be classroom-ready as more responsible teacher colleagues in ways they would not have been able to portray during the early stages of their teaching program.

In the Australian context of the role that preservice teacher education programs have in the development of professional practice for preservice teachers, Mayer et al. (2014) reported in their *Longitudinal Teacher Education & Workforce Study* that teacher education providers were expected to prepare preservice teachers to design and report assessment data in ways that established learning goals and informed the practice of evaluating learning activities, as well as improving student outcomes. This

longitudinal-based report concluded that the majority of teacher education providers had partnerships with schools or school clusters designed to improve the quality and effectiveness of professional experience.

The identification of key components of effective professional experience in ITE in Australia was the integral focus of an Australia-based study by Le Cornu (2015). Seven key components of professional experience were identified by Le Cornu as playing a key role in ensuring that ITE programs are of high quality, they are as follows: well-structured integrated ITE programs; well-managed integrated ITE programs; well supported integrated ITE programs, high quality supervising teachers; high level commitment from School Leadership; high quality school-university partnerships; and high quality systems-based partnerships. The integration of these key components into ITE programs around Australia was considered by Le Cornu to complement the existing national approach to program accreditation which outlines requirements to ensure high quality ITE programs (AITSL, 2011). These standards and procedures were described by Le Cornu (2015) as forming part of a current national commitment to teacher quality which requires both school-based and university-based teacher educators to provide evidence that graduates can demonstrate professional knowledge, practice, and engagement (AITSL, 2015).

In the case of preservice teacher education, a school provides a place of opportunity for preservice teachers to learn the profession of teaching in a formal workplace setting (Maaranen, Heike, & Krokfors, 2008; Serota & Bennett, 2007). The school symbolises a workplace testing ground in which preservice teachers can begin to demonstrate that they understand what it means to be a teacher, a step that affords them membership into the teaching profession (Fanthome, 2004). The aim of an effective school-based placement, then, is to help preservice teachers combine what they have learned in university coursework with what they learn in schools during a practicum. In the four-year BEd primary program referred to in the current study preservice teachers are required to spend 80 days of professional experience, and a 20 day internship in schools during their ITE.

The integration of knowledge between university studies and school-based contexts can be understood as an *expansive learning environment* (Pridham et al., 2013). An

expansive learning environment is multidimensional where learning occurs through participation in different forms such as at university, in schools, through professional and personal dialogues. Learning in this way thus becomes a shared practice. Pridham et al. Australia-based case study explored enablers and constraints that preservice teachers experienced in an expansive work-based learning practicum. The researchers in this study tracked 20 preservice teachers who were participating in a two-day per week practicum over a full semester in four different secondary school sites; rather than in a four-week practicum block in a single school setting as is the norm. Pridham et al. found that preservice teachers did not feel a strong sense of belonging when they perceived there were constraints blocking their participation in the school community. Constraints such as a lack of mentoring, a lack of communication, no sharing of resources and feelings of isolation were perceived to be powerful differentials between them and the school staff resulting in the preservice teachers feeling left out of meetings and other activities of the school community. Consequently, these preservice teachers felt marginalised in their school placements. The biggest enabler for them in this program was found in the open-space staff office where they could either be involved in or listen to the professional conversations and/or planning meetings between staff members. This kind of engagement could be described as a vicarious form of participation, yet it appeared to have been helpful for these preservice teachers.

The observation and practice of classroom-based teaching practice, such as classroom management, behaviour management, and teaching duties can influence the development of preservice teachers' professional practice and professional teacher identity. In their Australia-based qualitative study of 120 second-year preservice teachers in an undergraduate teacher preparation program Subban and Round (2015) explored preservice teacher observations of differentiated learning in classrooms. In this study, a focus group discussion revealed the preservice teachers' awareness that the organisation of the classroom allowed teachers to divide their time comfortably between whole-group teaching and small-group or individualised instruction, that lessons were structured and developed efficiently around student needs, and that explicit modelling of class rules and routines by the teacher created a cohesive learning environment. The current research explored the significance of preservice teachers' observations of teaching practice and engagement in authentic

teaching experiences as integral to their perceptions of developing a professional teacher identity.

There is recent research (Edwards & Mutton, 2007; Ferrier-Kerr, 2009; Serota & Bennett, 2007) which suggests that preservice teacher immersion programs through complementary partnerships between universities and schools demonstrate a shared commitment to providing professional learning opportunities to teachers where participation in the immersion program is characterised by a mentor-mentee relationship-oriented experience. In Ferrier-Kerr's (2009) study, the preservice teachers spent a large amount of time engaged in gaining practical classroom teaching experience under the guidance and support of a supervising teacher. In such environments, it was suggested, preservice teachers have greater and longer opportunities for observing their supervising teacher's teaching and for being observed and critiqued by their supervisor while practising and developing their teaching skills. The primary focus of any preservice teacher immersion program then would be to develop strong relationships with their supervising teachers and other school staff to assist and enable preservice teachers to adequately prepare for and to deal with the realities of school culture.

The realities of school culture that preservice teachers encounter in immersion programs is not only shaped by the 'here and now' of their engagement in school-based professional experience. Preservice teachers bring a range of lived experiences with them which shape their perspective on teaching during their engagement in immersion programs. Maaranen et al. (2008) suggested that immersion programs prepare preservice teachers by allowing them to integrate their past experiences, including those related to work, academic studies and schooling with theoretical knowledge, concepts, and practical applications in classrooms. However, in their study the preservice teachers preferred their own 'traditional' schooling as familiar and more comfortable approaches to teaching and resisted experimenting with more 'risky' approaches they were less familiar with. It could be speculated that these preservice teachers may have placed more value on what they perceived to be 'real' teaching, as demonstrated by their supervising teachers, rather than trying to integrate learning from both their teacher training and their learning in the school setting.

In another study that explored the development of preservice teacher professional identity development in a school-based immersion program, Schmidt (2010) found that what preservice music teachers valued about their teaching experience was the provision of autonomy in classroom teaching and planning, the development of contextual teaching knowledge, and a sense of community during their professional experience. This study focused on six recently graduated teachers who described a strong connection between their coursework and the experiences of teaching they had in school placements. These connections provided them with a range of alternative learnings about teachers and teaching and allowed them to view their coursework as meaningful and applicable to classroom settings. They developed a sense of belonging in the teaching community and so felt confident in their identities as teachers. Similar findings are mirrored in the literature, for example, Chong et al. (2011b) found that preservice teachers valued professional experiences gained through immersion, such as the development of their self as a role model and their professional growth as a teacher.

Further recognition of the value that immersion programs can have for preservice teachers in supporting their application of theoretical coursework knowledge in a professional context is found in Coffey's (2010) study of nine American preservice teachers entering a graduate school teaching program. This study researched participants' experiences through daily debriefing sessions, self-reflective journals, and online discussion board entries. Over a two-month period the preservice teachers expressed that school-based experiences in association with university-based theoretical learning provided them with a better understanding of how to interact and communicate with students in multiple contexts. Their accounts provided evidence that the course content, coupled with experiential experience in the classroom helped bridge the gap between educational theory and classroom practice. Moreover, these preservice teachers had the opportunity to engage in weekly conversations with students, parents and volunteers within the school community which provided further enhancement to their learning. The current research also utilised an online discussion board as a data collection technique and although it did not specifically collect the preservice teachers' requisite reflective logs, the preservice teachers in the study continually referred to these logs when describing their engagement in the immersion pathway.

There is a growing interest in offering preservice teachers opportunities for engagement in immersion pathways in addition to the traditional, mandatory professional experience placements. For example, Ferfolja's (2008) study of 14 Australia-based preservice teachers engaged in an immersion program over four months and found that benefits from engaging in an immersion program were multifaceted and preservice teachers were exposed to a considerable range of professional duties connected with the profession of school teaching. For example, in addition to the management of curriculum planning and delivery, pedagogy and assessment, preservice teachers gained first-hand insight into classroom management, parent and/or community interactions, and extracurricular activities such as going on camp, sports activities, and organising a science competition. The preservice teachers in this study were able to appreciate that teaching is a multifaceted profession and being allowed to participate in many of these activities helped them to gain a positive sense of themselves as teachers.

In contrast to Ferfolja's study, the current research explored preservice teachers' professional teacher identity development through their participation in a year-long immersion pathway. As described in Chapter 1 (see section 1.1) the preservice teachers participated as volunteers in the school community, learning about the many and varied activities and responsibilities of being a teacher that they would not have learned on a four-week professional experience placement. This kind of placement was different to formal professional experience in that the preservice teachers were not in the schools to specifically teach, although they did take up opportunities to teach when requested by their supervising teachers. Their immersion was seen as a pathway rather than a formal program; as a pathway their engagement in the schools allowed them to explore aspects of school functioning that they would encounter and be expected to participate in as graduate teachers. The pathway was also different to formal teacher education/school partnerships in that there was no obligation on the school's part to evaluate the preservice teachers' performances, unlike the situation for a mandatory four-week professional experience placement.

2.3 IMMERSION PROGRAMS AS COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE

Of particular interest to the current research was the focus on CoP immersion pathways in relation to teacher identity development. Although not originally focused on teacher education, CoP theory has been embraced by educators as an easy fit in that the foundation of education is in the various relationships within the school community. Preservice teachers must find a place for themselves within the community as part of the process in developing a teacher identity. Identity formation assumes that learners must make sense of and give meaning to the content of learning. Working with others, preservice teachers gain a greater understanding of teaching and teachers and, subsequently, who they are within the teaching community. Burke and Stets (2009) described that it is the individual's perceptions of who they are and how they are situated in a community that is central to identity formation. While Ten Dam and Blom (2006) suggested that in a school community preservice teachers must engage in a shared interpretation of meaning about teaching through shared practice. The shared practices can occur in multiple sites such as learning through coursework at a teacher education institute or through engagement in school placements. In a school environment the preservice teacher as a community member learns to take responsibility for her own role in relation to others (for example, supervising teacher, students, etc.) and the totality of the school community.

Ten Dam and Blom (2006) explored teacher identity development in a collaborative school-based CoP of teacher education between a school in Amsterdam and the University of Amsterdam. Participants included 5 preservice teachers, their teacher mentors, university-based tutors, and the deputy principal of the school. These preservice teachers were involved in the program which spanned a year of their course. The program involved the preservice teachers having opportunities to learn to be teachers and to participate in critical reflection on their membership in the school community to make teacher education more meaningful for both preservice teachers and the school. As the year progressed, the preservice teachers in this study came to feel that they were treated as teachers or novice teachers, that they were listened to by staff, and made contributions to the school like any other staff member. The teacher mentors expected the preservice teachers to participate in all school activities alongside their professional colleagues which resulted in the preservice teachers

feeling pressure of expectations from both the schools and their coursework at the university. While these preservice teachers felt a responsibility toward their students, they felt less responsibility for the communal, professional improvement of education at the school and so did not feel that they were full members of the school community.

Preservice teacher CoPs have been considered in relation to situated learning within preservice peer communities rather than a transition between schools and teacher education institutes. Bond (2013), for example, established professional learning communities where 20 secondary preservice teachers met four times over fifteen weeks in small groups of 5 students each to share their experiences of: teacher education coursework; developed artefacts from their professional portfolios; and to offer peers emotional support. Preservice teachers in this program were not provided with extra training on how to operate as group members or how to hold professional conversations with peers and so they did not have a clear understanding of the purpose of the meetings or how to behave during the meetings. It was found that the preservice teachers were focused mainly on their own personal problems rather than on discussing how to address learning for students in practicum classrooms. In contrast, Daniel et al. (2013) established peer CoPs with a focus on professional conversations with shared language and repertoire for first-year preservice teachers. In this program 65 preservice teachers in the first semester of their course worked together as an organised and highly structured community aimed at developing the core practices of teaching. Initially, preservice teachers worked in small groups of 2 to 4 members to rehearse teaching practices, which were video-taped. These small groups then formed larger groups of 12 with each group paired with an academic who acted as a group mentor. In these larger groups, members received training on how to give and receive constructive feedback from peers which was then considered as a collaborative critical reflection. Reflected practice was embedded throughout the program allowing preservice teachers many different ways to practise and develop this skill. The authors suggested that peer support was essential for the success of the community. It would seem from these two examples that structure and a clear and collective understanding of the function of the community is also necessary. In Bond's (2013) example, preservice teachers became disengaged as they did not understand the purpose of the community or their role in it. In contrast, preservice teachers in Daniel et al. (2013) program had a clear structure, support, and shared repertoire and so they were able to see themselves as productive,

contributing members of the established community.

Communities of practice have been looked at in other ways in education. For example, Iyer and Reese (2013) considered a sense of belonging for a group of culturally and linguistically diverse preservice teachers. In this study, the preservice teachers described themselves as different to the majority of white, Anglo-European Australian (domestic students), with 24 coming from East Asian, Pacific Islander countries or India and two identified as being Indigenous Australians. They found little evidence of CoP practices established in university tutorials for these preservice teachers who struggled to connect with the majority of preservice teachers. Further, the domestic preservice teachers exhibited a lack of understanding of different cultures. The preservice teachers in the study indicated that they felt isolated and that they were 'expected to act like Australians' to be included as a member of the community. In school settings, membership and a sense of belonging was dependent upon feelings of being welcomed or not welcomed by the supervising teacher. The study found that preservice teachers who encountered obstructions to shared repertoires resulted in these preservice teachers failing to become members of the community, or becoming marginalised at best. Iyer and Reese advocated the need for there to be a purposeful attempt to acknowledge difference as pluralism rather than an accommodation of difference.

In another form of CoP, Harlow and Cobb (2014) reported on the perceptions of preservice teachers who were in the first semester of the first year of their course and who were engaged in a collaborative program between participating schools and the teacher education institution. In the program, preservice teachers attended school-based tutorials which included hands-on practice in schools as a shared responsibility for teacher education. Findings suggested that this program provided preservice teachers with a 'more realistic and authentic understanding of what it means to be a teacher' (Harlow & Cobb, 2014, p. 70). The preservice teachers described that they had a greater understanding of the complexities of being a teacher and felt they were able to connect the theory of their coursework with the practices in schools. An important feature of this program was the opportunity for preservice teachers to engage in professional conversations with peers and with their supervising teachers. Those who found it easy to engage in these conversations obtained a greater sense of

belonging to the school and those who struggled to initiate or participate in such conversations felt a lesser sense of belonging. In observing their supervising teachers, the preservice teachers in the study described a better understanding of the need to build strong relationships with students to create effective learning environments.

The significance of relationship development to preservice teachers during their school-based professional experience was noted by Fenton-O’Creevy, Dimitriadis, and Scobie (2015), who described that identity formation involves an emotional investment and that tensions can exist when preservice teachers are challenged to adopt either a teaching approach or a personal approach (or both) in which they do not believe; in this sense the pressure associated in crossing boundaries (or feelings of being limited by boundaries) must be ‘continually negotiated but never entirely resolved’ (p. 38). Fenton-O’Creevy et al. suggested that dealing with the challenges of learning in a CoP is not peripheral but core to identity development. Learning is not only about ‘learning to do’ but also and equally important ‘learning to be’ (p.41); therefore, preservice teachers need to be encouraged to explore how to identify themselves as teachers. As indicated above, building strong relationships with supervising teachers, students, and other school staff is fundamental for preservice teachers’ identity development and sense of belonging as members in the teaching community. As evidenced from previous studies these relationships are the foundations for preservice teachers to feel included as members of the particular school community where they complete their professional engagement placements and, thus, play a significant role in shaping their developing teacher identity and practice. The following section describes relationships which are significant to the enablement of teacher identity development.

2.4 RELATIONSHIPS

Research has suggested that preservice teachers need to experience *being* teachers in order to make that transition in perception of self in relation to teacher identity (Darling-Hammond, 2012; Fenton-O’Creevy et al., 2015; Korthagen, 2004). Harlow and Cobb (2014), for example, suggested that professional teaching experiences affirm for preservice teachers what it means to be a teacher and that these perceptions are strengthened when preservice teachers feel that they are

accepted members of the school community. Furthermore, when preservice teachers feel like they have been accepted as a member of a school community they expressed more positive feelings about teaching and themselves as teachers. Relationships which are formed in the school context are crucial for a sense of belonging. The building of these foundations for their developing sense of identity depends on the support and acceptance preservice teachers feel from teachers, students, school administration, and all stakeholders in the school community (Caires et al., 2012; Darling-Hammond, 2010; Ferrier-Kerr, 2009; Korthagen, 2010). The support preservice teachers receive can either encourage and enable or discourage and constrain engagement in the development of a positive teacher identity (Graham & Roberts, 2007; Mueller & Hindin, 2011). Waddell (2010) suggested that a recognised way to retain teachers in the school system is to support them in a context that fosters positive relationships. Preservice teachers who value school community-based relationships gain positively in relation to their developing teacher identity (Beattie, 2000; Joseph & Heading, 2010; Sexton, 2008; Timostsuk & Ugaste, 2010).

Wenger (1998) suggested that belonging involves more than engagement in the community, describing three modes that need to be considered: *engagement*, *imagination*, and *alignment*. Engagement is described as the ‘active involvement in mutual processes of negotiated meaning’ (p. 173). Developing relationships in the community is vital for such negotiations which occur as a threefold process: 1) the ongoing negotiation of meaning; 2) the formation of trajectories; and 3) the unfolding of histories of practice. As each community is unique the relationships within are bounded to that space. Therefore, engagement can provide rich histories of practices for new-comers to learn or can be an obstacle to learning if the relationships formed are not supportive. A sense of belonging through imagination refers to a ‘process of expanding our self by transcending our time and space and creating new images of the world and ourselves’ (Wenger, 1998, p. 176). Imagination in this sense refers to the production of images of self and the world that transcend engagement. How preservice teachers initially perceive teaching and themselves as teachers, as described earlier in this chapter (Calderhead & Robson, 1991; Flores & Day, 2006; Trent, 2011), involves the process of imagination in identity formation. Imagination can be mistaken but can also be enhanced through engagement of a shared reality in a community. In this, imagination is not an individual process but a collective process derived and developed

through engagement in the community, but not confined by it.

Alignment refers to the ‘coordination of...energies, actions, and practices’ (Wenger, 1998) of the community. In this form of belonging, participants align their practices with expected rules and practices of the community. Without aligning themselves to the rules, practices, and discourses of schooling, preservice teachers are likely to fail in their pursuit of becoming teachers. Amin and Roberts (2006) suggested that the influence of engagement in a CoP on an individual’s learning and identity development can be shaped by its lifespan: the longer the engagement in the community the more likely the chances of stronger identity development as the individual has more opportunities to learn what it means to be part of the community. The notion of belonging in a CoP will be explored in more depth in Chapter 3 of this thesis as it was an important factor considered in the current research.

The most significant relationships that preservice teachers will form in schools are those with their supervising teachers, also called mentor teachers (Kasperbaur & Roberts, 2007; Pellegrino, 2010; Santoro, 1999). Therefore it is important to explore these relationships as they may evolve through participation in an immersion pathway as these relationships form the basis of connectedness and belonging to the school for preservice teachers and provide them with a compass on how to become a teacher in a particular setting. Preservice teachers need to rely on more established members to guide them along and this guidance inevitably involves power relationships, as described below.

2.4.1 Relationships with Supervising Teachers

It needs to be acknowledged from the outset that a preservice teacher’s relationship with a supervising teacher is inherently a power relationship which has the potential to work in a mutually supportive way or, conversely, can provide negative learning experiences. Preservice teachers’ relationships with supervising teachers can be considered to be the most vulnerable element of their school-based professional experience placement (Broadley & Ledger, 2012). Graham and Roberts (2007) and Mueller and Hindin (2011) suggested that power can be both positive (a preservice teacher works with a supportive supervising teacher and, as a result feels that she

has learned and grown as a teacher) or negative (the preservice teacher feels marginalised because she is not included in school activities for one reason or another).

Hodkinson and Hodkinson (2004), for example, referred to the uneven power balance between a preservice teacher on school placement and their supervising teacher. This imbalance of power is a legitimate concern as such a power imbalance will ensure that preservice teachers in reality are peripheral members in as much as they are not fully qualified teachers in the classroom. Preservice teachers can see themselves as non-experts with little to contribute while in school settings if they are not encouraged, or are fearful to participate in the activities and conversations of the school. Nevertheless, in spite of this power status preservice teachers can feel like full members of the school community if they are in a supportive and welcoming environment. Fuller, Hodkinson, Hodkinson, and Unwin (2005), for example, found that when preservice teachers are seen by the school community as contributing members not only is their learning enhanced but the learning of the school community is enhanced. Teachers often take on supervision of preservice teachers to increase or reinforce their understanding of the latest theory and/or trends in teaching.

Preservice teachers who complete their school placements in supportive environments have the potential to grow as teachers in positive ways (Hudson, 2013). Researchers (Graham & Roberts, 2007; Mueller & Hindin, 2011) have suggested that preservice teachers who complete their school placements experiencing difficulty to find support still have the potential to grow but may have more of a struggle than others. In this, Lave and Wenger (1991) and Wenger (1998, 2000) cautioned that one must look beyond the simple conflictual perspectives of power (power as domination, oppression or violence) to a more complex and multifaceted construct. Power is associated with the different levels and kinds of engagement of the various participants in a community and how these different kinds of engagement are played out through various activities.

Lave and Wenger (1991) suggested that participation in any community is always based on a situated negotiation and renegotiation of meaning related to that community's activities, ideals, and practices. Because they are not fully qualified teachers, preservice

teachers can be seen to be working on the periphery of school communities while they learn how to become teachers. Lave and Wenger described this placement as peripheral participation in a CoP where transformations occur between new-comers (preservice teachers) and old-timers (qualified teachers) in the context of changing practice. The changing practice in this context can be seen as preservice teachers sharing new knowledge/theory with their supervising teacher that may or may not be incorporated into teaching practice and the sharing of knowledge of supervising teachers to guide preservice teachers. The relationship is a complex one in that at times the preservice and in-service teacher are sharing knowledge but at other times the preservice teacher is fully aware of the power imbalance between them. A more thorough exploration of this theory is described in Chapter 3. While Lave and Wenger (1991) acknowledged the possibility of unequal power relations existing within communities, Hodkinson and Hodkinson (2004) suggested that in their notion of CoPs that Lave and Wenger (1991, and Wenger (1998), do not deal with this consideration effectively in determining how this factor may have an influence on the individual's capacity to learn and interact within the community. It is postulated in the current research that it was important to consider these relationships to understand the impact they may have on preservice teachers' developing identity and practice through their year-long participation in the immersion pathway.

An important element of a preservice teacher's school-based professional experience is the internship and the relationships formed during this phase of teacher identity development. The internship often comes toward the end of her time in a school community and situates the preservice teacher in a teaching role that she is expected to manage with a degree of autonomy. Ehrich and Millwater (2011) explored the micro-politics of preservice teachers completing a four-week internship. As described by these authors, internship differs from formal professional experience placement in that these kinds of placements come at the end of the BEd course and are largely unassessed placements. During their internship, preservice teachers take on a 50/50 relationship with their supervising teacher, taking on more responsibility as the weeks go by. The longer the preservice teacher is in their internship the more responsibility she takes on board, which results in a power shift between her and her supervising teacher. Ehrich and Millwater found that the more successful internships were ones that included a strong level of communication between the preservice teacher and supervising teacher, with

good development of cooperation, collaboration and congeniality. Building and maintaining trust was a key element in the relationship. Positive relationships occurred where both the preservice teacher and the supervising teacher felt confident to discuss and negotiate issues. These findings are similar to those of Graves (2010) who found that when communication broke down the school placement was put in jeopardy. Graves identified the three themes of: expectations, communication, and time as critical for preservice and supervising teachers to negotiate. Preservice teachers begin their placements with expectations of what they would like to learn and these may not always align with the expectations of their supervising teacher. Good communication is the only way to resolve any differences and understanding generally needs to evolve over time or misunderstandings need to be resolved for both parties to feel confident in the support of the other. Graves (2010) described that there is a need for both to understand their roles and responsibilities in order for the school placement to be successful.

Practicum-based professional experience related relationships have been explored by researchers to understand how these relationships influence preservice teachers' development of a professional identity and a sense of belonging in a school community. In Santoro's (1999) study of two preservice teachers' experiences on professional experience, one of the preservice teachers had a good practicum at the school whereas the other preservice teacher did not. The differences in the two experiences were attributed to the power each of their supervising teachers held in the relationship and how the supervising teachers positioned the preservice teachers in the class and in the school as well as in the ways the preservice teachers were allowed to access the knowledge and practices of teaching in the class. The support the preservice teachers received either encouraged or discouraged their engagement in teaching and the development of a positive teacher identity at the school. The warmth, acceptance, and level of friendliness afforded to preservice teachers as they enter a new school community impacts upon their sense of professional identity (Caires et al., 2012; McNally, Cope, & Inglis, 1997). McNally et al. in their study of secondary school preservice teachers noted that the initial feeling of welcome and warmth shown by supervisors developed into preservice teachers being treated as a colleague and developing feelings of being 'one of the team' (p. 492). These feelings then contributed to the preservice teacher's level of confidence (McNally et al., 1997) and a growth in their skills and knowledge (Caires et al., 2012) which is an

important part of status transition from student to teacher. Ambrosetti and Dekker (2010) found that it is generally accepted that the role of the supervising teacher is to provide support, explicit modeling of the job, and provide feedback on observations of the preservice teachers' engagement in classroom tasks. Supervising teachers' roles are dynamic and multifaceted and they change with the context.

Le Cornu (2010) described that teaching today has changed from the old paradigm of a teacher-centred approach as a result of changing political, economic, and societal issues and that supervising teachers must now take on more responsibility of preservice teachers' performance during school placements. Le Cornu, along with others (Ambrosetti & Dekkers, 2010; Ehrich & Millwater, 2011), advocated that there needs to be stronger ties between teacher education institutes and schools to better support both preservice teachers and school staff during school placements. Le Cornu (2009, 2010) suggested that there needs to be a reframing of preservice teachers' professional experiences in schools which would necessitate a shift in how all stakeholders see their roles in the process. Le Cornu advocated, for example, a need for more and better communication between schools and teaching institutions to grow a 'learning community model' with a focus on how best to support preservice teachers on how to develop into quality teachers. This notion of building stronger ties between school and teaching institutes is explored further in the next section.

In summary, the relationship between preservice teacher and supervising teacher is highly significant in assisting preservice teachers' developing teacher identity which evolves and transforms the longer the preservice teacher is in the school. This relationship has the power to enable or constrain positive identity growth and can be perceived by preservice teachers as more powerful than connections with university lecturers. These relationships appear to be strengthened when there is an alignment between learning at the school and learning at university. Walkington (2005) described preservice teachers' time in schools as a 'sharp learning curve' where they had limited time to learn about teaching and about themselves as teachers. Teacher education programs that connect learning between the school and teacher education institution appear to assist preservice teachers to not only change and grow in their teaching behaviours but build and transform their teacher beliefs and what it really means to be a teacher.

2.4.2 School-University Supervision Relationships

As described above, there is a general consensus that there needs to be strong connections between the learning that occurs at tertiary institutions and the learning that occurs in schools to assist preservice teachers in developing a teacher identity; they should not be seen as separate communities of learning. Harlow and Cobb (2014) suggested that when learning within these communities are seen as separate, for example, when preservice teachers cannot make connections between their coursework and the work they are asked to do on professional experience, the development of their teacher identity is compromised.

The literature revealed that preservice teachers differ in what they adopt in their role as developing teachers depending on how well they deal with the influences involved in their teacher training and on how much value they place on these influences as they relate to the school engagement (Ambrosetti & Dekkers, 2010; Ehrich & Millwater, 2011; Schepens, Aelterman, & Vlerick, 2009; Sutherland, Howard, & Markauskaite, 2010). The perceptions preservice teachers have of the connections between universities and schools in supporting the development of teacher identity is a common theme. Flores and Day (2006), for example, found that preservice teachers described their teacher education at university as weak compared with what they learned about teaching on their school placements. These preservice teachers felt that they had learned to become professionals through the act of ‘doing’ teaching rather than through any of the coursework completed at university, indicating that these preservice teachers felt that there was little synergy between the two sites of learning. Sutherland et al. (2010) described this situation as a mismatch of knowledge and understanding between university learning and situated learning in schools and advocated that preservice teachers need multiple opportunities to self-label as teachers and that partners at both learning sites need to play a coordinated role in providing these opportunities.

Walkington’s (2005) study also indicated that there needs to be closer ties between the learning preservice teachers are engaged in through their coursework and learning that occurs at schools during professional experience and that preservice teachers’

professional teacher identity development needs to be encouraged and supervised by both throughout their degree. Walkington suggested that the groundwork needs to be started at the university where coursework activities are designed to draw upon the personal qualities and capabilities of preservice teachers and that this process should be continued at schools. Ten Dam and Blom (2006) suggested that school staff generally do not take on the responsibility of professional development of preservice teachers and are interested in the contributions preservice teachers can bring only if it does not interrupt the rhythm of their class and the school. These findings echo those of Le Cornu (2010), Ehrich and Millwater (2011), and others, who suggested a need to provide training for both preservice teachers and their school supervising teachers on the roles and responsibilities of both to work toward the common goals of a successful school placement for both. Ehrich and Millwater (2011), for example, described that school-based mentors should be provided with opportunities to understand the micro-politics inherently involved in school placements to work toward improving engagement with teacher education institutions. These recommendations reflect Le Cornu's (2009, 2010) observation that today's school-based placements operate differently to how things were done in the past and that all stakeholders need to work differently together to create successful and responsible school-based placements for all involved.

In their study of Singaporean preservice teachers Chong et al. (2011a) found that at the beginning of their professional experience, preservice teachers commonly demonstrated closer ties with formal sources of support, that is, feeling closer to their university teachers than with their school-based supervising teachers. Over a period of time, however, these preservice teachers found increasing value in informal sources of support, such as with peers at university, other teachers in the school community, and friends outside of the school community. In contrast, Pellegrino's (2010) findings resembled those of Flores and Day (2006), where preservice teachers' perceptions were that learning at the university did not match what was expected in the class. Four out of the five preservice teachers in Pellegrino's (2010) study emulated their supervising teachers' behaviour management strategies rather than try to utilise what they had learned at university, citing that the university classes they took were not very useful in the real classroom experience. It was through their actual participation in the classroom community that these preservice teachers

reported that they were able to understand how to use behaviour management strategies and this learning was influential in shaping their teacher identity. These findings indicate a need to help preservice teachers make connections between learning in both sectors for their teacher education.

Transitions in preservice teachers' perspectives on sources of professional support which serve their teacher identity development has been discussed by several researchers. Schepens et al. (2009) described that most teacher education programs continue to teach from a positivist academic tradition where preservice teachers learn theory in their teacher education coursework but fail to integrate theory with practice when they go out on professional experience. Their study found that while teacher education programs make a difference in shaping teacher identity, it was not the most important variable. What was most important for the preservice teachers was whether or not they felt prepared skill-wise for the teaching profession as they embarked on professional experience placements. As with Pellegrino's (2010) research above, Laker, Laker and Lea's (2008) study found that the higher education institution became less influential as preservice teachers progressed through their professional experience. In this study there was a shift away from the university-based input from lecturers and tutors into an evolving dependency upon school-based sources of support such as those established with their supervising teachers and other teachers at the school. Laker et al. suggested that the shift away from university-based sources of support toward school-based sources of support demonstrated the willingness of preservice teachers to be socialised into schools where they feel that they are able to identify themselves as being members of the school community. In related research, Allen and Peach's (2007) Australia-based qualitative study of 34 preservice teachers explored connections between on-campus and school-based experiences of a teacher education program. Their study found that almost one-third of the preservice teachers acknowledged the value of networking and sharing when dealing with unfamiliar problems which meant generating conversations with members of the school community other than the supervising teacher alone. Support and communication from these professional sources enhanced opportunities for networking and the sharing of strategies to deal with unfamiliar situations such as classroom management concerns or the delivery of pedagogic knowledge.

Other research indicates that a broad-based structure of support, both school streamed and university streamed, can provide a valuable contribution to enabling the application of preservice teachers' theoretical knowledge and its practical application in school-based professional experience. MacDougall, Mtika, Reid, and Weir (2013) considered the school-university collaboration as a triad of preservice teachers, supervising teachers and supervisors from the university connected with professional experience placements in schools. In this study the university supervisors visited the preservice teachers twice during their placements in schools as a way to strengthen the learning connection between the university coursework and learning at the school for the preservice teachers but also to create stronger ties between the schools and the university. The authors posited that there was a need for strong communication channels necessary to build a relationship of trust and support for all stakeholders, and that the communication needs to be reciprocal with some elements of less formality at times to establish a sense of collegiality between the school and the university staff.

How well these relationships did or did not work or had an impact on the quality of the engagement preservice teachers had completing their immersion pathways in schools were considered in the current research to understand preservice teachers' perceptions of their developing teacher identity.

2.4.3 Relationships with Students

Another significant relationship for preservice teachers is the relationship that they develop with their students. These relationships can enhance, or detract, from the preservice teacher's professional experience and professional teacher identity. According to Appl and Spenciner (2008) and Hong (2010), healthy, productive working relationships with students contribute to the sense of ownership and responsibility that preservice teachers need to acquire to fulfil the role of a teacher. A sound rapport between preservice teachers and their students fosters greater understandings for the preservice teacher about how to effectively engage in their role of facilitating their own teaching and the learning outcomes of their students. Appl and Spenciner's (2008) three-year long, US-based qualitative study, for example, investigated the role of 82 early childhood preservice teachers in providing positive social learning environments for their students. Their research found that the

participants progressively developed a greater awareness of their role as a teacher as a result of their working with students. In providing support to students, the preservice teachers felt that they were enacting the practices of being a teacher. Similarly, Hong's (2010) US-based mixed-methods study of 84 preservice and beginning teachers found that when preservice teachers demonstrated the ability to build professional relationships with students their confidence in being a professional teacher grew. Although this study considered the perceptions of preservice teachers and beginning teachers, rather than only preservice teachers, the significant conclusion drawn here indicates a link between professional teacher identity and professional relationships with students.

Teacher-student relationships are a well-documented phenomenon in research, as argued by De Jong et al. (2014). However, these relationships are mainly focused on in-service teachers while less is known about characteristics of preservice teachers in relation to the teacher-student relationship. In their Netherlands-based quantitative study of 130 preservice teachers they found that preservice teachers used strategies based on reward and recognition because these appeared to them to create more student experienced affiliation; which the authors described as 'the emotional distance between teacher and students, ranging from hostile to warm' (p. 295). This study indicated that students were more positively responsive to preservice teachers they perceived to be kind and friendly. This is an interesting finding as, described earlier (see section 2.1), it is a focus for preservice teachers going into schools that they are perceived as kind for students to accept them as 'good' teachers.

Preservice teachers' perceptions of their ability to relate to, and manage their relationships with, students can be influential on their developing teacher identity. A study by De Jong, Van Tartwijk, Wubbel, Veldman, & Verloop (2013) researched 34 student teachers' patterns of interpersonal behaviour as perceived by the students they taught as well as the accuracy of preservice teachers' self-belief regarding their interpersonal relations with students. This study found that at the beginning of a year-long internship in which they taught for approximately 50% of the time preservice teachers in general underestimated rather than overestimated themselves both on class control and affiliation with students. However, at the end of their internship this was reversed where more of the preservice teachers overestimated than

underestimated themselves. Similarly, the preservice teachers underestimated their levels of control and affiliation at the beginning of their placement, whereas at the end of the internships the majority were overestimating themselves. This study concluded that overestimation could be the effect of a conflict between how preservice teachers feel they are perceived and how they want to be perceived throughout the course of their school placement. Edwards and Protheroe (2004) suggested that preservice teachers learn how to behave as teachers by observing how it is done by expert teachers. Observing how to speak with students, using both verbal and non-verbal language, when to intervene to manage behaviour and what strategies to use as most appropriate for a given situation can contribute to a preservice teacher's understanding of the subtle nuances of teaching that she may not have learned in her university coursework. It may be that preservice teachers in the study by De Jong et al. (2013) found more affiliation, and therefore more value, in their association with school staff than with those in their teacher training institution because it was more hands-on teaching in the schools.

Of interest to the current research were the changing perceptions that preservice teachers develop about their relationships with students and how these relationships relate to the development of their professional identity and practice in a CoP. An examination of preservice teachers' perceptions on their image of themselves as teachers was conducted by Woods, Barksdale, Triplett, and Potts (2014). In this US-based qualitative study of 50 preservice teachers in an elementary education graduate program, participants were tracked over two university semesters which totaled 12 weeks of school-based professional experience. Participants were asked to answer questions through their creation of drawings and briefly write comments in connection to their drawings as a means of providing personal interpretations of those drawings. A key finding from this research was that in the first semester of the study preservice teachers had a strong focus on becoming warm, nurturing teachers who established strong relationships with students. Yet, by the end of the second semester, preservice teachers were showing less concern about emotion and compassion and a greater focus on meeting academic goals for students. These findings by Woods et al. (2014) link in with the notion that preservice teachers experience a tension between developing a warm, caring, and positive relationship with students while maintaining the need for discipline (Weinstein, 1998).

Weinstein's research study (1998) of 141 preservice teachers' perceptions on care and order demonstrated that preservice teachers need assistance in understanding how to enact both care and order in broader terms and to see that positive interpersonal student-teacher relationships contribute to order, and to creating safe and productive classrooms, which are enacted through a pedagogy of care. The role of preservice teachers' perceptions of their identity as teachers was explored in the current research.

2.4.4 Effect of Personal Characteristics of Preservice Teachers on Relationships

Although little research has been conducted in this area it is important to begin exploring the characteristics of preservice teachers, particularly their age and parenthood status as today's intake of preservice teachers has changed in recent times from first-year students enrolling directly from high school, to a much more diverse group of first-year intakes across teacher education worldwide. This changing pattern of age at enrolment in teacher education was found in the current research where three of the participants were young, single women (in their early twenties) and three were older (in their forties) and mothers of young children. The researcher, therefore, felt there was a need to understand if there are different perceptions of developing a teacher identity between these two groups and if so what are the differences?

Wright (2013) studied the reasons why mature-aged mothers chose to train as childcare workers and found that the women described 'drifting' into the profession based on prior work as volunteers or teacher aides at childcare centres. None in Wright's study described choosing a career in teaching for economic reasons; instead, in spite of the low pay, many were seeking satisfaction in other ways such as a change of status from mother to teacher, a perceived raise in self-esteem and the anticipation of future possibilities. These mothers acknowledged that a change in one sphere of their lives would inevitably change others and believed that the changes in their family lives would be benefited by a change in their working lives as teachers. The mothers in this study sought a balance of priorities but always placed family needs first before planning for the other areas of their lives.

Additionally, Duncan's (2000) study produced similar results with mature-aged mothers who were preservice teachers. In this study, it was found that prior

experiences, both publicly and privately, helped to alert the preservice teachers to potential difficulties they may face in their program. The study found that the 'older' women were able to negotiate strong relationships with their supervising teachers whereas the younger teachers in the study described that they generally felt intimidated by their supervising teachers and the power difference that they felt. Whether the older women felt less intimidated because they were mothers or because of their greater life experience was not clearly described but the researcher proposed in the current research that it was an area worth exploring more. Bukor (2015) explored the 'sense-making' of three teachers in relation to the relevance they made of their life experiences to their teaching and found that family relationships, particularly relationships with mothers (in this study) had a profound effect on shaping teachers' identities and feelings of competence as a teacher.

The demands placed upon preservice teachers when fulfilling the role of being a parent and at the same time learning to become a teacher through participation in school-based professional experience was explored by White (2008) who wanted to understand how mothers navigated the dual roles of being preservice teachers and mothers. This study revealed that the mothers in this study had chosen to enroll in teacher education only after they had spent the formative years of their children's lives at home with them. Once their children were firmly established in schools, these preservice teachers felt they could manage both roles. The study found that many of these preservice teachers struggled to meet the demanding needs of both roles and this was particularly evident when they were required to teach full days in school during their professional experience placements. The study found that some of the preservice teachers' children resented the time taken away from them for their mothers to study and attend classes but the preservice teachers felt strongly that they had something to offer as teachers and as parents and continued on with their studies.

As mentioned earlier, there has been little research done in relation to the professional teacher identity development of mature-aged mothers who are preservice teachers. Although not originally an area anticipated for the current research it happened that the issue did arise and so the researcher would be remiss not to mention it as a possible factor for the preservice teachers in their teacher identity development.

2.5 CONCLUSION

This chapter has explored the literature related to preservice teachers' professional teacher identity development through participation in professional learning experiences. Preservice teachers enter preservice teacher immersion programs with a nascent teacher identity formed through preconceived ideas and prior experiences. In immersion programs, the development of preservice teachers' teacher identity is shaped through preservice teachers' negotiation and renegotiation of mediated meanings, that is, the understanding that preservice teachers have of being a teacher through their interactions with others in particular situations relating to their school-based professional experience. The literature points to the need for preservice teachers to make a transition in their thinking to understand that developing perceptions of themselves as a teacher is different from their early perceptions of teachers gained when they were students.

Preservice teachers can be considered to be completing a short 'apprenticeship' when they attend placements in schools and are in need of guidance on how to understand and grow their teacher identity. Being situated in schools provides many and varied opportunities and learning activities that help shape a professional identity where preservice teachers can learn the language and behaviours of teaching. Preservice teachers require guidance on how to critique teaching and learning theory on more than just a surface level and make connections from this learning to their teaching practices which involves the development of a philosophy of teaching. Preservice teachers' self-reflection on their developing professional identity and professional practice provides them with opportunities to gain a more thorough understanding of the breadth and complexity of the teacher's role in professional teacher identity formation.

The notion of preservice teacher CoPs in relation to situated learning within preservice peer communities rather than a transition between schools and teacher education institutes has been discussed in this chapter. The ability of preservice teachers to access the knowledge and practices of teaching through their engagement in a school community and build relationships with members of their school communities, and in particular, their relationships with supervising teachers, fellow

preservice teachers, and students, are critical to the enablement of preservice teachers' teacher identity development and sense of belonging as members of the teaching community.

The literature indicates that there is a need for stronger alignment between learning that occurs in teaching institutions and learning that occurs in school settings as not all placements are positive experiences for preservice teachers. Several enabling and constraining influences on the development of preservice teachers' teacher identity and sense of belonging in a school community were discussed in this chapter in relation to preservice teachers' access to productive relationships in the school community, their involvement in professional conversations with school staff members, and their exposure to sufficiently high quality mentoring by supervising teachers. The current research explored preservice teachers' identity development as occurring within the community school placement in a year-long immersion pathway. The following chapter explores the theoretical background to this kind of placement.

Chapter 3: THEORY

INTRODUCTION

This chapter provides the theoretical background for the current research. Section 3.1 describes sociocultural theory which provided an overarching theoretical foundation. Sociocultural theory explains human functioning as occurring through individual development that is mutually constitutive within social and cultural activities. The social and cultural activities of the research are fourth-year preservice teachers' participation in a year-long immersion pathway in schools. Section 3.2 explores the application of Wenger's (1998, 2000) theoretical lens of community of CoP for understanding preservice teachers' identity development through engagement in the immersion pathway. Wertsch (1989, 1997) described that from a sociocultural perspective, professional experience-based activities can be viewed as inherently being situated in cultural, historical, and institutional settings. A description of situated learning relevant to the current research is provided in section 3.3. Section 3.4 explores practice as meaning in situated learning and considers the four key areas of: negotiation of meaning (section 3.4.1), participation (section 3.4.2), reification (section 3.4.3) and artefacts (section 3.4.4). It is posited in the current research that participation in the immersion pathway put the preservice teachers in a position of experiencing professional development in school settings that included an intermeshing of the cultural, historical, and institutional influences of becoming a teacher; these influences shaped their perceptions and practices as they developed their professional identity as a teacher. Section 3.5 provides the conclusion of the chapter.

3.1 SOCIOCULTURAL THEORY

Vygotsky's (1978) work provides a basis for much of our understanding of sociocultural theory. Theorists have built upon Vygotsky's work as it is applied to education, where learning occurs through participation in a broad range of joint activities and the effects of working with others (Bloomfield, 2008; Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1998). In the process of social and cultural interactions, individuals

acquire new knowledge of their culture, their world and themselves, and develop new strategies to better participate as a member within a community. Learning can be considered to occur as a result of the individual's social development, yet it can also be understood as occurring in relation to her cognitive development. For Vygotsky (1981), the connection between social and individual functioning is the result of mediated learning through semiotic mediation. Examples of semiotic mediation include: language, systems of counting, mnemonic techniques, illustrations, diagrams, maps, schemes, and symbol systems (Vygotsky, 1981). These means of mediation can aid in the appropriation of knowledge through representational activity by a developing individual. Appropriation is described by Rogoff (1995) as the resultant change that occurs from an individual's own participation in an activity. Bakhtin (1981) explains appropriation through the construction of knowledge as it can occur in language. For example, a word in language becomes the individual's own only when she uses that word with her own intention and voice and adapts the word to her own expressive intention. In that moment, the individual appropriates the word, that is to say, she adapts the word by developing a meaning from its use in the form of knowledge that can be used as her own. Appropriation is an important process whereby an individual reconstructs knowledge that she internalises where she makes that information important to herself, thus she transforms how knowledge is construed and used by herself and others (Grossman, Smargorinsky, & Valencia, 1999). An example of appropriation for a preservice teacher would be having her adopt her supervising teacher's classroom language to create a continuity of learning for the students under her guidance and supervision. Without such an appropriation where the preservice teacher may instead use unfamiliar language and meaning seemingly contrary to that used by the classroom teacher, students may become confused and turn away from learning.

According to the collected works of Vygotsky (1997) the individual's development occurs through mediated action; mediated action is the action of using objects such as cultural artefacts and tools to make something happen and for meaning to derive from these interactions. Artefacts can be understood to be objects, including items that have cultural and/or historical significance and are introduced and/or used by the individual in order to develop an activity in a cultural, institutional, and historical context. Artefacts relevant to developing preservice teachers' identities may include an

identification badge that provides recognition as membership of the community of teaching, a portfolio of teaching episodes or collected photographs or other forms of memory collections. Artefacts mediate the interaction of the individual with her environment and serve as a means by which she appropriates knowledge. Like artefacts, tools serve a purpose for community membership (Douglas, 2014; Wenger, 1998). Tools can be understood to be objects that shape teacher identity and practice through a process of reification and negotiation. An example of a tool used by preservice teachers is a school policy that outlines expected strategies for managing student behaviour.

As well as appropriation of language, Rogoff (1995) described participatory appropriation which occurs when the individual changes through her involvement in an activity and constructs knowledge that she can use to become prepared for subsequent involvement in related activities. Participatory appropriation is exhibited in a process of the individual changing and handling a situation in ways prepared by her participation in a previous, similar situation rather than as a result of simply acquiring knowledge. In the example of a preservice teacher mastering competency in time management during teaching practice, the preservice teacher appropriates knowledge through the feedback offered by her supervising teacher and through her participation in time management planning and application and developing an understanding of the strategies used by the classroom teacher as well as the school policy on behaviour management.

School-based experiences put the preservice teacher in a position of experiencing professional development in school site settings that have an intermeshing of cultural, historical, and institutional influences that shape their perceptions and practices as they develop their professional skills of facilitating teaching and learning. It can be argued that each school site has its own history; that members of its school community contribute to the cultural identity of the school environment; and that each school has an institutional social order in which their members function and cooperate with each other in that school's community. Social influences can be found in the interactions that the preservice teachers have with other people, namely: teachers, school staff, students, students' parents, peers, and other members of the school community. Cultural influences can be found in the shared use of cultural tools and practices (Gutiérrez &

Rogoff, 2003), such as calling the attendance roll at the beginning and end of the school day and participating in weekly staff meetings.

Preservice teachers construct and examine knowledge through social engagement (Harris et al., 2010) and different aspects of schooling can be either formal or informal in structure. A formal structure can be observed through university-based teaching and learning programs where preservice teachers may attend tutorials or workshops on a weekly or regular basis to discuss and share work integrated learning experiences on poignant professional learning issues. At school sites or in social settings beyond a university or school site preservice teachers may casually and informally communicate about their school-based experiences, again offering support, advice and camaraderie as empathetic peers. Preservice teachers gain professional and social identities through their position as interactants within a school community. Hagstrom and Wertsch (2004) argued that through the actions taken by preservice teachers during social interactions with others, identities are formed. These activities and gains in knowledge contribute to preservice teachers' appropriation process to become a teacher.

As described above, one's professional identity does not develop in isolation but within a community of like-minded professionals. The current research posits that preservice teachers' professional teacher identity developed within what Wenger (1998) describes as a *Community of practice* (CoP). The following section elaborates on the school environment as such a CoP.

3.2 COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

For the current research, social interactions deemed necessary for developing a professional identity were considered within a shared domain of learning in a Community of Practice (CoP). According to Wenger (1998), each community develops its own practices, routines, rituals, artefacts, symbols, conventions, stories, and histories. Being a member or becoming a member of a community necessitates knowing or learning about the cultural identifiers of that community which can only be gained through participation in the community. Knowing what is needed to become

a professional in a CoP involves both the competence that a community has established over time (for example, what it takes to act and be recognised as a competent member of the teaching community) and engaging in ongoing experiences of the community, both within the context of the community and beyond (for example, being recognised as a teacher both within school and within the wider community).

Communities of practice, according to Wenger-Trayner and Wenger-Trayner, B. (n. d.), ‘...are groups of people who share a concern or a passion for something they do and learn how to do it better as they interact regularly’. However, not everything called a community is a CoP. Wenger suggests that there are three main characteristics that need to be present in order for a community to be called a CoP: the domain, the community, and the practice. Domains are created by a shared competence ‘that distinguishes members from other people’. Preservice teachers are part of the domain of members training to become teachers rather than architects or firefighters. A community involves the joint activities, interests, and sharing of information that allows members to learn from each other. The practice includes the notion of shared practice where community members share a repertoire of resources such as experiences, stories and/or tools, to help them address recurring problems or new challenges. It is argued, without this combination of these three elements there is no CoP.

Wenger-Trayner and Wenger-Trayner (2015) suggested that there are three dimensions of CoPs in education: *internal* - organising educational experiences around subject matters; *external* - connecting students’ experiences to actual practices through peripheral forms of participation; and *over the lifetime of students* - serving the lifelong learning needs of students. The current research was particularly focused on the external dimension of the CoP because preservice teachers enter the classroom as trainees and never fully become classroom teachers during this training period. Therefore, they are peripheral participants in the classroom and the broader school community. For example, in a school setting a preservice teacher observes how a supervising teacher manages a classroom. It may not be obvious to the preservice teacher what specific theory or strategies of behaviour management the teacher is using and she becomes anxious because she knows the teacher will expect her to manage the class in a similar, but as yet unfamiliar way. The preservice teacher may have learned about different approaches to behaviour management at university but must now learn how to apply the

most appropriate one for this classroom. She must learn effective behaviour management strategies through conversations with her supervising teacher and through practising these skills herself. Also, the preservice teacher must learn the culture of the classroom and embed that culture into her teaching practice to work effectively in the classroom. According to Wenger's (1998) theory a preservice teacher in this kind of situation feels an 'urgent need' to align her experiences with that of the community in order to be accepted as a member. The practices she uses to indicate membership are externally based in the existing school community.

Wenger (2000) viewed learning in a social context as involving the competence that a community has established over time, that is, an individual in the community knows what is required to act and be recognised as a competent member of that community; being a member includes the individual's ongoing experience of the world as a member of the community and beyond. In this way, learning can be defined as interplay between social competence and personal experience and is formed by the relationship between people and the social learning systems in which they participate. Wenger (2000) considered that learning in social systems entails that community members experience a sense of belonging in three particular forms: engagement, imagination, and alignment, as described below.

Engagement as a mode of Belonging occurs where the individual learns what she can do and how the world responds to her actions. For a preservice teacher, one's active involvement in a school-based CoP can provide a space in which she can act and construct her identity through the creation of a shared reality with other members of the community. Engagement in a CoP is bounded in relation to the scope of activities, the number of people and the number of artefacts with which to sustain relationships and commitments; for example, one can only commit to being in one place at a time. The actions of the community are mutually negotiated toward the development of a joint enterprise that guides the community for continued learning. As Goodnough (2010) suggested, engagement as a mode of belonging for teachers involves sharing in activities and practices of the teaching community where members are able to determine, maintain and negotiate activities and practices and, in the process, create and recreate identities within the schooling community. Ngyuen and Sheridan's (2016) Australia-based study examined the impact of teaching practice on identity formation among language

background other than English (LBOTE) preservice teachers. Their research found that strong engagement with different stakeholders was an important factor for preservice teachers to gain a sense of belonging in the school community and for participation in a variety of school and staff activities, such as being given the opportunity by a mentor teacher to grade and supervise students.

Imagination: The second mode of Belonging is *imagination*, through which the individual constructs an image of herself and her community in order to develop her sense of self and awareness for interpreting her participation in the social world of her community. Imagination is defined by Wenger (1998) as the ‘process of expanding our self by transcending time and space and creating new images of the world and ourselves’ (p. 176). Imagination in relation to membership in a CoP involves removing oneself from direct engagement to examine actions from a historical perspective to understand ourselves and others better. In her study of Hawaiian preservice teachers, Au (2002) found that ethnicity and community membership had an influence on the perceptions and learning of preservice teachers. Historically, all public school teachers in Hawaii were native Hawaiians; however, in contemporary times native Hawaiian teachers have become a significant minority. Au observed that while talking with preservice teachers in a local community about the historical record of Hawaiian schooling that the Hawaiian preservice teachers with whom she was talking seemed to be heartened by this past accomplishment of their ethnic community. These preservice teachers were able to imagine their school system in a different way and imagine how they could possibly reinvent themselves and their teaching practices.

In another example, Gonzalez and Zapata-Cardona’s (2014) findings illustrated the concept of imagination as a mode of belonging whereby each experience leads the individual to an image of the past as well as to an image of the future. In this case the in-service teacher who had studied statistics at an undergraduate and postgraduate level felt a strong sense of admiration for his statistics teacher in high school. Past experiences coupled with present-day professional development as an in-service teacher encouraged this teacher to try to imitate a respected mentor and positioned him with a self-realised identity of being a statistics teacher. In this sense these memories and modes of engagement nurtured this preservice teacher’s imagination about belonging in the community of teaching.

Alignment: The third mode of Belonging is *alignment*, through which the individual positions her actions to be sufficiently aligned with other processes so that those actions can be effective beyond her engagement. Alignment refers to a mutual process of coordinating perspectives, interpretations, and actions so that higher goals can be realised, allowing the identity of a larger group to become part of the identity of the individual participant (Wenger, 1998). Alignment bridges time and space to coordinate and connect members of a CoP where they become a part of something bigger than the part each plays in the community. In this process, members align their practices of the community.

In Trent's (2012) study the teachers' alignment with the goals of the partnership was implied by their commitment to engaging in the practices and activities of the partnership and their alignment with its objectives for teaching and learning during their professional development experience. Ngyuen and Sheridan (2016) found that among the LBOTE preservice teachers the presence of other teachers who were also LBOTE themselves and spoke with accented English allowed the preservice teachers to not feel much different from other staff members. Ngyuen and Sheridan concluded that this type of alignment may result in a stronger sense of belonging to the community. Gonzalez and Zapata-Cardona (2014) identified that the alignment teachers may or may not feel for subjects that they teach can be associated with their satisfaction for teaching that subject and the self-perception that the individual has in seeing herself as a particular subject teacher.

The individual's development of a sense of belonging in a social learning system occurs through the coexistence of degrees and combinations of engagement, imagination, and alignment which can shape the individual's social competence and personal identity in relation to a CoP. Alignment can also have negative consequences where control can result in individuals being disempowered if they are engaged in practices which have little meaning for them (Goodnough, 2010; Wenger, 1998). The modes of belonging were important for the current research in understanding preservice teachers' identity formation.

To date no studies have been located that have focused on teacher identity development through preservice teachers' engagement in a year-long school immersion pathway; the current research fills this gap.

3.3 SITUATED LEARNING

The current research had a particular focus on preservice teachers' sense of belonging through engagement in an immersion pathway. According to the theory of CoP the immersion pathway can be described as 'situated learning'. Learning in situ, or 'learning by doing', refers to learning as an 'integral and inseparable aspect of social practice' (Lave & Wenger, 1991, p. 31) and affirms the concept that much of what is learned by the individual is specific to the situation in which it is learned (Lave, 1988).

The theory of situated learning (Lave & Wenger, 1991) sees learning as a situated activity in CoPs wherein the individual engages in social practice characterised by a process called *Legitimate Peripheral Participation* (LPP). As learners gain mastery of knowledge and skills they move away from the periphery of that practice as a new-comer and move toward full participation in the sociocultural practice of the community. Activity is situated in the community and learning is not about simply receiving knowledge, but instead is linked to the 'transformative possibilities of being and becoming complex, full cultural-historical participants in the world' (Lave & Wenger, 1991, p.32).

Learning in a school community becomes an improvised practice where the curriculum provides opportunities for engagement in practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991). Engaging in practice has been demonstrated to be critical in the effectiveness of learning (Bulunuz, 2012; Curtis, 2015; Sivan, Leung, Woon, & Kember, 2000). Learning by participation within a CoP provides the learner (variously known as the new-comer or the apprentice) with more than an observational perspective of the work done.

Bruner (1999) described this kind of learning as a participatory and proactive process resulting from discourse, collaboration, and negotiation. This absorption in learning occurs over an extended period of time and allows the learner to make

the culture of practice hers. As both an observer and a participant, the learner will gradually assemble and accumulate information and skills related to the practice of the community. The social context of the CoP offers exemplars, finished products, and relationships with other learners at different stages in the process of becoming full practitioners (Lave & Wenger, 1991).

In this study, each preservice teacher participated in the evolutionary process of gaining mastery of teaching practice through her ‘apprenticeship’ which is situated under the guidance of her supervising teacher. In relation to a traditional master-apprentice styled apprenticeship, the supervising teacher (or mentor) coaches the preservice teacher as an apprentice as she learns to apply the practice of teaching and being a teacher. However, Lortie’s (1975) notion of apprenticeship of observation suggested that preservice teachers acquire generalised notions of what ‘good’ and ‘bad’ teaching is based on how particular kinds of teaching have affected them. Feimennemser (2001) put forward that teacher educators need to take seriously the concept of preservice teachers as learners by recognising that they bring experiences with them, that their learning is continuous and dynamic, and that preservice teachers need to examine beliefs critically in relation to visions of good teaching. In the immersion pathway, it is reasoned that the images and beliefs preservice teachers bring into their school-based professional experience act as filters for new learning (Mewborn & Tyminski, 2006) and that their participation in school-based CoPs gives them opportunities to analyse their beliefs so that these beliefs can be developed and amended.

Wenger, McDermott, and Snyder (2002) suggested that there are seven principles to cultivating CoPs: 1) design for evolution; 2) open dialogue between inside and outside perspectives; 3) invite different levels of participation; 4) develop both public and private community spaces; 5) focus on value; 6) combine familiarity and excitement; and 7) create a rhythm for the community. Wenger cautioned that the design principles are not a recipe for creating a CoP but rather make explicit the possibilities of the community. Design for evolution refers to a community’s natural evolution based on existing networks and practices. In relation to the current research, the immersion pathway was a new design for most schools who participated; however, the community members had prior knowledge of preservice teachers coming to the

school for professional experience so needed only to evolve their thinking to incorporate what they already knew with the new concepts involved in participation in the immersion pathway; such flexibility in design needed participants from the schools and the university staff to engage in an open dialogue about expectations for preservice teachers and their supervising teachers, to engage in the pathway.

According to Cook and Brown (2005) and Rogoff and Angelillo (2002) individuals use knowledge as a tool, linking new knowledge and new practice into what is already understood. Individuals need to make sense of their world and how they learn depends on how they are able to engage with what is happening around them. While Lave and Wenger's (1991, 2000) notion of CoPs held significance for the current research there are various critical perspectives of their theoretical rationale. For example, Amin and Roberts (2006) suggested that the influence that a CoP may hold for the individual's learning and development can be shaped by its life span. A CoP may be established for a specific purpose such as a weekly teachers' e-learning workshop which is delivered for only one month. While members of this community can benefit from learning and gaining new knowledge during the workshops, the degree to which teachers mutually engage in learning and further develop their teaching skills can become limited. Once the four-week period is finished the CoP will not exist in its formal structure and opportunities to learn more about e-learning instruction are likely to end.

Daniel et al. (2013) described that as accepted legitimate peripheral participants in school communities, preservice teachers are able to fully participate in the activities of the community and in the process make meaning of what it is to be a teacher. Preservice teachers are able to gain entry into working beside the professional they wish to become by engaging in the activities of the community as well as engaging in constructing the language of the community as ways to be recognised and accepted in the community. It is posited in the current research that the duration of the connection with a school community during engagement in a year-long immersion pathway contributed to the development of preservice teachers' professional practice and identity in ways different to participation only in mandated professional experience placements.

3.4 PRACTICE AS MEANING

Wenger (1998) suggested that social communities, such as school communities, define practice. Practice is about meaning as an experience of everyday life and, for the individual, being included in what matters is a requirement for being engaged in a CoP. Of particular importance to the current research was the concept of practice as meaning, which explores the *negotiation of meaning*, *participation*, and *reification*, as well as the role of *artefacts* in understanding and making meaning of practice. The following section explores what these terms mean and how they related to the current research.

3.4.1 Negotiation of Meaning

Negotiation of meaning denotes ‘reaching an agreement between people’ through interactions within a community as a productive and continuous process which is historical (for example, is not simply made up on the spot), contextual, and unique. The process of negotiating meaning generates new circumstances for further negotiation, learning, and making meanings which results in the production of new relations with and in the world (Wenger, 1998, 2000). The meaningfulness of being a member in a community is found in the continual process of renewed negotiation, without this communal negotiation, failure to be accepted as a community member will occur. Negotiation cannot occur, therefore, without the individual’s participation in the community. An example of this kind of negotiation in the current research would be the preservice teachers negotiating with their university coursework supervisor to be accepted as a volunteer in the immersion pathway and before this the negotiations between the university supervisor and the various schools to determine the parameters for having preservice teachers volunteer. It was important from the start that all stakeholders related to the immersion pathway shared a common understanding of the need for the program and how each participant would benefit through engagement as a shared enterprise (Ehrich & Milwater, 2011; Le Cornu, 2010; Ten Dam & Blom, 2006). This shared negotiation of meaning ensures that time and resources are directed toward a common goal for all.

Another form of negotiation of meaning that was most important to the preservice

teachers in the current research is that which was done with their supervising teachers and other school staff. Without an understanding of what they are meant to be doing in the school the preservice teachers are in danger of becoming confused and frustrated. This scenario was the case in the study by Iyer and Reese (2013) where preservice teachers felt isolated and disengaged because they felt that they could not talk to their supervising teachers. Harlow and Cobb (2014), on the other hand found that when preservice teachers are able to hold professional conversations with their peers and supervising teachers they gained in confidence and understanding of teaching and what it means to be a teacher.

Carter (2012) suggested that induction into teaching needs to begin at the initial stages of teacher education to allow preservice teachers multiple opportunities to learn how to negotiate what it means to be a teacher as perceived by multiple stakeholders in a variety of social and professional settings. The preservice teachers in Carter's study revealed that they preferred more formal than casual approaches of induction into the school community as it allowed them to feel more professional and accepted as a member of the school community. The preferred induction processes included a formal welcome to the school, an official tour of the campus, and the provision of both oral and written information about the school. These induction processes were seen as a positive way to begin their placements and were perceived by these preservice teachers as a way to accelerate their participation in the school community.

Fourth-year preservice teachers, like those in the current research, are starting their transition phase from being a student to graduate teacher. In a CoP their level of their peripheral participation becomes more fluid as they negotiate their way through different levels of engagement. These negotiations are enhanced when there is an alignment between community spaces (teacher education institutions and schools). As Wenger et al. (2002) described it, 'the key to designing community spaces is to orchestrate activities in both public and private spaces that use the strength of individual relationships to enrich events and use events to strengthen individual relationships' (p. 59). It would appear that the more effort all stakeholders put into negotiating meaning of roles and responsibilities the better the process is for all, and particularly for the preservice teachers involved in the professional experience placement. Of particular importance in negotiating meaning is preservice teachers'

perceptions of the amount and level of participation they are allowed and feel able to do. The following section considers the role of participation in an immersion pathway.

3.4.2 Participation

Participation involves active engagement that combines doing, talking, thinking, feeling, and belonging in the community. Harlow and Cobb (2014) described that for preservice teachers the school community consists of many participants that include their supervising teachers, the students, senior school management, parents, and the university lecturers who help to prepare preservice teachers for practicum. Each participant has her own perspective of the role the preservice teacher should fulfill. While there are different levels of participation in a school CoP this participation can be considered to be on the periphery as preservice teachers are not part of the core community of the school staff. Lave and Wenger (1991) suggested that participation in most communities is voluntary (as was the case with participants in the immersion pathway of the current research) and the value that comes from these communities is often derived from informal, day-to-day interactions. While there is a familiarity of events, such as the structure of running a classroom, the members of the community generate new ideas and activities. Anecdotally, teachers often describe that they like to have preservice teachers in their class because they bring in the latest theory and new activities to share with the class, which brings in an element of novelty and excitement (Hudson, 2013; Langdon, 2013). While there is an excitement and vibrancy to the community there is also a rhythm created by the established routines and inherent expectations of community members.

Within the community there is mutual recognition of participants but this mutuality does not automatically entail equality or respect. Rogoff and Angelillo (2002) cautioned that the culture of a school community is a multifaceted concept, not a 'fixed box' of categorical properties attributed to one culture but more fluidly integrated constellations of community practices. The tools and practices of teachers need to be understood in relation to how they may affect the professional teacher identity development of preservice teachers while engaged in a school community. Pellegrino's (2010) findings indicated the mismatch of expected participation in a community when preservice teachers perceive a disconnection between

what they are learning in their coursework and what they were expected to understand and do in the classroom. Having an extended time in the immersion pathway it was proposed in the current research that the participants would be able to make stronger connections between their learning at university and applied learning in schools, particularly with their supervising teachers and the students at the school.

Participation as a member of a school community can be found in the shared use of cultural tools (for example, school policies) and practices of schooling (for example, a school behaviour management policy, the practice of wearing the school's name badge, and the strategies used to teach a lesson). These tools and practices are significant in the shaping of a preservice teacher's emerging identity and the sense of who she is and how she is understood in a school community. Wenger (1998) described these cultural tools as a *reification* of practice; the notion of reification is described below.

3.4.3 Reification

If we accept that preservice teachers must understand the roles and practices of teaching, including appropriate usage of the tools of teaching and learning in order to identify themselves as teachers, then we must also explore where the ideas, practices, and tools for teaching originate. We can do this by exploring the construct of *reification*. Wenger (1998, 2000) described reification as a process of projecting meanings into the world where these meanings are then perceived as existing and having a reality of their own. Examples of this might be writing an education policy (such as the *Melbourne Declaration on Education Goals for Young Australians* - Ministerial Council on Education, Employment, Training, and Youth Affairs, MCEETYA, 2008) or creating a procedure (such as a handbook outlining preferred activities for preservice teachers while on their professional experience placements). These policies begin as ideas which are ultimately produced and used as a tool (written rules or criteria) that provides 'form' for a certain shared understanding. Thus, reification involves the sense that abstract ideas are made into objects that can be understood as substantially existing, or being concrete, and so can be used by members of a particular community with a shared understanding.

A cultural tool in the current research would be the criteria laid out for what is expected of preservice teachers engaged in the immersion pathway. The concrete actions would be the agreed upon activities by the school and university supervisors that indicate that the preservice teacher has met the criteria and so has successfully completed the program. Completing the criteria successfully contributes to her gaining in developing a positive professional teacher identity. Enacting the written criteria for the immersion pathway is a form of reification.

Banner, Donnelly, and Ryder (2012) described the process of reification in relation to how a particular education policy, *How Science Works* (HSW), was understood and used at various levels in the education network. In the process of reification, the HSW policy began at the Education Departmental level as an ideal to encourage more students to engage in learning science subjects at school. At this level there was limited pressure exerted for standardisation of what the policy really meant or how to enact it in schools, but there was also an expectation by the department for school authorities to take this fairly abstract idea into teaching practice. The HSW policy at the next level of the network was embedded into an overarching syllabus as a form of standardisation of the policy which identified the operational accounts of desired teaching and learning activities to be employed in schools. However, at this level the policy was still broad enough to allow it to be localised. At the school level the HSW policy was developed into school syllabus with more detailed description of specific teaching and learning activities teachers were expected to use to encourage more students to study science. It is the process of making an abstract idea into a tool that can be enacted that is the heart of reification.

According to Wenger's (1998, 2000) notion of reification, tools such as the HSW policy need to pass through a *negotiation of meaning* in some form or other at the different levels of the network. While reification shapes the individual's experience and having a tool to perform an activity can change the nature of that activity and one's identity within the activity, it is rare that classroom teachers have opportunities to negotiate meanings of policy with members of Education Departments. Not having a direct line of communication with departments, teachers take into account their own personal histories, knowledge, and experiences of objects similar to a new policy

to help them make sense of that policy. Therefore, participation and reification cannot be considered as separate entities. Without having teachers interpret and use the policy, it will not be used as intended. A reified tool then can be a vehicle to open engagement (Wenger, 2000) on an issue of common ground across the network where the various levels of negotiation of meaning of the object enable it to be translated in a way that allows for it to be implemented as a concrete activity.

Bobbitt Nolan, Horn, Ward, and Childers (2011) considered reification in relation to how novice teachers understood the negotiation process around assessment. Assessment directives from the National and State level were written to capture the meaning and values at that level of the network. The focus at this level was to address the perceived need for testing to achieve desired student outcomes (for example, passing the tests). As with the HSW policy in a study by Banner et al. (2012), the assessment policy in a study by Bobbitt Nolan et al. (2011) passed through the various levels of the education network, being changed and revised for each level. With these changes were also implied changes in power as each level put down their interpretation of the policy. Power relationships existed then at all levels of the network with each level protecting their understanding of policy while also shifting or sharing the negotiation of the meaning of them with other members of the community network so the tool could in the end be enacted. Bobbitt Nolan et al. (2011) described how this shift in power also occurred in the change of status from preservice teacher to novice teacher in how each understood the policy from their unique perspectives. Preservice teachers were largely protected from high stakes negotiation of meaning of assessment in a school; however, as a novice teacher there were real expectations and accountability for them to enact professional behaviour as an understanding of policy. The individual as a classroom teacher must take on the responsibility of embedding the policy into her assessment practices whereas the preservice teacher had the support and guidance of her supervising teacher in learning how to embed assessment in her practice teaching lessons. In summary, the power of the negotiation of meaning for teachers became relative to their position with others in the teaching community and within the network.

This perception of power affects how the reified object (for example, the assessment tool or the HSW policy) is understood and used by a teacher. Kostogriz and Doecke

(2011) described that through the process of reification teachers can feel a sense of loss of control over the process of teaching and learning, such as with national testing. When this happens, teachers may feel a sense of detachment from imposed testing regimes. However, while they may feel a distance from policy makers, they also exhibit compliance in order to provide a quality education for their students so that the students can actually pass the test. If a whole class does poorly on the test the teacher must shoulder the responsibility of accountability for why this occurred. Therefore, it sometimes happens that teachers may feel pulled in both directions at the same time (trying to fulfil expectations of department directives and providing the best quality education for students, which may conflict with perceptions of the policy). Thommen and Wettstein (2010) described that a social system, can only sustain its unity and survival by reproducing stable patterns of processes and procedures. For the education system, this involves all members in the network having some level of mutual expectations of what education is and should do. Along the network, reified ideas are interpreted and reinterpreted through participation in a community. Community members help each other to make sense of expected and desired outcomes in what the community as a whole hopes and expects to achieve.

Preservice teachers in the current research negotiated an understanding of several different policies and standards of teaching from national standards through to local school management policy and through connecting their university coursework. In negotiated meaning between the shared communities of schools and the university they gained in understanding their role as a preservice teacher within the immersion pathway experience. In this situation the preservice teachers participated in a shared enterprise of providing a quality education for the students, using a shared repertoire of teaching practice under the protection and guidance of their school supervising teachers and in negotiation with their university lecturers. This shared enterprise was embedded in established guidelines that were enacted through participation in the immersion pathway.

There are different policy guidelines (tools) that support preservice teachers' school engagement. For example, there are university guidelines that describe desired behaviours and activities for preservice teachers when they are in schools for completing the immersion pathway and other practicums. These guidelines must

be interpreted by school personnel (supervising teachers, school site coordinators of professional experience) and the preservice teachers in a way that misunderstandings do not occur so that the preservice teachers gain the maximum benefit of being in the school. The stakeholders in this situation need to have a shared repertoire of meaning to successfully enact the immersion pathway. Therefore, it was important in the current research to understand how preservice teachers understood the meaning conveyed by these tools in order for them to negotiate a shared meaning with their host school of what they would do in the school over the course of their year-long immersion at the school. Within a CoP, *artefacts* also play a significant role in developing one's identity. The following section describes the possible artefacts that contribute to developing a professional teacher identity.

3.4.4 Artefacts

Professional teacher identity can be considered through objects described as artefacts. In the current research an artefact referred to an object that has been transformed for special purposes within a particular community or culture. Researchers (Siegel & Callanan, 2007; Vygotsky, 1978; Wenger, 1998) have described people as cultural beings who create and use artefacts to mediate their relations with their environmental surroundings. Lave and Wenger (1991), for example, described artefacts as the 'technology of practice' that makes access and participation in a community transparent to its members. Every community has a range of activities specific to it; in the case of teaching, these activities include knowing what and how to teach and being recognised as possessing such knowledge and skills. It is the how of teaching that utilises everyday technologies (artefacts), such as a white board, computers, pencils, pens, and paper that are needed to ensure that the activities can be completed. These activities are the cultural practices of the classroom and cannot be done effectively without using the cultural artefacts of teaching. Understanding the use and value of the artefact connects one to the history of the practice and, thus, on how to connect more directly with the cultural life of the practice. Artefacts relevant to being recognised as a teacher and, thus, contributing to preservice teachers' developing professional identity may include: an identification badge that provides recognition as membership of the school and therefore of the community of teaching, a portfolio of teaching episodes, collected photographs, or

other forms of memory collections.

Siegel and Callanan (2007) explored the mediation of artefacts as teaching aids. In their study, participants were presented with four stories about four novel objects with invented names: a tog (used for trapping insects), a zig (used for squashing flowers), a dax (used for collecting flowers), and a wug (used for floating on water). Pictures of each object were shown along with eight picture cues to the four objects' various functions. Participants were asked to judge each picture and then if they would judge any, some, or all of the four artefacts differently if told that many people were using the artefacts in a different way than the creator intended, as opposed to just one person using it in a different way to its originally intended purpose. The study found that the participants were less likely to think of the artefact purely in terms of the inventor's function upon learning of the many alternate functions. Siegel and Callanan's findings demonstrated that individuals can interpret the purpose(s) of artefacts in different ways and that artefacts indeed must have a context for interpretation.

Spencer Armour (2011) described the use of 'manga' as authentic material to teach Japanese. Manga can be expository text for language learning, often found as computer software which has an appeal for young learners as students can move along at an individual pace and level of learning. Spencer Armour found that students learned conversational Japanese much quicker when they used manga as an artefact for learning. Being able to manipulate the artefact was central to capturing students' attention and allowing for greater learning to occur. In contrast, Yao, Aldrick, Foster, and Pecina (2009) explored the use of a more traditional pen and paper artefact of notebook entries to guide science teaching to understand teachers' perceptions of their identity as science teachers. The study found that the quality of notebook entries differed depending on the teacher's interpretations of the curriculum and their instructional practices. They found that not all teachers utilised the artefact in the same way. For example, one teacher was very conscientious in using the notebook which greatly enhanced her understanding of herself as a science teacher; another teacher who did not initially identify herself as a science teacher did not use the notebook and continued not to identify herself as a science teacher by the end of the project.

Teaching portfolios are commonly used artefacts by preservice teachers in relation to school-based experiences (Dinan-Thompson, Lasen, & Hickey, 2010; Lin, 2008). In a qualitative US-based study, Wray (2007) found that portfolios afforded preservice teachers opportunities to articulate their personal stories about teaching and learning. As part of their university coursework, these preservice teachers were required to construct teaching portfolios and present them orally to their university supervisors, peers, and cooperating teachers. Artefacts from coursework and practicum assignments were used in the construction of the portfolios. The study found that these preservice teachers perceived their portfolios as being reflective pieces which would be of benefit to their futures as beginning teachers. The preservice teachers cited the value of the portfolios in their use for articulating connections between theory and practice and better understanding the scope of their learning through consideration of their personal educational philosophies.

More recently electronic portfolios (e-portfolios) have been used by preservice teachers (Dinan-Thompson et al., 2010; Lin, 2008; Yao et al., 2009). Preservice teacher participants in these studies viewed e-portfolio artefacts as a physical demonstration of their transformation to professional practice. The e-portfolios contained documented evidence of their professional knowledge and experiences and so played a significant part in their professional teacher identity development. Interestingly, Yao et al. (2009) found that the preservice teachers described that the artefacts of their teaching more so than their reflections showed how competent they were as preservice teachers during their school placements. Some preservice teachers in their study raised the possibility that the documenting of teaching competencies shows the knowledge base that someone has, but it does not necessarily demonstrate how one would apply that knowledge in the classroom. In other words, it is possible to fake evidence about one's teaching skills through a reflection but more difficult to do so with the concrete evidence of teaching. Overall though, preservice teachers viewed teacher e-portfolios as being representative artefacts of how competent they were as developing professional teachers.

To date no research was located that reports on the types of artefacts that may be significant for preservice teacher identity development as it evolves in a year-long

immersion pathway experience. It was proposed in the current research that a preservice teacher's use of a particular artefact plays a role in the development of her teacher identity and sense of belonging during immersion in a school. In its simplest form, an example of an artefact could be a school whistle. In a practical example of the use of such an artefact, a preservice teacher is handed a sports whistle from a mentor teacher before lunch yard supervision. The preservice teacher performs her lunch time supervisory duties and blows the whistle on several occasions to alert students that they are not to run in 'walking only' areas, not to play in or access out-of-bounds areas, and ensure that students return to class promptly at the end of a lunch period. The preservice teacher's use of the whistle during lunch duty could produce various meanings, such as the preservice teacher is a member of the teaching community, or is a lunch time yard duty supervisor. It is the use of a tool that can result in a meaning being produced by the preservice teacher and by those who view her actions. In contrast, if the sports whistle sits on the preservice teacher's desk in a classroom it does not produce a clear meaning of function or connection of use by the preservice teacher. Yet, when that preservice teacher places the whistle around her neck, walks around the school yard on lunch time supervisory duty, and blows the whistle to alert students of unsafe behaviour then the function of the whistle becomes concrete. That is to say, it is a tool that is used by the teacher for work. It can be understood that the whistle, when it is used by the preservice teacher on lunch duty, exists with a clear function and it gives identity and belonging to the preservice teacher in her school community. In this example, the artefact takes on multiple meanings that are both overt and tacit to teaching. The current research explored the kinds of artefacts that were significant for preservice teachers engaged in the immersion pathway.

3.5 CONCLUSION

This chapter has examined Lave and Wenger's (1991) and Wenger's (1998, 2000) theoretical notion of teacher identity development in a CoP through the lens of situated learning. The literature suggests that for a community to work successfully, participants need to perceive a sense of belonging at whatever level they are engaged in the community. For preservice teachers the level of belonging may be peripheral to a school community or preservice teachers may feel a great attachment and sense of belonging.

The chapter has described the role of negotiation of meaning, participation, reification, and artefacts as probable means of teacher identity development in a year-long immersion pathway. The following chapter outlines the methodology for the research.

Chapter 4: RESEARCH METHOD

INTRODUCTION

Utilising sociocultural theory, this qualitative case study explored the development of teacher identity through fourth-year preservice teachers' extended immersion in school-based professional experience. There is a dearth of research that specifically explores preservice teachers' teacher identity development in an extended immersion pathway.

The overarching research question was:

What experiences do preservice teachers perceive as providing insights into the profession and in developing an identity of belonging in the profession?

From the overarching research questions two sub-questions emerged to explore preservice teachers' identity development:

- 1. How do preservice teachers develop an identity as a teacher through their immersion in a professional community?*
- 2. How do preservice teachers develop professional practice through their immersion in a professional community?*

This methods chapter describes the utilisation of a case study design through an interpretivist epistemology (section 4.1). The chapter includes a description of the case study approach (section 4.2) with specific reference to an interpretivist case study design (section 4.2.1) that has incorporated a qualitative longitudinal research approach (section 4.2.2). Section 4.3 describes the participating preservice teachers in the research and how they were recruited. Section 4.4 describes the specific data collection methods used in the research, including sections: interviews (section 4.4.1); moderated online discussion board (section 4.4.2); and artefacts and tools (section 4.4.3). Section 4.5 provides an overview of data analyses, including: thematic analysis (section 4.5.1), and coding of themes (section 4.5.2). Ethical considerations for conducting the research are then stated (section 4.6) before a conclusion to the chapter (4.7) is given.

4.1 INTERPRETIVIST EPISTEMOLOGY

The qualitative approach used in this research is described as interpretive research which is a common epistemological stance for case study research where preservice teachers' lived experiences result from social interactions in which they interpret and make meaning of their own and others' actions through jointly constructed understandings (Merriam, 1998). The utilisation of an interpretivist epistemology in this research was aimed at understanding preservice teachers' identity and professional development through participation in a year-long immersion pathway. Goffman (1956) suggested that the individual's construction of her social world is formed differently by each person in each situation she faces. The process considers the way an individual knows and understands something exists or occurs through either a written or verbal account, although often the meanings of such accounts need to be negotiated between the speaker and the listener or the writer and the reader. Interpretivism as the overarching epistemological position is used to understand knowledge as it is perceived by individuals (Scotland, 2012) and was deemed the best fit for the current research.

O'Donoghue (2007) defined interpretivism as an approach to studying human actions with the understanding that all human actions are meaningful and are to be interpreted in a social context, that is, things that occur have meaning for people in their everyday interactions. Wray (2007) viewed the approach to include not only the understanding of meanings from human actions but also the consideration of experiences and histories that people have had and how these are understood in the context of these interactions. For example, preservice teachers bring past life experiences as members of previous school communities: as school students, as preservice teachers on prior professional experience placements, or through previous employment experiences to their current situation. By including an understanding of the past histories and experiences of preservice teachers, a richer analysis of the development of preservice teacher identity evolves than might be afforded only by viewing preservice teachers through their immediate day-to-day experiences.

The ontological position of interpretivism in the current research was relativism. Guba and Lincoln (1994) defined relativism as the view that reality is subjective and

differs from individual to individual. For example, reality is individually constructed and emerges when the individual engages with an object and develops a conscious awareness of the meaning of that object as it is used and interpreted in a particular situation (Crotty, 1998). Reality can be formed through language, which actively shapes and moulds reality (Frowe, 2001), and through the interaction between language used by the individual and aspects of an independent world, noting that this world does not exist independently of the individual's knowledge of it (Grix, 2004). Accordingly, interpretive researchers assume that access to reality occurs through social constructions such as language, consciousness, shared meanings, and objects (Myers, 2009). As argued by Heron and Reason (1997), the individual's experience of a world occurs via her participation in it. Therefore, the social world can only be understood from the viewpoint of the individuals who are participating in it (Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2007).

As an example, a preservice teacher in the current research was provided with a school prospectus that consisted of curriculum developments and directions at her immersion pathway school. She referred to this school document as a 'bible of sorts' when giving her account to the researcher in order to describe its significance to her and her developing teacher identity. In this example, the individual interpreted the meaning of a teaching tool, constructed through the interaction between her current and historical understanding of teaching and her current engagement in the immersion pathway at the school.

A potential shortcoming of an interpretive paradigm is that it is sensitive to individual meanings that can become lost within broader generalisations (Samdahl, 1999). Scotland (2012) warned that knowledge produced by an interpretive paradigm can be of limited transferability for three reasons: it is usually fragmented and not unified into a coherent body, such research usually produces highly contextualised qualitative data, and interpretations of participating preservice teachers' data involve subjective individual constructions. These concerns are common for case study research but as argued below (see section 4.2) Simons (2013) suggested the obligation with case study is not necessarily to generalise results but to demonstrate how and in what ways findings may be transferable or used by others.

As argued by Thomas (2014), interpretative inquiry and case study research marry well. The interpretative case study demands a deep understanding of the multifaceted nature of social situations, and describes that the social world is indivisible and should be studied in its completeness with the researcher making interpretations about what is happening along the way. In the current research, for example, the journey of the preservice teachers involved many and complex interactions with various people in a diverse range of social situations in their school communities; these data needed to be recorded and analysed as an ongoing process rather than at a single cumulative point. This process, while acting as a form of triangulation in that it provides an archive of perspectives from different vantage points in time, also provides a rich base for understanding preservice teachers' changes over time (McLeod, 2003). Therefore, an understanding of preservice teachers' immersion in this pathway needed to include entry points gained through the different kinds of data collected at three different times throughout the year-long immersion as described in the methodology section below.

4.2 CASE STUDY APPROACH

Case study was used in the current research as this approach is described as especially good for getting a rich picture of a particular sociocultural situation. This picture allows for analytical insights of a research issue both in its completeness and by looking at it from many angles (Stake, 2005; Thomas, 2014). Case study design is flexible (Miles & Huberman, 1994; Robson, 1993) and the researcher can select a topic and determine the boundaries of the issue or problem to be researched. Creswell (2012) described that a case study is a *bounded* system meaning that the case is separated out in terms of time, place, or some physical boundaries. Stake (2000) suggested that case study research seeks out what is common and also what is particular about a case or cases, but the end product of the research regularly draws out the uncommon (Stouffer, 1941; Thomas, 2014). Nunan (1992) defined a *case* as a single instance of a class of objects or entities and also defined a *case study* as the investigation of that single instance in the context in which it occurs. In another definition, Robson (1993) described case study as a strategy for doing research that involves an empirical investigation of a particular contemporary phenomenon within its real life context employing multiple sources of evidence. In the current research case study was conducted as a bounded system where

the case was a single unit: preservice teacher identity development through engagement in a year-long immersion in a school-based CoP, with each preservice teacher written up as a case.

It is important to consider potential factors for utilising case study research such as the type of case to conduct and the location of the research that will yield the best results. In the current research the case study was conducted as qualitative and longitudinal research as it was important to understand what contributed to professional teacher identity development over the course of a year. This approach lent an air of ‘authenticity’ (Guba & Lincoln, 1989) to the data. Authenticity includes the concepts of fairness, respecting participants’ perspectives, and empowering them to act. Authenticity lends weight to the concept of *trustworthiness*. Guba and Lincoln (1989) identified four criteria to ensure trustworthiness in qualitative research which include: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. These criteria are described below.

Credibility assures that the research measures what is actually intended and this involves choosing the correct procedures (for example, data gathering and analysis of the data) to fit the research purpose. The researcher should have a familiarity with the culture of the participating organisation or environment before data collection begins and a consideration of triangulation, which involves the use of different data collection and analysis methods, such as interviews, an online discussion board, and the collection of artefacts, which were used in the current research. It should be noted that the current researcher has been a qualified primary school teacher for eight years and so is familiar with the context and activities that generally involve preservice teachers in school settings. Supporting documents, such as the immersion pathway outline and the Field Experience handbook were used to provide a background to understand the expected and revealed attitudes and behaviours of preservice teachers and to verify particular details that preservice teachers have supplied. Credibility can also be enhanced with the inclusion of the researcher’s *reflective understanding of the interpretations of the participants* as the project develops to inform the emerging patterns and themes. In the current research the researcher maintained a process of reflection on the interpretations of the shared accounts provided by preservice teachers and constantly reconsidered his understanding of their interpretations in order to better represent their accuracy of meaning during data collection and analysis throughout the year.

Transferability is the extent to which the findings of one study can be applied to other situations (Merriam, 2002). However, paradoxically because case studies are specific to small populations it is impossible to demonstrate that the findings are applicable to other situations and populations. Nevertheless, other researchers could find that if their situations are similar to the research under question they may be able to relate the findings to their own positions. To support transferability, researchers need to ensure that there is sufficient, or thick, description of the phenomenon under investigation to allow readers to gain a proper understanding of it, enabling them to compare the phenomenon described to their own situation. Guba and Lincoln (1989) suggested that *thick description of the phenomenon under scrutiny* promotes credibility as it conveys the actual situations and context that have been explored. Having multiple means of data collection over time in the current research addressed the notion of thick description.

Dependability occurs when the researcher reports the processes of the research in detail, thereby enabling a future researcher to repeat the work. This kind of in-depth report allows the reader to gain a thorough knowledge of the effectiveness of the methods used and of the findings described.

Confirmability ensures, as far as possible, the findings are the result of the experiences and ideas of the participants rather than the characteristics and preferences of the researcher. These criteria were key indicators that guided the current research.

4.2.1 Interpretative Case Study

While there are various kinds of case studies used by different researchers for different purposes, it was the employment of an interpretative case study (Merriam, 2002) that held significance for the current research. Merriam suggested that case study research should draw upon multiple sources of information related to a bounded system (Creswell, 2012). In a bounded system there is a finite amount of data collected, that is, when the system is suspended there is no further data to collect. In the current research the bounded system was the year-long immersion pathway in which the preservice teachers were engaged. Stake (2005) asserted that collective cases, or multiple cases, in

a research design should be used to accommodate the research of a common group of participants.

A criticism of case study is that it is too subjective (Denzin, 1989; Guba & Lincoln, 1989). However, Simons (2013) would argue that by their nature case studies are suitable for gaining insight into and understanding of a particular phenomenon within a real-life context and they have the potential to involve participants in the research process. The case study researcher attempts to document and analyse naturally occurring phenomena within a specific context. Therefore, a certain subjectivity is justified and, indeed, not possible to eliminate as this kind of research is based on the researcher's judgments and analytical views. Another criticism of case study is the perceived lack of *generalisability* of the findings. Simons (2013) suggested that the intent of this kind of research has a built-in obligation to demonstrate how findings from one case study can be transferable or used by others and that this transferability may be interpreted as a form of generalisability, but that the intent of qualitative research is not to fit within quantitative paradigms. Instead, case study research provides a general understanding of a situation that has been studied in-depth.

An interpretivist case study design was used in the current research to explore multiple cases of professional teacher identity development in order to provide multiple measures of the same construct (Gray, 2009). Data collection in the current research used the methods of semi-structured interviews, an online discussion board, the collection of professional artefacts, and document analysis from six preservice teachers viewed as separate cases within the overarching case of preservice teachers. By accommodating the in-depth study of multiple cases, an exploration of each individual preservice teacher's experiences was compared within the structure of a collective case.

4.2.2 Qualitative Longitudinal Research

A key feature of the current research was its tracking of preservice teachers' professional teacher identity development over the course of a year-long immersion in schools. Qualitative longitudinal research generally embodies a range of mainly in-depth interview studies where the researcher returns to the interviewees to measure and explore changes over time (Creswell, 2012; Neal & Flowerdew, 2003). In the current

research the researcher sought to engage the preservice teachers and elicit their lived accounts in a reflexive manner by collecting multiple forms of data progressively over a one-year period, through semi-structured interviews, the collection of professional artefacts, online discussion board postings, and by encouraging preservice teachers to continually question what they knew, how they perceived they knew it, and their relationships with that knowledge.

A main drawback to this kind of research approach is the time commitment and the amount of data that such a commitment generates (Creswell, 2012). It is therefore important that the researcher keep a constant process of data collection and analysis throughout the project to identify recurring and new themes. This process indicates a strength of the design as real change needs to be observed over time.

In the current research follow-ups in data collection were conducted to gather richer data which helped to gauge a sense of preservice teachers' feelings about change which, in turn, provided depth to understanding their interpretations of their teacher identity development. The researcher regularly monitored participant involvement in the online discussion board and showed the preservice teachers their interview transcripts after each round of interviews to achieve accuracy in meaning as a form of member checking. A constant comparative analysis was used to achieve as high a level of trustworthiness as possible.

4.3 PARTICIPANTS

In qualitative research, sampling is not usually random and the number of the sample in case study research can be very small (Hakuta, 1976). Although the method of sampling and the sample size is commonly small, qualitative case study research investigates the particularity of an individual or a group in-depth so the particularity of each participant needs to be identified by the researcher in order to form a case (Hsieh, 2004). Hsieh recommended that the researcher consider and evaluate the representativeness of the participants and portray the multiple aspects of the participants in detail using data collection techniques which are applied in natural settings. Such an approach strengthens the trustworthiness of the data.

Participants in the current research were six fourth-year preservice teachers in their final year of a BEd degree (Primary Education) at an Australian university. The preservice teachers had all volunteered to participate in an immersion pathway in a school community for one year. Therefore, a purposive sampling technique (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Neuman, 2003) was utilised. In this kind of recruitment strategy the researcher intentionally (or purposely) selects individuals to understand a central phenomenon. The selected individuals in the research formed a homogeneous sampling group in that they were all fourth-year preservice teachers engaged in the same immersion pathway as part of their university coursework, but located at different school sites.

The individuals were all females and varied in ages from 21 to 45 (see Table 4.1). Although the preservice teachers were in different school settings many of the activities undertaken while at these schools were similar. For example, each of the preservice teachers participated in ‘student free’ day team building and professional development sessions, curriculum planning sessions, staff meetings, yard duty supervision, and assisted with teaching in their classes. Individual activities included, but were not limited to, organising school dance nights, athletics carnivals, group song and dance competitions, IT class sessions, working in a kitchen-garden community, and helping with a robotics workshop. Characteristics of the participating preservice teachers are provided in Table 4.1. Pseudonyms are used to identify the preservice teachers while protecting their identity in the research.

Table 4.1
Information of Participants

Participant	School	Year level(s)	Age	Number of children	Age of children
Emma	A	4, 5, 6	21	0	N/A
Jennifer	B	5, 6	21	0	N/A
Sabrina	C	4	23	0	N/A
Katherine	D	3, 4	45	2	10 & 6
Renae	E	1, 3	40	2	14 & 2
Roberta	E & C	1, 3/4	41	2	14 & 11

It should be noted that three of the preservice teachers were in their early twenties, with no children, while three were in their forties, with children. The researcher did not initially take this information into consideration because it was rarely commented upon

by the preservice teachers. However, after further exploring the data collected the researcher considered it to be possible that these backgrounds contributed to shaping their developing teacher identity. The researcher took the stance of allowing the preservice teachers to tell of their experiences in the way they wanted to do. What the participants conveyed was not necessarily related to their age or their parental status but to their common position of being preservice teachers. However, there were a few instances where this personal information was mentioned and so it needed to be recorded for analysis.

The researcher approached prospective participants with an email invitation through the unit coordinator of the immersion pathway in early February 2015. Participation in the study was voluntary. However, by the end of February, no participants had responded to the invitation to join the research. Consequently, the researcher organised to speak with prospective participants by visiting them in their university classes. As a result of this recruitment process, six preservice teachers signed consent forms to participate in the research. While the researcher had initially anticipated a larger sample size, in reality this relatively small sample size allowed the researcher to focus on each individual's personal experiences as continuous; and in much more depth than would have been possible with a larger group of participants (Clandinin & Connelly, 2000).

As suggested by Simons (2009), the researcher's role must also be considered in case study research because the researcher is the main 'instrument' of data gathering through observations, interviews, and continuous interactions with participants over the course of the research. Merriam (2009) identified four possible roles the researcher may enact in case study research. These include being: 1) a complete participant, where the researcher is a member of the group and conceals his role as a researcher, 2) a participant as observer, where the researcher's observations activities are known to the group but are subordinate to the researcher's role as a participant in the group, 3) an observer as participant, where the researcher's observation activities are known to the group but participation is secondary to the role of information gathering, and 4) a complete observer, where the researcher is completely hidden from the group.

In the current study the researcher adopted the fourth role of complete observer as the most suitable role because he was not located in the same city in which the preservice

teachers' schools were located. The researcher was not present in the schools or classrooms where engagement in the immersion pathway occurred for any of the preservice teachers. Therefore, the researcher was very conscious of his role in managing the data collection, and recognising the inherent difficulties of neutrality and bias, while taking on as neutral a role in the research as possible.

4.4 DATA COLLECTION METHODS

The following section describes the data collection methods used in the current research. Data were collected at several data collection points from the beginning, mid-point and end point of the preservice teachers' immersion pathway experience as described below in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2

Schedule for Participants in Online Discussion Board & Interviews

Type of participation & number of participants	Total number of participants	Time
Interview (1 st round: early in the year) <i>2 individual & 1 unplanned group of 4</i>	6	4 th week of March & 1 st week of April
Interview (2 nd round: mid-year) <i>4 individual & 1 unplanned group of 2</i>	6	1 st week of July
Interview (3 rd round: end of the year) <i>3 individual & 1 unplanned group of 3</i>	6	1 st & 2 nd week of November
Online discussion board (<i>5 out of 6</i>)	5	From 1 st week of March to 4 th week of October

The online discussion board was an initial meeting space for the preservice teachers and the researcher to meet. However, due to personal commitments such as university coursework, school duties in the immersion pathway, part-time employment and, for some, parenthood, participation in the online discussion board was infrequent. Indeed, as the year progressed, contributions to this space were largely discontinued by the preservice teachers.

Infrequent participant involvement in the online discussion board led the researcher to refocus his attention on the interviews. The first round of interviews was originally planned as one-on-one semi-structured interviews. However, due to the various constraints facing the preservice teachers at the time, as described above, four of the preservice teachers requested an initial group interview be conducted rather than

individual interviews, and this was done. The original plan, prior to the commencement of data collection, was to hold a focus group for the third round interview and include all six preservice teachers. Upon reflection after the first round of interviews, the researcher offered the preservice teachers the choice of one-on-one interviews or group interviews for the second round of interviews at times that suited each preservice teacher. Subsequently, two preservice teachers opted for a group interview and the other four preservice teachers were interviewed individually. The third round of interviews consisted of one focus group interview with three preservice teachers and individual interviews for the three other preservice teachers. Great care was given by the researcher to the preservice teachers to flexibly cater to their interview availability throughout the research. A description of each of the data collection methods beginning with an explanation of the interview protocol follows.

4.4.1 Interviews

Two kinds of semi-structured interviews were conducted in the research: individual interviews, and focus group interviews. Patton (1990) suggested that there are four main purposes for individual in-depth interviews. One is to document the interviewee's perspectives on the topic. The second is the active engagement and learning for both interviewee and interviewer in identifying and analysing issues. A third purpose is in the flexibility of this kind of interviewing which allows for a topic to be probed further and for a change in direction to pursue emerging issues. The fourth purpose is the potential to uncover feelings and events that cannot be observed. Semi-structured interviews encourage openness between interviewee and interviewer that can lead to unexpected disclosure of issues and information not generally gleaned with fully structured interviews.

As described above, some of the preservice teachers requested group interviews. Focus group interviews are moderator-led, usually consist of six to ten participants, and use a nondirective style of interviewing where the main concern is for the moderator to encourage a variety of viewpoints on the topics in focus for the group (Chrzanowska, 2002; Seal, Bogart, & Ehrhardt, 1998). Brinkmann and Kvale (2015) described that the aim of the focus group is not to reach consensus about, or solutions to, the issues discussed, but to bring forth different viewpoints on the topics at hand. An important

feature of focus groups is that they can achieve a cascade effect where listening to other people's memories and experiences stimulates ideas in other participants (Lindlof & Taylor, 2002). This was particularly the case in the current research because the preservice teachers realised that they shared common experiences and felt that their views were validated and supported by others. This effect was also present in the earlier group interviews of the research. Fern (2001) warned against issues involved with group cohesion and group composition that might occur with focus group interviews. For example, there can be dissent within the group which could compromise data collection. These concerns did not apply to the preservice teachers in the current research possibly because they had studied together for three years prior to participating in this research. An advantage of group interviews is that they are less threatening for participants in that they eliminate the possibility of individual disclosures but open up a sense of group agreement on issues as they provide a cross-check within the group on the consistency of perspectives and statements of certain individuals (Simons, 2013). In this way, group interviews facilitate a social construction of meaning where shared frames of reference are likely to be revealed through the social interactions of group discussions.

The questions that were asked of the preservice teachers over the course of the year allowed the researcher to compare responses for professional teacher identity development over time. Analysis of the data after each interview set informed the development of the questions for the next set of interviews. While a set of questions was established prior to each of the interview sessions, flexibility existed in these semi-structured interviews for new questions and probes to responses to be introduced during the interviews in response to participant comments (Lindlof & Taylor, 2002). Open-ended questions were an important part of the interviews utilised to allow the preservice teachers to use their own words (Yin, 2010). It should also be noted that the interviews, both individual and group, were not face-to-face, but online. The researcher and participants lived in different cities (during data collection and analysis) so it was both cost and time effective to conduct interviews in this manner. The online interviews were conducted via the My Immersion Pathway (MIP) Google+ (n.d.) community (see Appendix D for a screen-shot of the MIP site), a closed website constructed specifically for this research, as well as through Google Hangouts (n.d.) and Skype (n.d.). The interviews were audio-taped for the purpose of providing an accurate record of the

conversations for transcription. All interviews ran for a period of approximately from forty-five minutes to one hour.

In the first round, two individual interviews and one focus group interview of four participants were conducted. The purpose of the first round of interviews was to gain some insight into preservice teachers' aspirations in regard to participating in the immersion pathway around the beginning of their engagement in the schools in the fourth week of March 2015 and the first week of April 2015. A sample interview question was: *Please, share a story of your engagement so far at your school community (e.g., what surprised you, shocked you, made you think about or question something in particular)*. This question illustrates the researcher's intention to stimulate the preservice teachers' reflectivity and facilitate their capacity to describe events at the beginning phase of their school-based experiences.

The second round of interviews was conducted in the first week of July 2015 at the end of the university semester once preservice teachers had completed a four-week practicum block in schools. Two preservice teachers were interviewed in a group and four preservice teachers were interviewed individually. These interviews were done around the mid-point of the preservice teachers' engagement in the research. One aim of this set of interviews was to learn how the preservice teachers' professional identities were developing in relation to how they were managing the workload of being in school and completing their university studies. An interview question was: *In relation to your sense of professional identity, describe why you feel you are at this stage currently (e.g., was there a particular incident/activity/meeting that occurred that you felt either enhanced or hindered your sense of professional identity in the classroom/in the school community)*. The researcher commenced the interviews by reiterating the aims of the research, issues of confidentiality, and how the interview data were going to be used and stored.

The final interviews were conducted as one focus group interview with three preservice teachers and individual interviews for the other three preservice teachers. There is no consensus on how many participants should comprise each focus group. Numbers range from six to twelve participants and as few as three (Morgan, 1988). In the current research there was a natural constraint in participant numbers for the whole

project; however, there was still a sufficient number to continue with this technique for the final interviews and it was the preferred methods for the preservice teachers. Krueger and Casey (2009) suggested that through focus group interviews participants have the opportunity to compare and contrast elements of the discussion put forward by other group members as a way to develop a deeper understanding for themselves and so further the discussion. At the commencement of the proceedings the interviewer reiterated the aims of the research, issues of confidentiality, and how the interview data were going to be used and stored. The same procedure was followed for the final one-on-one interviews. The interviews were conducted in the first week and second week of November 2015 after the preservice teacher preservice teachers' final four-week practicum and their four-week internship to gain insight into the impact of the immersion pathway. A sample interview question was: *Describe your current philosophy of teaching and what has helped to shape your philosophy of teaching.* This question was used to explore if preservice teachers' evolving teaching philosophy contributed in shaping their teacher identity and teaching practices.

Because it was important to include contextual aspects of participants' voices it was decided that semi-structured interviews would provide preservice teachers with the best way to present their views. In contrast, closed questions are similar to what preservice teachers would find on a questionnaire in quantitative research and so deemed not suitable for the current research. The researcher prepared an interview guide as recommended by Patton (2002) but was prepared to allow participants to lead the interview conversation to some extent cognisant of the fact that each participant had a unique story to share. However, having a structure for the interviews ensured that data were compatible for use in a constant comparative approach to data analysis. The interview questions were in large part developed from the literature reviewed for the current research. A copy of the interview protocol for the first and second rounds of interviews and the interview protocol for the third round of interviews, respectively are included in Appendix B and Appendix C.

4.4.2 Moderated Online Discussion Board

A conversational group-oriented online discussion board on Google+ (n.d.) was set up for group participation. This site, available only to the research participants and the

researcher, was intended to provide a channel of communication for personal journal writing and sharing of information among fellow preservice teacher participants in the immersion pathway and the researcher throughout the year. Online discussion boards can be used as collaborative communication tools and showcases for participants to display information in the forms of written material, videos, photos, or podcasts for educational purposes (Wang, 2008). The preservice teachers were invited to post their thoughts, experiences, and images pertaining to their school-based professional experience throughout the duration of the research from the first week of March 2015 until the fourth week of October 2015.

A code of conduct was established prior to the preservice teachers using the online discussion board and its users were expected to abide by this code in terms of providing a proactive and safe social forum of input. Items for the code of conduct included: non-disclosure of private information, such as names, images of people, etc.; constructive but not critical feedback or replies for other preservice teachers' postings; use of appropriate language; building upon other preservice teachers' responses to create threads; and the use of prior experience and knowledge when posting on the board. The moderated online discussion board code of conduct is provided in Appendix E.

For the entirety of their year-long professional experience in the immersion pathway, the online discussion board was available for all preservice teachers to use. Participants were able to select whether comments they made were private or public. Also, they were able to upload images that related to their school-based experiences and any artefacts that they associated with their development of professional identity. The role of the researcher was to ask the preservice teachers to interpret how those artefacts contributed to the development of their professional identity. Entry postings were presented in a reverse chronological order where the last shared item of information held itself to be the most up-to-date and relevant (Stephenson, 2001) for the dual purposes of mirroring authentic communication and accommodating reference points of communication for further reflection among the preservice teachers.

The preservice teachers were asked to upload postings fortnightly and the length of these postings was at the discretion of the preservice teachers. The researcher, in the role of moderator, provided a series of stimulus questions to prompt discourse among

preservice teachers about their school-based professional experience. An example of a stimulus question prepared by the moderator for the first online chat and blog session was: *Have you learned any particular teaching and learning strategies in the classroom over the past two weeks?* The researcher monitored the online site on a fortnightly basis to ensure that preservice teachers were not encountering any technical difficulties accessing the board and to respond to participants' postings. When a preservice teacher became infrequent in their online communications, the researcher corresponded with that individual to enquire about her circumstances and whether continued participation or termination from the current research was sought. Data from the online discussion board were collected throughout the duration of the research. However, as stated earlier contributions to the online discussion board were infrequent.

4.4.3 Artefacts and Tools

Examples of artefacts that were collected include: samples of professional work, anecdotal online discussion board posts, and photographs of teacher identification (for example, a teacher's name tag at the preservice teacher's immersion school). As the online discussion board was open to all participants, preservice teachers were cautioned not to include any images of students or any identifiers of their school for ethical reasons. For example, if a preservice teacher posted her name tag, she would have to cover over the name of the school. The collection of school-based artefacts was used to provide tangible evidence of the development of preservice teacher professional identity and inclusion within school-based CoPs. The artefacts were analysed and interpreted through the meanings that they had to the preservice teachers which were communicated during interviews and online discussions. Artefacts were collected by the preservice teachers throughout the course of the immersion pathway experience which commenced in January 2015, with the commencement of student-free days, and finished in October 2015. Additionally, the researcher collected evidence of the preservice teachers' professional artefacts during data collection from the first week of March 2015 until the second week of November 2015.

There are several documents (Tools) that the preservice teachers used in connection with their engagement in the immersion pathway and their university course units relating to field experience and internships. These included the immersion pathway

outline which guided the preservice teachers in their school-based practice activities but not classroom teaching. The activities suggested include: working with small groups and individuals, and assisting in other areas of the school so that preservice teachers could gain an understanding of the school culture and infrastructure. According to the immersion guidelines these out-of-class activities may include: organising sporting events or other school events, such as carnivals or dances, working in the library, or helping with tuck shop (school canteen) duties. The voluntary immersion pathway is school-based and starts with student-free days and continues throughout both semesters of the school year with school visits, one day per week. Other documents discussed by the preservice teachers were school behaviour plans or curriculum planning documents made available to them during their time at their immersion pathway schools.

Another group of documents was the Field Experience handbooks. Field experience is a compulsory placement for all fourth-year preservice teachers, but is not connected to the immersion pathway placement. Preservice teachers completed two 20-day Field Experience placements and one 20-day internship at the same school as their immersion pathway placement. These documents were analysed in relation to references made to them by the preservice teachers during data collection. Other documents that the preservice teachers referred to include: the school behaviour management policies, and the school hand-book provided to teachers each year to guide their teaching.

4.5 OVERVIEW OF DATA ANALYSES

In qualitative case studies, data collection and analysis is a simultaneous activity and the research stages of data collection, analysis, and reporting are interactive and iterative (Creswell, 2005; Merriam, 2009). As the end product of a case study is a rich, thick, descriptive account, the prime purpose of the analysis is to reach across the multiple data sources and to condense them (Miles & Huberman, 1994). Transcript-based analysis is reported to be the most rigorous and time-intensive mode of analysing data (Onwuegbuzie, Dickinson, Leech, & Zoran, 2009). The researcher transcribed each individual and focus group interview himself. This ensured that he was fully immersed in the data and allowed him 'to get inside it'. It is argued by some researchers (Patton, 2002; Richards & Morse, 2007) that this allows for more emergent insights.

4.5.1 Thematic Analysis

Thematic analysis was used to identify meaningful themes throughout data collection over the year-long research (Fulcher, 2010). Thematic analysis as defined by Braun and Clarke (2006) is a method for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns of themes within data. Daly, Kellehear, & Gliksman (1997) suggested that thematic analysis is a search for themes important to the phenomenon being researched which in the current research was the development of preservice teacher professional identity and practice. The identification of themes resulted from the careful reading and re-reading of data (Rice & Ezzy, 1999). Mogashoa (2014) described that thematic analysis involves themes which are clusters of linked categories conveying similar meanings and usually emerge through the inductive analytic process.

The identification of themes describes the complexity of a story, adding depth to the understanding of individual experiences. Coding can begin with analysing one interview transcript to identify categories. The identified categories can then be confirmed or disconfirmed in subsequent interview transcripts. It is highly unlikely that the full story can be revealed in one interview; therefore, it is necessary to analyse several interview transcripts to search for significant and meaningful themes in the data (Fulcher, 2010).

The researcher followed Simons's (2013) process of coding as a three-stage process. In the first stage, categories were identified and confirmed. The transcribed interviews were margin-coded to begin the process of identifying themes, issues, and topics (Bertrand, Brown, & Ward, 1992). These data were then sorted into categories through a 'scissor and sort' technique (Morgan, 1988) to initially identify categories that would lead into themes. In the second stage, relationships and connections between the categories were examined in a similar fashion to that for stage one but with more depth in identifying relationships between categories. In the third stage, the generation of overarching themes that serve to indicate the whole picture, or part of the picture, of the case were identified. It should be noted that an initial deductive approach was used for the current research as there was a foreseeable possibility for significant categories to be identified before analysis began, such as identity and/or situated learning (Lave & Wenger, 2000). In light of the possibility of bias these codes were not used per se, rather

the data were read with an intuitive eye, looking for the experiences the participants' chose to communicate to the researcher.

This quasi-constant comparative method of analysis (Glaser & Strauss, 1967) is a qualitative research approach that seeks to understand the whole phenomenon being described rather than a word-by-word analysis. In a constant comparative procedure raw data are formed into indicators or small segments of information from different people over different times. These indicators are then grouped into several codes which then form categories. The researcher must constantly compare indicators to indicators, codes to codes, and categories to categories in order to eliminate redundancy in the data (Creswell, 2005). It uses a systematic and rigorous approach to inductive analysis of discourse (written or verbal). The researcher described this as a quasi-constant comparative method as the literature on CoPs has set identifiers as to what constitutes a community, such as identity and practice (Lave & Wenger, 2000).

4.5.2 Coding of Themes

The coding process began with open coding (also known as preliminary coding or provisional coding) which consisted of sorting units of meaning (words, phrases, or sentences that indicated in some way the subjects' way of thinking and/or behaviour patterns) (Charmaz, 2001; Glaser, 1978; Glaser & Strauss, 1967). The researcher had predetermined themes of identity and practice before analysing the data in more depth. At the same time as the initial analysis was done, the researcher explored 'the general sense of the data' (Creswell, 2012, p. 243). During this stage the researcher made notes of themes not explicitly sought out in the data. In consideration of using a quasi-constant comparative method of analysis to analyse data from different people over different times (Glaser & Straus, 1967), the researcher adapted Boeije's (2002) approach to using constant comparative method analysis by implementing four stages of analysis for application in the current research:

1. Compare/contrast within an individual and group interview;
2. Compare/contrast between the three rounds of interviews;
3. Compare/contrast between online discussion board postings; and
4. Compare/contrast artefacts with interview and discussion board data.

Boeije (2002) suggested that researchers take pragmatic steps to select types of comparison that address their research issues or problems. The researcher attempted to do this by comparing and contrasting the commonalities and differences in preservice teachers' perceptions of their experiences as the data were gathered. This occurred both at the time of collection and retrospectively to compare/contrast new data with that already gathered.

Initial coding was derived from Wenger's (1998) social theory of learning components. The coding began with the overarching focus for this research which is *identity*. Further coding then revealed a major theme: 'sense of belonging' which further revealed three themes of *relationships, teaching practice, and philosophy of teaching* (see Figure 4.1 below). The theme of relationships was further divided into six subthemes that indicated relationships with: school principal and deputy-principal, supervising teachers, other school staff and members of the school community, fellow preservice teachers, students, and parents. The theme of teaching practice was divided into three subthemes: classroom management, behaviour management, and teaching duties. The theme of philosophy of teaching was divided into two subthemes: current teaching, and future teaching. The themes and subthemes identified in the current research (see Figure 4.1) provided an operational framework for the application of the theoretical foundation of this research in relation to preservice teachers' professional practice and identity. These themes and subthemes were analysed through a lens provided by sociocultural theory, CoPs, and practice as meaning in situated learning which included the four key areas of negotiation of meaning, participation, reification, and artefacts (see Chapter 3 for detail on these concepts).

Figure 4.1. Coding Data for Themes

The data were entered onto a spreadsheet with the phrases or descriptions colour-coded according to each theme. A sample of the coding is provided in Table 4.3 below. The first column of the table indicates the source of the data collected; the subsequent columns indicate the data that is representative of each of the themes according to the data source. These data were then analysed to identify whether there were any links from one theme to other themes and where interconnections were made across the data for all six participants. This mapping process provided a process of triangulation (Patton, 2002) of the various sources of data to establish rigor in the research, providing rich insights of preservice teachers' perceptions of how their engagement in the immersion pathway contributed to their developing teacher identity.

Triangulation: In case study-based research, triangulation can be used to increase confidence in the trustworthiness of a researcher's data and its interpretation. In qualitative research, the goal of achieving findings in one's study that have a strong degree of trustworthiness can be found in one's ability to establish four criteria (Guba & Lincoln, 1989): credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (see section 4.2 for detail on these criteria). Triangulation refers to the use of multiple methods or data sources in qualitative research to develop a comprehensive understanding of phenomena (Patton, 1999). Fielding and Fielding (1986) argued that it is important to select a research approach which is specifically situated to exploring the research issue(s) being investigated which can capture the essential elements of its meaning to those involved, and do so by combining methods which focus on the 'everyday' with methods that address the observable-individual. As discussed in Section

4.4 (data collection methods), two forms of interviews were implemented, that is, individual interviews and unplanned focus groups and they provided data at different levels (Flick, 2007). The challenge of qualitative data analysis is to make sense of massive amounts of data (Patton, 1990) and while a researcher may expect that triangulation will help to yield a more accurate and valid estimate of a result when each method of measurement actually converges on the same answer (Mark & Shotland, 1987), complete convergence may not always occur in qualitative data.

In the current research data source triangulation was used to collect data from different individuals to gain multiple perspectives and validation of data (Carter, Bryant-Lukosius, DiSenso, Blythe, & Neville, 2014). Fielding and Fielding (1986) maintained that qualitative researchers rarely use triangulation to achieve construct validity, which is commonly used in quantitative research, but rather use triangulation to attain ‘completeness’ in order to reveal the varied dimensions of an area of each source of data which contributes another piece to the puzzle. The use of triangulation for the purpose of completeness in the current research aimed at revealing multiple dimensions and capturing a contextual portrayal (Breitmayer, Ayres, & Knal, 1993) of the development of teacher identity and professional practice among preservice teachers through their participation in an immersion pathway. Both multiple collection methods and multiple data collection times (see Table 4.2) enhanced the process of comparing information collected to determine corroboration and implement a qualitative cross-validation (Wiersma, 2000). The use of a triangulation procedure allowed for multiple comparisons (Bateson, 1996) and by combining the information from multiple sources this procedure helped the researcher to gain a wider pattern of interpretation, which assisted in the process of confirming the ‘realness’ (Konecki, 2008) of the research issues explored (see section 1.3 for research questions).

The process of analysing data in the current research involved a ‘distillation’ of the data by the researcher through several methods illustrated in Figure 4.2. A process of coding, using Simons’s (2013) three-stage process was implemented. This process involved: identifying and confirming categories that would lead to themes, identifying relationships and connections between categories, and generating overarching themes that indicated the whole picture, or part of the picture, of the case. A quasi-constant comparative method of analysis was also used to analyse data from each of the

preservice teachers over different times (Glaser & Straus, 1967) with the researcher adopting an adapted approach (Boeije, 2002) which included four stages: comparing and contrasting within an individual and group interview, comparing and contrasting between the three rounds of interviews, comparing and contrasting between online discussion board postings, and comparing and contrasting the artefacts collected with interview and discussion board data. Triangulation of the data collected at different points in time during the year-long study helped the researcher to compare information collected to determine corroboration and implement a qualitative cross-validation (Wiersma, 2000) of the data. Examples of triangulation of data collected from several of the preservice teachers in the current study are exemplified below in Table 4.3.

Figure 4.2. Process of Distillation of Analysed Data

The table below provides sample data from the different sources over the course of the year’s data collection to provide a visual of how preservice teachers changed in some ways in their thinking and feelings and in what areas.

Table 4.3

Analysis of Coding from Data

Source	Sense of belonging	Relationships	Philosophy of teaching	Teaching practice
Initial-pathway interviews	...it's so nice to be accepted by everybody and not just my mentor teacher. So, it's been really nice and really positive (Renaë).	...my teacher now has been so inclusive and I think this is why I am so ready and confident (Sabrina).	I guess my philosophy now is still very, very much student focused with the focus that every child can learn and it's up to us to find a way to help them learn (Katherine).	...I was able to meet the parents...and just have normal conversations with the parents...I was just another person in the classroom who was significant enough to be there along with the teacher (Emma).
Final interviews	...so definitely being in the pathway and being surrounded by professionals and participating in conversations, meetings, stuff like that, all to do with things constantly in school. That's been the single biggest development in my teacher identity (Renaë).	I can call my Principal now and...quite regularly volunteer at my school...this is so out of my comfort zone for me. I like to be quiet...but I know that to be successful and to learn as much as I can that I need to do that. I think that this year I've changed so much in that kind of way (Sabrina).	I think because I have been through this pathway and I've understood and seen how all the support staff work I've been able to draw on their strengths and [have] been able to add that into my own teaching (Katherine).	The pathway was probably the best school experience in my course because it gave me so many opportunities to learn from so many people...to be able to put into practice the theory of what I am learning at uni, to be able to actually test it out and reflect on that and not feel like I'm confined to a four week prac (Emma).

The above data indicates the growth of participants in the current study in different dimensions as they continued their placements in the immersion pathway. The sample from Renaë indicates a tentative perception of being accepted at the beginning of her engagement in the immersion pathway to her change in perception from participating in professional conversations and other school activities more as a colleague than a preservice teacher on the periphery.

4.6 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

As with all research the current study followed rigorous procedures to ensure that the research was ethically sound. For example, the level of risk involved with this study

was assessed by the host University's Faculty of Education ethics committee in accordance with the requirements of the *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research* (Australian Government, National Health and Research Council, 2012). It was proposed that this research was of a 'low-risk' status. Several control measures were implemented in order to reduce risks. The researcher was not involved with teaching the prospective participants prior to the commencement of this study and did not have any influence over their academic progress or academic assessment. All participating preservice teachers were volunteers in this research. The online discussion board was a closed online site available only through an invitation issued by the researcher. Data collected, while initially identifiable by student user name and student on the online discussion board site, were de-identified so that participants would only be referred to and recognised in data analysis by way of pseudonyms in order to secure confidentiality of the participants' identity and their responses. Summaries of the data collected and analysed were available for the preservice teachers to verify and comment on prior to final inclusion in the thesis in order to ensure that the preservice teachers' perceptions of the research observations were accurately represented. Furthermore, at any time during the data collection, the preservice teachers were able to use the specific key expression 'No comment' to indicate their desire to avoid answering or commenting on a question or topic if they felt any distress or discomfort as a result of any communication during their interviews. Additionally, names and identifying features of schools were omitted from the results and pseudonyms were used instead. The online discussion board was closed down upon completion of the research.

It is inevitable that a researcher's world view and values will influence the research, particularly in qualitative research. It is important that the researcher situates 'self' in case study research as the researcher is the one to collect and interpret the data and so must restrict as far as possible his own subjectivity in the research. To create checks and balances, the researcher maintained a process of reflection of the interpretation of the preservice teachers' shared accounts of their experiences throughout the year. The researcher sought clarification from the preservice teachers either during the interviews or upon reading the online discussion board postings in order to represent accuracy of meaning in what the preservice teachers' were conveying during data collection. Analytic reflection (Ezzy, 2002) was important in the current research for linking the

coding process to the research questions, monitoring how the data were being interpreted over time, and developing a broader picture of the phenomenon of preservice teacher identity development more broadly as a collective case. Constant reflection by the researcher supported the development of data analysis that reflected the iterative process of data collection and analysis over a period of time when changes in the development of preservice teacher identity, professional practices, and immersion in school-based CoPs were observed.

4.7 CONCLUSION

This chapter has outlined the methodology for the current research. An argument for using a case study design was given with specific reference to the utilisation of a longitudinal interpretivist case study approach to explore preservice teachers' teacher identity development through their engagement in a year-long immersion pathway. The data collection techniques were described as well as the data analysis methods. The following chapter describes the findings of the research as growth over time. While Chapter 6 explores the data in relation to the various dimensions of preservice teachers' situated learning through their engagement in a school community.

Chapter 5: FINDINGS - Change over time

INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents key findings from the research that explored the development of preservice teacher identity development through the context of fourth-year preservice teachers' engagement in an immersion pathway. The overarching research question was:

What experiences do preservice teachers perceive as providing insights into the profession and in developing an identity of belonging in the profession?

There were two sub-questions established to explore preservice teachers' identity development:

- 1. How do preservice teachers develop an identity as a teacher through their immersion in a professional community?*
- 2. How do preservice teachers develop professional practice through their immersion in a professional community?*

This chapter considers the data in relation to preservice teachers' identity development and sense of belonging over the year-long immersion in a school community (section 5.1). This section is divided into three parts with a focus on the progressive development of preservice teachers' professional identity and sense of belonging over time through the year-long immersion pathway: early in the year (section 5.1.1), mid-year (section 5.1.2), and end of the year (section 5.1.3). Section 5.2 provides the conclusion of the chapter.

5.1 PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY & SENSE OF BELONGING

At the beginning and mid-year points of the immersion pathway the preservice teachers were asked to identify on a continuum posted on the online discussion board (and discussed in their first and second rounds of interviews) their confidence level in relation to their sense of professional identity as a teacher (Figure 5.1) and their sense of belonging in their school community (Figure 5.2). Each of the preservice teachers

was asked by the researcher to describe and discuss their self-perceptions of changes in their sense of professional identity and sense of belonging in both the first and the second rounds of interviews (see Appendix B). Any significant changes in the preservice teachers' self-perceptions seemed to occur in the first two rounds of interviews. So, the researcher explored other aspects of the preservice teachers' development of: a sense of belonging in the teaching profession, teacher identity, and professional practice in the third round of interviews (see Appendix C). A visual representation of the preservice teachers' self-perceptions of their sense of professional identity and sense of belonging to their school community is provided below in Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.1. Continuum of Preservice teachers' Confidence in their Professional Identity

Figure 5.2. Continuum of Preservice teachers' Confidence in their Sense of Belonging

5.1a) Progress over time: Preservice teachers' development of professional identity and sense of belonging - Early in the year

In relation to confidence in their professional teacher identity, four of the preservice teachers ranked themselves as being 'confident' at what they described as the end of the scale (see Figure 5.1). Emma and Roberta indicated that they were at the 'C' end of the word 'confident' rather than the 't' end of the word. While Jennifer and Renae indicated that they were at the middle of the word 'confident':

I am towards the end of the confident section but not at the end of that section (Jennifer, Online discussion board, April, 2015).

I think we're all at that *not very confident end* [of the word, confident], but definitely up towards the end of that scale; where the 'C' starts but not at the end of where the 't' starts (Renae, Online discussion board, April, 2015).

However one preservice teacher, Sabrina, identified that she felt halfway between confident and not confident, as she described it:

I am definitely not at the point of 'confident' simply because I am the youngest there. I feel like am confident around kids and feel like I can take things on board. I can teach. It's just that I think you are always so secure when you are on prac because there is always someone there when something goes wrong...I think my confidence will be, until I can go out there and do it by myself, a bit lower (Sabrina, Online discussion board, April, 2015).

Sabrina suggested that because she was young she had not enough experience and learning to feel more confident in developing her teacher identity in spite of the fact that she believed that she was good with children and was able to teach. She perceived that until she had her own classroom she would not feel confident in her identity as a teacher. In her third interview held toward the end of the preservice teachers' placement in the immersion pathway, Sabrina revealed that she had struggled throughout the year, questioning whether teaching was the right career choice for her. She described that at one of her low points she talked to her mother who encouraged her to focus on the children rather than on any short-comings she may have been seeing in herself as a

teacher. This conversation appeared to help as Sabrina described that she *had to remove my preconceptions* about teaching (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015), which she did. This new approach helped her to feel *more relaxed as a teacher* (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015). When she was asked what surprised her most about herself through her engagement in the immersion pathway, she described:

Going through uni [university] with Roberta, Renae, and Katherine and how they're a bit older and have a lot of life experiences - they're surer of themselves than what a twenty year old is [Sabrina]. So, they were always very involved in the conversations at uni [university] and at all our lectures; they always had something to add. It can be a bit daunting to come to these ladies who seem to know exactly what they want and they have all this experience with what they're doing. I've just come from high school and I don't have anything to add to that. I cruised through high school and I didn't do anything exceptional at high school. Yet, this year I put in the same amount of effort that they did and I've come out of it with a contract [to teach] and all these professional relationships with a lot of different people that I never would have had. And those are experiences that I have had that a lot of my friends at uni [university] don't have (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Sabrina identified that she felt somewhat intimidated by the life experiences and seeming confidence of the older preservice teachers in the group and initially did not know how to overcome these feelings. She recalled that up to this point she had been 'cruising' through her teacher education course in the same manner that she had *cruised through high school* (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015), but this approach had led her to a crisis point of questioning whether she wanted to be a teacher (or not). It would appear that once she started putting in the effort into being a teacher or at least *the same amount of effort that [her peers] did* (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015) things began to turn around for her. She began to feel more like a capable teacher and, as equally important, made others feel that she presented as a capable teacher to the point where she was offered a contract to teach once she graduated from her BED degree program.

There is little research that specifically explores that point where preservice teachers stop thinking of themselves as extended high school students and begin thinking of themselves as capable teachers in training. It is not known, for example, how younger preservice teachers, like Sabrina, situate themselves as teachers alongside older and more experienced peers who they perceive to be better prepared for teaching because of their life skills. Sabrina's perception that her older peers felt confident in their roles was not entirely borne out as described below.

The preservice teachers were also asked to rank their sense of belonging on the confidence scale early on in their participation in the immersion pathway. Some of the preservice teachers, including Sabrina, Renae, Jennifer, and Emma ranked their sense of belonging at the higher end of the scale: Confident (see Figure 5.2). Sabrina attributed her sense of belonging to the relationship she had built with her supervising teacher:

I have a sense of belonging in her classroom and in the way she operates because she is so inclusive (Sabrina, Online discussion board, June, 2015).

Two of the preservice teachers: Katherine and Roberta, on the other hand did not indicate such confidence (see Figure 5.2). Roberta, for example, ranked herself at three-quarters of the way to 'confident', and Katherine ranked herself at the midway point of the scale, indicating that she felt the least sense of belonging at this stage of her engagement. Roberta's placement was different to that of the other preservice teachers in that she was placed in a classroom where there were three teachers team-teaching in a combined class of 51 students. Because there were so many teachers in the class already, Roberta felt that she was *like I'm an extra wheel that doesn't really need to be there* (Roberta, Interview 1, April, 2015). Her sense of belonging in this class was further compromised when two of the teachers began a campaign to ostracise a third member of the team who they felt was underperforming:

...they were coming up with schemes in front of me to see how they could trip her up and basically get her removed from the classroom (Roberta, Online discussion board, April, 2015).

Because this unprofessional behaviour was occurring as an ongoing issue, Roberta reported it to her university supervisor who negotiated with the school to have Roberta moved. As it happened, Roberta was moved to a different school to complete her

immersion pathway engagement. This example illustrates the role of situatedness in supporting preservice teachers' sense of belonging in a school community. Contrary to Sabrina's perception that the older preservice teachers [such as Roberta] were more confident than she felt, Roberta did not feel confident in her sense of belonging and questioned her placement. Katherine, another of the older preservice teachers, did not feel confident either in her teacher identity or in her sense of belonging at the school early on the immersion pathway. She attributed her lower confidence to being somewhat shy about opening up to other people:

I'm not very good at just putting myself out there. I like to get to know somebody quite slowly before I kind of open up a bit and expect them to open up to me about their philosophies of teaching and that sort of thing (Katherine, Interview 1, April, 2015).

From Katherine's interview it would appear that being an older preservice teacher does not necessarily mean being a more confident preservice teacher, as perceived by Sabrina.

5.1b) Progress over time: Preservice teachers' development of professional identity and sense of belonging - Mid-year

At the mid-way point of their engagement in the immersion pathway, the preservice teachers were again asked to identify where they felt their confidence levels were both in their teacher identity and in their sense of belonging at their school. Most of the comments, including Roberta, were similar to Jennifer's comments about her confidence in her professional identity (see Figure 5.1):

My confidence has definitely improved...I'm way up at the end of the confident end of the scale. I know now that I'm a good teacher (Jennifer, Online discussion board, June, 2015).

Katherine, however, perceived that she was only *three-quarters confident* (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015) in her sense of belonging in the school and her particular classroom (see Figure 5.2):

I still have a little bit of time this year left and because I've just changed classes I kind of feel that I'm not where I was like at the start of the year but

there's that unknown quantity of having to relearn new classroom procedures and routines and also get a new feel for the teacher (Katherine, Online discussion board, July, 2015).

Katherine identified a key element of possible obstruction to every preservice teacher's identity development: they are teaching in someone else's classroom so are not able to teach as they may want or know how to do. Instead, preservice teachers must conform, to a greater or lesser degree, to that of their supervising teacher which positions them as peripheral participants (Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1998) in that they are part of the community but not yet full members.

Because the contributions to the online discussion board fell off as the preservice teachers became busy with their coursework and professional experience placements the researcher asked, in a final interview, for them to describe their teacher identity at the end compared to where they perceived they were at the beginning of their engagement in the immersion pathway (see Appendix C). All of the preservice teachers agreed that their level of confidence had grown considerably since the beginning of the year and attributed this, in part, to their participation in the immersion pathway. As Roberta explained:

I think that I am probably more confident in myself, in my own ability than what I was earlier in the year, and I think it is just because of that immersion. We have been in schools in a classroom since the very first day of this school year so we have had exposure to the classroom constantly throughout the last eleven months and I think that has really helped...I feel that I can contribute to the professional conversations that I have with my year level team and also in staff meetings and in moderation. I've participated in various moderations throughout the past two months and presented my own marking and I feel very much more confident to be able to put forward why I think a student got a certain mark. And I can, not defend, but justify my marking and my grades, and I definitely would not have been able to do that at the beginning of the year (Roberta, Interview 3, November, 2015).

For Roberta this was a big step forward to where she was positioned at the beginning of the year, but her comments reflect those of the other preservice teachers. All of the

preservice teachers described that being in a school for the whole year contributed to their professional identities and sense of belonging to the teaching profession. It should be remembered that volunteering in the immersion pathway differed to engagement in mandatory professional experience. The preservice teachers felt that there was a great diversity of activities in which they were expected to engage. Katherine, for example, described the benefits of not being expected to stay in the same class over the year but to engage in a variety of teaching and learning situations as well as engage in many other ways to understand schooling and what it means to be a teacher beyond teaching lessons:

The other thing that I thought about the immersion pathway and that really helped me was being in the one school and even changing classes. You really get to understand how the school works better...so it meant that going into the last prac not only was I more confident in my abilities but also I was very comfortable in knowing the school's policies and procedures to getting things done. So, I think...that by not participating in a pathway like this you probably don't get to experience that until you are in your first year of teaching...so I think that...when I start next year I'm not starting at the same level that everyone else who has not been in the pathway will be. They've got to find their feet; they've got to work out how to become a part of the community first. Whereas, we've already had exposure to that so there will be more important things for me to be able to establish when I get my classroom (Katherine, Interview 3, November, 2015).

The other preservice teachers expressed similar feelings about having confidence as a teacher that they attributed to their engagement in the immersion pathway. Renae, for example, mentioned that being *surrounded by professionals* (Renae, Interview 3, November, 2015) all year was a confidence booster in her teacher identity development. Sabrina described she now felt *more aware that I can manage behaviour and do things by myself and that I can be successful in this career* (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015). Emma described some of the activities that went beyond working in a classroom with a supervising teacher:

I was able to be involved in extracurricular things like a school concert to raise money for the school, school dances for the kids, a school camp, going

on excursions and all these extracurricular things which I wouldn't have got the opportunity to do on a prac (Emma, Interview 3, November, 2015).

One could argue that preservice teachers are able to participate in the above activities while on prac, but few would have the same opportunities to be engaged in all these activities in a four-week prac. Being involved in so many activities also meant that the preservice teachers were able to work with a variety of staff members at the school. Many of the preservice teachers mentioned that being able to work with a variety of different staff was also beneficial to their teacher identity development and sense of belonging at the school as they were able to appreciate that there is no one-size-fits all for teaching as well as learning. These different staff perspectives and practices allowed the preservice teachers to expand their repertoire of teaching beyond a single classroom teacher's perspective and practices; something which is difficult to achieve when completing a compulsory four-week practicum.

As well as developing more relationships with staff at the schools, the preservice teachers commented on the opportunity to develop relationships with students during the immersion pathway that they could not have done if they were at the school for a shorter period of time. Emma described being surprised one day when she realised that she had made a deep connection with the students during her time at the school. She described how the students had written her (thank-you) letters and some had bought her a gift which she described as a massive deal for them as they were *from poor families* (Emma, Interview 3, November, 2015):

So, it kind of really all hit me that day that because I'd been with them for so long that I was able to better connect with them on a deeper level than if I had had an eight week prac or a four week prac in a school (Emma, Interview 3, November, 2015).

This kind of connection with the students was similarly described by all of the preservice teachers. For example, Katherine observed:

I didn't know that my class had been labelled as a 'problem' class by all of the supply teachers because they didn't misbehave for me in any way other than what they have done already for their teacher. So, I think that was a big positive for me because it made me feel like, not only did the staff and

families perceive me to be on the teaching staff, but so did the kids (Katherine, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Making that transition from being perceived as a preservice teacher to being a teacher was a great achievement for all preservice teachers. They recounted many instances, where having been in the school environment for several months, they were often mistaken as a staff member by other teachers and staff in the school, by parents, and by the students, as described in one comment by Katherine: *I can't believe that you're not already a teacher* (Katherine, Interview 3, November, 2015). Being recognised as a teacher helped the preservice teachers in the study take on that persona and internalise it to the point where they came to think of themselves as teachers.

5.1c) Progress over time: Preservice teachers' development of professional identity and sense of belonging - End of the year

In their final interview the preservice teachers were asked to sum up the value of completing their engagement in the immersion pathway (see Appendix C for the third round interview questions). None of the six described any negative aspects of being in the pathway and, indeed, were keen to describe how they had benefited from their engagement:

The opportunities that it provided in terms of professional development sessions, building relationships with the staff and the students really made the year very educational and I grew a lot as a teacher. I'm 200 times more prepared to start my classroom next year than if I hadn't done the immersion pathway (Emma, Interview 3, November, 2015).

To think that last year I wasn't ready to graduate [to]...making the transition to now, where I am totally ready to go out and be an independent teacher; the immersion pathway has heavily influenced that...it enabled me to be a better teacher. If I hadn't completed it, I would still be ready to teach now but I wouldn't have the confidence that I currently have as a teacher (Jennifer, Interview 3, November, 2015).

I can't see any disadvantages. It just helps your professional development as a teacher. It gives you insight into how a classroom is set up from Day One, which is something that as a general prac student you never get to experience...I would definitely recommend it and it's been a key part of my learning as a teacher (Roberta, Interview 3, November, 2015).

I do know that you have to kind of live through it to see the benefit that it has. The biggest thing that sold it for me was the opportunity to see a classroom set up from the beginning of the year because you're just not exposed to that at uni [university]; you don't have a prac at the start of the year and you always come into a prac when it's an established classroom (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Having the experience of seeing how a classroom is set up at the beginning of the year and having experiences beyond the usual mandatory professional experience placements were mentioned by the preservice teachers as important factors for them to engage in the immersion pathway, as Katherine shared:

I have confidence in my teaching because really for eleven months I have been teaching. it's not just the last eight weeks where I've had my last prac and internship...I was considered a teacher from the start of the year and my confidence, the way that I've handled myself has been...an invaluable experience (Katherine, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Renaë summed up the ultimate benefit of being in the immersion pathway:

I stayed with my school for the whole year and actually had my suitability interview [for teacher registration] last week and after the interview I was offered a job for next year at the same school. That's very exciting (Renaë, Interview 3, November, 2015).

All six preservice teachers in the study were offered jobs the following year and referred to the significance of their participation in their immersion pathway placements in helping them to gain employment. This was noted by the researcher in the final round of interviews conducted in this study. However, while the preservice teachers described participation as overwhelmingly positive they also mentioned that there were some

drawbacks. The biggest drawback was the time needed to commit to the placement, particularly at the beginning of the year when school begins three weeks earlier than university classes begin. Therefore, the preservice teachers had to be prepared to give up some of their holiday time to participate in the immersion pathway. During their engagement in the immersion pathway they were expected to attend school during these three weeks then reduce their time in school to one day per week:

You're there for the three days a week of your holidays...that's one of the reasons many of my friends said they didn't want to do it. It was because they didn't want to give up their last summer holidays for uni [university] (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015).

It was tough time wise trying to fit everything in but also rewarding at the same time. As long as you are organised, it's doable (Renaë, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Renaë also mentioned that preservice teachers who relied on their part-time employment to stay in university might find it hard being in the immersion pathway, but that was a decision they had to make and one which was made by Jennifer:

I decided that my career in the future was more important than my part-time work that I was employed for. I reduced my hours at my part-time job and discussed with my teacher the best way that I'd like to be able to engage in the immersion pathway and still do my part-time work commitments (Jennifer, Interview 3, November, 2015).

The above comments suggest that there are many different factors that need to be considered by all stakeholders committed to the immersion pathway. It is a different kind of engagement with schools than mandatory professional experience requiring different kinds of commitments. Mandatory professional experience, for example, is assessed where engagement in the immersion pathway was voluntary. This distinction between the two may have been a factor in overall participation. More research is needed in this area to determine if this is so. There were some indications in the current research to suggest that the preservice teachers did make a distinction between mandatory professional experience and volunteering for the immersion pathway and how each

and/or both contributed to the development of their teacher identity. The analysis of preservice teachers' perceptions is presented in the following chapter.

5.2 Conclusion

This chapter has explored how these commitments made by the preservice teachers led to real growth and change in their teacher identity development and sense of belonging to the teaching community and the particular school community of their placement. Changes over time were signposted by progress marked starting at the early, mid, and end points of the preservice teachers' engagement in the year-long, school-based, immersion pathway. The preservice teachers indicated that several important enablers supported the development of their professional identity and sense of belonging during their participation in the immersion pathway. Exposure to a school community for an extended period of time benefited them in various ways. Time spent with school community members allowed the preservice teachers to develop relationships with staff, students, and parents. Being surrounded by teaching professionals all year, engaging in professional conversations during the one year period, working with a variety of staff and seeing different perspectives and practices, as well as gaining insight into observing how a school year program is set up from the beginning of the year, that is, from before Day One of the school year, contributed to preservice teachers' growth in professional identity and sense of belonging in the schools. Learning by participation over an extended period of time in school communities provided the 'new-comer' preservice teachers with opportunities for engagement in practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991) through a participatory and proactive process resulting from discourse, collaboration, and negotiation (Bruner, 1999) which enabled them, in varying degrees, to make the culture of practice their own.

Preservice teachers also indicated that there were constraining influences that affected the development of their professional identity and sense of belonging in the immersion pathway. Being in another teacher's classroom placed the preservice teachers in the situation of having to conform, to a greater or lesser degree, to that of their supervising teacher which positioned them as peripheral participants. The imbalance of power between the preservice teacher and their supervising teacher (Hodkinson & Hodkinson, 2004) was raised by several of the preservice teachers. The life-spans of

classroom-based CoPs appeared to influence preservice teachers' learning and development (Amin & Roberts, 2006) as the change of supervising teachers around the mid-point of the year-long immersion negatively affected several of the preservice teachers. They had to relearn new procedures and routines and become familiar with their new supervising teachers. Being immersed within the classroom of a supervising teacher during the extended period of time in the immersion pathway meant for some of the preservice teachers that were always supported if something went wrong in the classroom and thus they were unable to be fully confident in their professional identity. In those cases, they perceived their participation to be on the periphery in classroom-based CoPs (Lave & Wenger, 1991) rather than considering themselves as full-fledged teachers. Nascent teacher identity formed through preconceived ideas of the preservice teachers in the immersion pathway about what teachers are and what teachers can do can be quite unrealistic (Darling-Hammond, 2006). Youth and inexperience in life particularly affected one younger preservice teacher, who very self-consciously gauged her professional identity development against her perception of the professional identity development of the three mature-aged preservice teachers in the immersion pathway. While she perceived them to have more confidence in their professional identity and sense of belonging in their school community than she did, findings presented in this chapter suggest that regardless of age or life experience, all of the preservice teachers experienced challenges in the development of both their teacher identity and their sense of belonging during immersion in school-based communities. The following chapter analyses in depth the various factors of being in a CoP through engagement in an immersion pathway.

Chapter 6: FINDINGS

INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the key findings from the research that explored the development of preservice teacher identity development through the context of fourth-year preservice teachers' engagement in an immersion pathway. The overarching research question was:

What experiences do preservice teachers perceive as providing insights into the profession and in developing an identity of belonging in the profession?

There were two sub-questions to explore preservice teachers' identity development:

- 1. How do preservice teachers develop an identity as a teacher through their immersion in a professional community?*
- 2. How do preservice teachers develop professional practice through their immersion in a professional community?*

The findings are presented under the major theme and other themes that emerged from the data in addressing each of the above three research questions. The overarching focus of this research was teacher identity development, which included: a major theme - *Sense of Belonging*; and three themes - *Relationships*, *Teaching Practice*, and *Philosophy of Teaching*. Section 6.1 presents findings in relation to the theme of sense of belonging. Findings pertaining to the theme of relationships (section 6.2) is divided into six subthemes: relationships with the school principal and deputy principal (section 6.2a), relationships with supervising teachers (section 6.2b), relationships with other school staff (section 6.2c), relationships with fellow preservice teachers in the immersion pathway (section 6.2d), relationships with students (section 6.2e), and relationships with parents (section 6.2f). Section 6.3 provides an account of findings in relation to the theme of teaching practice and is divided into three subthemes: classroom management (section 6.3a), behaviour management (section 6.3b), and teaching duties (section 6.3c). The theme of philosophy of teaching

(section 6.4) is divided into two subthemes: current teaching (section 6.4a), and future teaching (section 6.4b). Section 6.5 provides the conclusion of the chapter.

6.1 SENSE OF BELONGING

The overarching focus for this research was teacher identity development. The most significant theme was a sense of belonging. For the preservice teachers in the current research a sense of belonging included the relationships they formed and through their developing teaching practices as well as through their developing philosophy of teaching. Preservice teachers in the immersion pathway illustrated their self-perceptions of their sense of belonging (or lack thereof) in their school community in terms of their engagement, imagination, and alignment (Wenger, 1998) of practices and discourses in their school community. The data revealed that the preservice teachers' sense of belonging grew the longer they were participants in the immersion pathway. They could see, for example, how this engagement set them apart from other preservice teachers who had not participated in the immersion pathway, as described by Jennifer below:

Someone that doesn't belong in a school community isn't going to be offered to write a lunch time program. They're not going to be offered jobs, and they're not going to be accepted by the students. But I feel I am, that I'm well integrated in that community now, and that I definitely belong in that situation (Jennifer, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Jennifer identified herself as a member of the community. Being invited by members of their school community to share in cultural practices (Gutiérrez & Rogoff, 2003) signified to the preservice teachers that they belonged to the institutional social order of their school in which members functioned and cooperated with each other in the school community. Jennifer appeared to perceive herself to be a teacher, that is, a self-produced image of her new identity in connection with her school community. Being accepted by the school community was the most common theme and this was manifested in several different ways. Emma described below how being included in the school staff photographs made her feel a sense of belonging:

A particular incident that made me feel a strong sense of belonging...when another [preservice] teacher and I arrived at our school...they were taking

these staff school photos and we hadn't found out about it but once we got there the principal came over and said, 'We'd love you to be in the photos with us.' So, that obviously made us feel like we had a huge sense of belonging there. Also, all the students were there watching their teachers get their photos taken. Also, being a part of that photo showed to them that we weren't seen as anything different to the teachers there (Emma, Interview 1, April, 2015).

How a preservice teacher perceives herself as a teacher involves a process of imagination in identity formation (Flores & Day, 2006; Trent, 2011). A preservice teacher's sense of belonging through a process of imagination refers to the production of images of self and the world that transcend engagement (Wenger, 1998). The informal and spontaneous invitation from the school principal to participate in the staff photographing session represented a symbol to Emma of being accepted as a member of the school community. The photographs were hung on the school wall for all staff, students, parents, and other school community members to view on a daily basis, even when Emma was not at the school but back at university doing coursework. Emma's inclusion in the staff photograph and its placement in her school community contributed to what Day and Kington (2008) would describe as 'situation-oriented' identity and that this photograph, that is, a professional artefact (Carter, 2012), had an environmental influence on her sense of developing teacher identity. Wenger-Trayner and Wenger-Trayner (2015) would suggest that Emma's inclusion in the staff photo represented her experience in the actual practice of being included in a peripheral form of participation because she entered the school as a 'trainee' and would never fully become a regular member of staff during her training period. However, Emma perceived her participation in the staff photo as being a shared experience with members of the school community that helped to create her identity within the school community.

Classroom-based artefacts, created by the preservice teachers and located in the school environment, were physical and cultural identifiers that contributed to the preservice teachers' sense of belonging and their inclusion in CoPs. CoPs have set identifiers as to what constitutes a community, such as identity and practice (Lave & Wenger, 2000). Knowing what is needed to become a professional in a CoP involves

an understanding of what it takes to act and be recognised as a competent member of the teaching community. A manifestation of preservice teachers' beliefs that they were engaging in a 'shared' competence that distinguishes them from other people not in the teaching community at their schools was described by the preservice teachers in the immersion pathway in relation to their creation of teaching artefacts:

I have had the opportunity to put little bits of me everywhere around the room because I have been able to write things down and put them up on the wall. Like the behaviour management [protocol], the reading groups [lists] and that kind of thing is all written down by me. So, I can kind of look around and go 'Yeah, I'm kind of included around the place' which is nice to see (Sabrina, Interview 1, March, 2015).

A preservice teacher's ability to negotiate and renegotiate her identity in a school community could significantly affect her acceptance (or failure to be accepted) as a community member. Without an understanding in the classroom of one's identity, a preservice teacher may experience feeling confused and isolated and as though she cannot easily talk with her supervising teacher (Iyer & Reese, 2013). In the case that there was a lack of acknowledgement present in a classroom the preservice teachers' sense of belonging was diminished, as described by Renae:

When I was...in a Year Three and a Year Four class, the Year Three teacher introduced me as 'Ms. + (my) family name' which was fine. But the Year Four teacher introduced me as 'Mrs. + (my) given name' which I sort of thought it was a little bit strange. And I didn't really feel like I belonged in that room (Renae, Interview 1, April, 2015).

Renae described that the Year Three teacher introduced her to the students as another professional in the school, acknowledging her formally as a teacher by her surname, whereas the Year Four teacher introduced her in a more casual manner (using her first name). Being placed as a student teacher rather than as a teacher made Renae feel that she did not really belong in the class and appeared to constrain her ability to connect with members of that classroom community. Although she struggled at the beginning of her placement, over the extended period of time in the immersion pathway Renae began to feel a greater sense of belonging with the teachers at the school:

And then I went back to visit my class in the last week of term and a lot of the teachers asked how I was going and how uni [university] was and that it was nice to see me again. So it was nice and I sort of walked away feeling that yes I really belonged there and felt welcomed and not just like an intruder (Renaë, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Preservice teachers' relationships with supervising teachers are inherently power relationships which can be a vulnerable element of their school-based professional experience placements (Broadley & Ledger, 2012). For one preservice teacher and early on in her engagement in the immersion pathway the uneven power balance between she and her supervising teacher ensured that she saw herself as a peripheral member of the classroom (Hodkinson & Hodkinson, 2004) with little to contribute because she was not encouraged to participate in activities or conversations in the classroom. Roberta struggled with developing a sense of belonging in her first school placement. She was put in a class with three other teachers who were not working well together as a team. Roberta wanted to share ideas and have the supervising teacher support her but felt that staying longer in this class would achieve the opposite effect and constrain her opportunity to engage in her role as a preservice teacher in the classroom at a level at which she would be satisfied:

In the class, sometimes I feel like I'm an extra wheel that really doesn't need to be there. Just because of the sheer number of teaching staff already in the classroom. A lot of the time there's not a lot for me to do, I guess. So, then I start to think 'Should I even be in here?' because of the levels of staff already in the room (Roberta, Interview 1, April, 2015).

When the situation did not improve Roberta asked to be placed in a different school:

I felt that it would be of more benefit to me to go to a different school because the culture of the school is not a place where I would like to work. So, I don't see that there is any employment benefit for me there either. So, I think it would just wear me into the ground by the end of the year (Roberta, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Roberta's feeling of being marginalised in her capacity as a teacher in her first classroom placement was further exacerbated due to the inter-staff conflicts and the

subsequent obstructions to satisfactory engagement with her supervising teacher and the two other teachers in the classroom. Roberta perceived that the problematic classroom environment resulted in her failing to develop a sense of belonging in that class. Such barriers to shared understandings and interactions with their supervising teachers can have a negative impact on preservice teachers (Iyer & Reese, 2013).

In a school-based CoP, a preservice teacher's ability to position her actions to be sufficiently aligned with other processes so that those actions can be effective beyond her engagement may significantly influence her sense of belonging in that community. A preservice teacher's alignment through the coordination of perspectives, and actions within a CoP allows the identity of the members of that CoP (as a group) to become part of the identity of that preservice teacher (Wenger, 1998). When Roberta was placed in a new school she found that she was encouraged to participate more fully, particularly in professional conversations, and thus developed a greater sense of belonging, through her engagement and alignment, as a preservice teacher at the school:

On professional development days you do get put into, well at my school, we were put into small groups. And I was not always with my teacher, who I had only just met as well. So, everyone knew who you were. By the end of those three days I could walk through the school and everyone knew who I was and why I was there, that made me feel like I was on staff at school...[it] helped me develop who I am as a teacher as well because you have those [professional] conversations with other teachers. For example, I had a conversation with a teacher and she said, 'If you have time, pop into my classroom when you're here' (Roberta, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Being identified by both staff and students as a member of the school community was highly significant in assisting preservice teachers to develop a sense of belonging. Artefacts such as identification badges were one influential identifier in shaping preservice teachers' sense of belonging, particularly in the way that they felt other members of their school communities perceived them. As cultural beings (Wenger, 1998), several of the preservice teachers used artefacts, in the form of identification badges, to mediate their relations with their environmental surroundings; which gave

them a sense of self-recognition and perhaps a feeling of recognition from others in relation to their membership in the teaching community at their school. Roberta described that she had been at her school for two and a half months and had yet to be issued with a teacher's badge. Rather than query this with a staff member, she decided to wear her university identification badge at school so parents and staff would recognise her as a teaching member of the school:

I do not have any form of school-issued badge despite being at the school for 10 weeks. I do wear my university student badge which I guess is some way to show parents and other staff who I am (Roberta, Online discussion board, April, 2015).

Jennifer described that being in possession of an identification badge did not necessarily help her to gain a sense of belonging because the wording on the badge that she was given was particularly relevant to how she felt that other people perceived her at the school:

I felt like a *prac student* at the beginning of the year and then they labelled me with a badge saying *prac student* and I had to wear that badge this entire year. So, putting on that badge every morning I felt like, 'No, I'm not a *prac student*, I am a teacher. But everyone is going to read that and think I'm a *prac student* and label me that way.' The badge has the school logo on it and as I walked through the school it didn't say my name on it. It just said *prac student*. At the end of my year, I just wanted to hand it back and get rid of it. At other schools I have been to I've had badges that said *preservice teacher* on them and that is nicer than *prac student* because preservice teacher says you're a teacher who still needs to complete pracs Whereas, *prac student* because it has the word *student* in it, it makes you feel less experienced than you are (Jennifer, Interview 3, November, 2015).

For Jennifer, her past experiences of being referred to as a preservice teacher when she was previously issued with an identification badge made her feel that she was a teacher in some capacity whereas during the immersion pathway having the label of *prac student* on her identification badge and not having her name on the badge contributed to a degree of uncertainty about her belonging to the school

community. Additionally, the wording on the identification badge, in its function as a professional artefact that Jennifer used at her school community, indicated that an artefact can be interpreted in different ways by different people in the same community (Siegel & Callan, 2007). Jennifer did not raise her concern with any staff member at the school. Instead she kept this frustration about the generically labelled badge to herself until the end of the year when she could *hand it back and get rid of it* (Jennifer, Interview 3, November, 2015). Jennifer felt that there were contrasting images of her as a member of her school community because of her perception of how she and others interpreted her role in the school through their interpretation of the artefact that was this school badge. Perceptions provided by Jennifer about the image she constructed of herself and how she perceived other members in several school communities viewed her while either wearing (or not wearing) identification badges of various descriptions influenced her sense of self and awareness for interpreting her participation (Wenger, 1998) in those communities. These artefacts were influential in shaping the preservice teachers' sense of belonging in their school community. A stronger identifier was the relationships that the preservice teachers developed with various members of their school community. The following section explores how forming different relationships contributed to developing the preservice teachers' sense of belonging, which in turn, helped in developing their identity as a teacher.

6.2 RELATIONSHIPS

A second theme that emerged from the data was preservice teachers' perceptions about the importance of building relationships in regards to the formation of their developing teacher identity. A school community consists of many participants who may influence preservice teachers' teacher identity and practice during professional experience (Harlow & Cobb, 2014) and each of those participants, such as, supervising teachers, students, senior school management, parents, etc. has their own perspective of the role the preservice teacher should fulfill. Preservice teachers in the current study described several different types of relationships which they experienced through their engagement in the immersion pathway including: a) the school principal or deputy-principal, b) their supervising teacher, c) other school staff, d) fellow preservice teachers not in the immersion pathway, e) students, and f) parents. The following

section begins with a description of the importance to the preservice teachers of developing a good relationship with the school principal and/or the deputy-principal.

6.2a) Relationships with the School Principal, Deputy-Principal

The preservice teachers identified their ability to access relationships with senior administrative staff at their school, specifically the principal and/or deputy-principal, as important to their immersion in the school community. For preservice teachers in the immersion pathway, becoming accepted legitimate peripheral participants (Daniel et al., 2015) in school communities contributed to their ability to fully participate in the activities of the community and in the process of negotiating (and renegotiating) a meaning of what it is to be a teacher. For example, as described above, early in the school year Emma was asked by the principal to join the school staff photo being taken; she described that this invitation made her feel that she belonged to the school and was not just a visitor as the photo would eventually be sent to all staff, students and their parents. She commented that she did not think such an invitation would have been extended to her had she not been in the immersion pathway. It was due to her continual weekly presence in the school from the beginning of the school year that she was asked to be included in the photo and the fact of the photo being on display for all stakeholders to see at the school increased her visibility and membership in the school community. For Emma, the school photo situated (Burke & Stets, 2009) her in their school community and was an integral part of her developing teacher identity. Recognition from senior administrators in a big school was a significant identifier for Jennifer who expressed that having her name remembered by senior staff made her feel that she was of value to her school community:

My principal and deputy-principal, who is also our Head of Curriculum, address me by my name (Jennifer, Interview 1, April, 2015).

Being identified by name by senior staff was significant for all of the preservice teachers as it provided them with acknowledged acceptance of their place in the school, thereby increasing their sense of belonging. Katherine described an incident where her welfare was of interest to her principal when she had a confronting experience in the school yard in which she physically got between two students who were fighting:

I really felt that the principal...sought me out afterwards. She had a big, long talk with me about what I had seen...she also followed that up with making sure how I felt about the whole situation (Katherine, Interview 1, April, 2015).

Katherine's involvement in this 'critical incident' (Correa et al., 2014; Tripp, 1994, 2012) of teaching practice outside of the classroom appeared to make her realise the depth of immersion that she had engaged in at her school community. Because there was no staff member in the vicinity at the time, she took it upon herself to contain the problem appropriately and professionally until support came. Her involvement in this incident appeared to allow Katherine to negotiate her teacher identity as a trusted member of the community and to align her actions with behaviour expected of a teacher on lunch duty in the playground, that is to say, to act in the interests of students to perform a duty of care to the children under her supervision. Her behaviour was acknowledged by the principal who made a point of ensuring that Katherine's well-being was considered. Katherine felt that she was supported by a senior staff member at her school and appreciated for her actions. On the whole, having the principal of the school take an interest in them was described as a positive relationship in the school community by the preservice teachers. However, one preservice teacher, Sabrina, felt intimidated by her school principal:

I don't feel so confident with him. He's kind of a big guy so he's intimidating, as a *prac student* he's kind of intimidating in his role and I'm not really [disposed] to talking with the principal I suppose (Sabrina, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Sabrina's experience describes a potential barrier to feeling like a member of the school community. Her response is interesting because it indicates that she was not quite ready to see herself as a teacher, instead referring to herself in this situation as a *prac student* (Sabrina, Interview 2, July, 2015). Sabrina was the youngest of the six preservice teachers in the research and described a few situations where she did not feel confident perceiving herself as a teacher to the same degree as the other preservice teachers. By positioning herself as a *prac student*, and while holding onto that self-image, she appeared to feel challenged about her teacher identity. Sabrina was not quite ready to take on the responsibilities of a teacher that the other preservice teachers

described they were doing or wanted to do. However while Sabrina did not develop the same kind of friendly relationship with the principal that the other preservice teachers described, she did develop a good relationship with one of the deputy-principals at her school. She described this relationship below:

I had weekly year meetings with the deputy-principal and she knew who I was, what I had been doing, you know, comparing what we'd done in year level meetings (Sabrina, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Sabrina described that these weekly meetings included learning about curriculum planning which helped her unlock how to implement a particular teaching tool that turned out to be very beneficial to her teaching. Coffey (2010) described that a preservice teacher's engagement in weekly conversations and debriefings within the school community enhances her learning. This deputy-principal appeared to have taken Sabrina under her wing, perhaps recognising her need for more support and scaffolding in her professional development than the other preservice teachers needed. But the fragility of professional relationships, due to the sometimes transient nature of relocating staff, was demonstrated shortly thereafter when a second deputy-principal at her school replaced the first one. Sabrina had to adjust to the different approach taken by the new deputy-principal:

A new deputy came along and he didn't have those weekly meetings with me. The [previous] deputy knew who I was (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Comparing the relationships that she had with both deputies Sabrina lamented losing the working relationship with the first deputy-principal because she perceived that the new deputy did not seem to have the same interest in developing a similar kind of relationship with her. As noted by Chong et al. (2011a) when confronted with conflicting experiences, such as the one Sabrina was exposed to with her two deputy-principals, a preservice teacher's identity can be challenged. Her feeling of being cared for within the school community was shaped differently by the relationships she had with her first and second deputy-principal, although she seems to have accepted the new situation as something beyond her control and this caused Sabrina to reflect on her positioning in the school. She seems to have been waiting for senior staff to take

the initiative to include her rather than taking steps herself to become part of the school community.

While Sabrina seemed to be somewhat passive in initiating and developing relationships with the deputy-principals at her school, Roberta's example describes one way the other preservice teachers were proactive in developing a relationship with the deputy-principal. Rather than waiting for the deputy to approach her, Roberta took the initiative. She spent a lot of time immersing herself in the school community and was rewarded with recognition by her deputy-principal early on:

On the second observation day she [the supervising teacher] was sick and I didn't know and I went in anyway. I did the day and I think it was at lunch time, the deputy said to me, 'We have a Maths PD tonight. Will you be staying for that?' I said, 'Yes, I will. I know no one in the room but I will be there.' And I think that was me thinking that I have to do this and I have to show them how serious I am. After that he was my best friend, I think because he had given me no notice and I still turned up anyway. So, it turned out well and I was happy with that (Roberta, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Roberta's initiative paid off in that she felt fully accepted as a member of the teaching team *after that he was my best friend* (Roberta, Interview 3, November, 2015), indicating that the deputy-principal appreciated her effort in both attending the second observation day even though her supervising teacher was sick and in agreeing to attend the Maths PD session with little notice. Roberta's effort to align herself with the deputy principal's expectations of her as a member of the school community provided her with access to a senior level staff member and a sense of belonging with other teaching staff. The data suggested that the more effort the preservice teachers applied to becoming members of the school community, the more that effort was recognised by senior staff as a positive contribution to the school community. The two different approaches taken by Sabrina and Roberta to position themselves in their school communities had an impact on their identity development and learning. As Mutton et al. (2010) described, the depth of preservice teachers' learning from their school-based situations varies considerably in relation to the expectations of and responses to their individual experiences at their school sites. While forming

relationships with the principal and deputy-principal of their school was important for shaping the preservice teachers' sense of belonging, they spent most of their time at the school under the guidance of a particular supervising teacher. The significance of these relationships is described below.

6.2b) Relationships with Supervising Teachers

As would be expected, relationships with supervising teachers were extremely important for all six of the preservice teachers during the immersion pathway and were a daily presence and influence on the development of their teacher identity and professional practice at their school. Early in the immersion pathway the preservice teachers expressed a desire to emulate their supervising teachers in developing positive relationships with the students in their class, as Sabrina described:

I think that is the kind of relationship I want to build with my kids. So, I think having that and feeling so included with her as my mentor teacher it has really given me the kinds of things to think about for what kind of teacher I want to be (Sabrina, Interview 1, March, 2015).

In the example above the supervising teacher acted as both a mentor and model for good teaching practices. McNally et al. (1997) suggested that the initial feeling of welcome and warmth that preservice teachers are shown by their supervising teachers can result in the experience of being treated as a colleague and developing feelings as a member of a team in the classroom. It seemed that Sabrina had found in her supervising teacher, a role model and a professional member of her school community whose classroom manner with the students was something that she wanted to emulate.

In the immersion pathway each preservice teacher stayed with one supervising teacher for the first half of the year and then changed to another class and another supervising teacher for the second half of the year. Mueller and Hindin (2011) suggested that the preservice teacher/supervising teacher relationship is inherently a power relationship that has the potential to work in a mutually supportive way or provide a negative learning experience. Comparisons were inevitably made by the preservice teachers about their two supervising teachers, as described by Jennifer:

My first teacher saw me as another teacher and not as a prac student. I developed a whole heap of resources for my second teacher as well but it wasn't received as graciously or as openly as it was with the first teacher. The second teacher kind of just assumed that I could teach and that I was going to be at least just an average teacher (Jennifer, Interview 3, November, 2015).

With the first teacher, Jennifer described that her sense of self as a teacher was validated. With the second teacher, Jennifer's teacher identity was somewhat deflated. Her language here is revealing. Rather than seeing herself as a dynamic contributor to teaching, Jennifer perceived that the second teacher 'assumed' that she was 'at least' capable of being a teacher. The second teacher may well have found Jennifer capable and, therefore, not in need of a great amount of scaffolding. Jennifer's perceptions conveyed through her language may be incorrect, but these perceptions were real to her and determined her sense of belonging in the class. Forging a new relationship in a new class may have been a challenge for Jennifer. One can become comfortable with the familiar and, similar to the other preservice teachers, Jennifer had to make adjustments to work in a new class with a new supervising teacher and in essence negotiate and renegotiate the meaning of her role in the classroom and her identity as a teacher. Jennifer's experience suggests that she had formed a strong communicative relationship with her first supervising teacher but not with her second supervising teacher. With the second teacher her sense of belonging was more on the periphery of her classroom-based community. Each of the supervising teachers had the potential to support Jennifer, which they may both have believed they had done. Jennifer, however, perceived one as more supportive than the other.

Teaching generally involves developing and using a lot of tools and artefacts such as program planning, hand-outs, and worksheets. Having their supervising teachers share their professional resources had a positive effect on the preservice teachers as described by Katherine:

She was very generous in all of the things that she's made over the years, templates and things. In the last week she said, 'Don't forget to bring in your hard drive' and she basically downloaded everything that she'd got on to it (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Such unsolicited sharing created the perception in the preservice teachers' minds that they were given important 'tools of the trade' for teaching that they would not have been given if they had not developed such good relationships with their supervising teachers through their time in the immersion pathway. The access to knowledge and practices of teaching that a supervising teacher allows a preservice teacher can impact on a preservice teacher's sense of professional identity (Santoro, 1999). For the preservice teachers in the current research having their supervising teachers share their resources (knowledge and practices of teaching) positioned them favourably in the classroom and seemed to give the preservice teachers a greater sense of ownership of their teaching.

The preservice teachers in the research also described how their teacher identity was enhanced when they perceived that their supervising teacher(s) respected them enough to ask for their opinions on different aspects about teaching the class. This type of professional conversation gave Katherine, for example, confidence in her relationship with a supervising teacher and in her belief that she was accepted as a teacher in the class:

We had a group of girls we had trouble with, they were not focusing, chatting, that sort of thing. And she [supervising teacher] said to me, 'What do you think?' And I said, 'Well, at this stage we now have to move them along a bit, we have to think how we can weigh that up. Let them retain their friendships but break them up so that they're actually focusing more on their learning than their talking.' So, the fact that the teacher was asking me what I felt, what I thought, made me feel like I was being accepted as a teacher (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015).

In this example, Katherine perceived her role to be a valued teacher in the classroom whose opinion mattered and allowed her to feel accepted. However, not all of the preservice teachers in the research developed this kind of professional relationship with their supervising teacher. Roberta, for example, described how a lack of professional guidance from her supervising teacher (and fellow support teaching staff in her classroom) was quite damaging to her ability to develop a sense of professional identity in her situation:

It wasn't that they, you know, exploited me, they didn't...[but]...they were meant to be mentoring me. They were meant to be teaching me. But I was just part of the furniture (Roberta, Interview 2, July, 2015).

In this example, Roberta wanted more scaffolding (mentoring) by the expert (supervising teacher), which she felt did not happen. The generally accepted role of the supervising teacher is to provide support, explicit modeling of the job, and feedback on observations of the preservice teacher's engagement in classroom tasks (Ambrosetti & Dekkers, 2010). It was a role that Roberta's supervising teacher neglected to fulfil leaving her feeling frustrated at the lack of guidance that would help her grow as a teacher. Roberta was unable to understand what she was meant to be doing in her classroom and felt isolated and disengaged because she felt that she could not comfortably hold professional conversations with her supervising teacher.

While the other preservice teachers enjoyed positive relationships with their supervising teachers, Roberta's initial time at her school was marred by internal conflicts with the teaching staff she was set to work with which proved problematic and negatively impacted on her learning and sense of belonging as a teacher. In Roberta's case the classroom supervising teacher and fellow support teaching staff were embroiled in an internal work conflict that she felt she was being drawn into without wanting to be and it affected her role in the class:

They [supervising teacher and one support teaching staff] were coming up with schemes in front of me to see how they could trip her [other support teacher] up and basically get her removed from the classroom. So, just things like that, it was constant talking about each other and complaining about each other and not really trying to fix the problem but I would just call it in-fighting. You know one would be running off to gossip about the other and it was just not very nice (Roberta, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Being exposed to such unprofessional behaviour by teachers compromised Roberta's learning and sense of belonging in the school community. Eventually Roberta was moved from this negative environment and placed in the same school as Sabrina. Once she had the time to reflect on her situation in the first school she identified that she had been acting more professionally than the teachers in her former

class. Roberta appeared to want to move away not only from the teachers in her classroom but also the type of behaviour that she observed. This was an example of one of the preservice teachers experiencing a feeling of divergence with her supervising teacher and another colleague in that classroom, in relation to how she viewed their actions and the emerging conflict that she felt about how she saw those individuals in their role as a teacher and how she viewed herself in her role of the type of teacher that she wanted to become. These reflections helped her to see the kind of teacher that she wanted to become based upon the negative attributes that she saw some others displaying at her first school and thus, the teacher she did not want to be:

I think my professionalism has increased and my identity as a teacher has definitely been able to cement a little bit better due to the fact that I had a lot of experiences of non-professional teachers during my time [in the immersion pathway]. So, therefore, I was able to see how that impacted and was affecting the classroom plus the relationships within the school (Roberta, Interview 2, July, 2015).

The depth of learning that preservice teachers gain from their school-based experiences can vary considerably depending on the expectations of and responses to individual experiences at school sites (Mutton et al., 2010). A breakdown in communication can put a school placement in jeopardy (Graves, 2010) and this is what occurred for Roberta. When she finished her first placement at the first school and changed schools for the second half of the year she immediately felt more comfortable and confident that she would gain in learning about becoming a teacher through her participation in a more welcoming and positive school environment. Apart from their supervising teacher(s), the preservice teachers also commented on the growth of their sense of belonging through the relationships they developed with other members of the school staff, as described below.

6.2c) Relationships with other School Staff

Part of being a member of a school community included having the preservice teachers develop relationships with other members of staff besides their supervising teacher(s). Developing these relationships was a key to assisting the preservice teachers' developing sense of belonging at a school. As described above, all of the

preservice teachers had attended a three-day, student-free block prior to the commencement of classes at the beginning of the year. These three days were devoted to teachers' professional development and the setting up of their classroom. The preservice teachers were included in all of the sessions, which they described as vital for their sense of learning about the school community. Jennifer, for example, described how she gained access to many staff members during those days and was able to ask for advice about anything and everything class and non-class related:

Being involved in the student-free days at the beginning of the year is the single most significant thing because in that time and in those three days I was able to meet all of the staff, including the non-teaching staff, groundsman, and cleaners and we really had an opportunity to get to know each other. And at any point in my prac and anytime I was at that school I was able to talk to anybody and they would all know my name and they would all know who I was and where I was coming from. They could all give advice and discuss the students in the class and the different strategies that were working for them and everyone was so approachable (Jennifer, Interview 3, November, 2015).

As Harlow and Cobb (2014) found, when preservice teachers feel that they are accepted as members of their school community they express positive feelings about teaching and themselves as teachers. Being able to participate in the student-free days at the beginning of the school year provided the preservice teachers with a window into the world of teaching beyond the classroom. Experiences with various school staff afforded the preservice teachers with opportunities to interact with others to gain an understanding of the school community and provided learning situations they may not have had time for in a mandatory four-week placement. While the staff members at the schools were welcoming, the preservice teachers also had to take some initiative to include themselves in the school community. Katherine, for example, found she had to make an effort to initiate contact and build relationships with staff. However, she found that attending and being involved in school activities in the student-free days offered a gateway to make those opportunities happen:

And because I'm not very good at just opening myself up to a discussion I've found that that has been a bit hard. But luckily with those three days, I've been able to go and sit with somebody and chat while they're working

or whatever. And even some people have let me help them do things. I think, so, that's quite nice too (Katherine, Interview 1, April, 2015).

Staff rooms were also noted as spaces that provided the preservice teachers with opportunities to become immersed in their school-based communities. Emma, for example, felt at ease to talk on professional and/or social topics of conversation in her staff lunch room:

I found it very comfortable there and even just coming into the staff room at the end of lunch times, being able to sit at whatever table and feel comfortable enough to carry on that conversation with them and talk about things outside of the school setting as well. So, I think because I had been around for so long they were a lot more likely to interact with me and engage with me, and I with them as well (Emma, Interview 2, July, 2015).

The preservice teachers in this study sometimes referred to their four-week professional experience placements and how fellow preservice teachers at their school, who were not in the immersion pathway, would complain that they did not always feel included as members of the school community, particularly in the staff room. For the preservice teachers in the research, however, the staff room was a space where they developed personal connections and in Jennifer's case, below, her school staff members showed their interest in her as a person as well as in her development as a teacher at the school:

In the staff room, people would ask how it's going [to me] and we'd talk about the weekend. And there would be all sorts of questions that they probably wouldn't have asked if I was probably just a prac student. Then, when I stopped going to school to do uni [university] and I'd come back for my one day a week they'd be saying, 'We don't see you' and 'We feel like we're losing you' and 'You need to come back and be part of us again' (Jennifer, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Daniel et al. (2013) found that as accepted legitimate peripheral participants in school communities, preservice teachers are able to fully participate in the activities of the community and in the process of making meaning of what it is to be a teacher. As evidenced in the accounts given above by Katherine, Emma, and Jennifer the

preservice teachers had become active participants in the various activities of the community and, in doing so had learned to construct the language and behaviour of the community; consequently, they felt that they were recognised and accepted in the community.

The above examples illustrate the importance of being a continual presence in the school in order to be recognised as part of a school community and valued by others as someone who is wanted as a member of their school community. In shorter professional experience placements preservice teachers have described their time in schools as a ‘sharp learning curve’ where they have limited time to learn about teaching and about themselves as teachers (Walkington, 2005). In contrast, in the current research, preservice teachers’ experiences demonstrated the depth of immersion that they had been able to achieve in the school community which they felt had moderated their learning curve and their learning appeared to be deep rather than hurried and superficial.

Beyond the teaching staff and classroom environment, one preservice teacher, Sabrina, found that some of her most frequent interactions at her school were with administrative staff. When Roberta joined her school for the second half of the year, Sabrina perceived that Roberta needed to build relationships that she had already established successfully and that these relationships would assist Roberta in developing a sense of belonging in the school community and improve her image in her school community:

You need to get to know admin [administration] staff. Roberta came to my school after I had already been there for six months and it was interesting. Even signing in at the office and having conversations with the ladies at the office. They would have conversations with me and we had been doing that for six months and Roberta was like the new kid there (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Support from professional school staff other than supervising teachers was important in the formation of professional relationships for several of the preservice teachers, particularly in relation to the feedback these staff provided:

They all gave me great feedback and this really helped to boost my confidence and made me feel like a valuable member of staff. All of them commented on how settled the class was and how much I had established strong relationships with all the students (Emma, Online discussion board, June, 2015).

This type of feedback appeared to strengthen Sabrina's confidence and identity in being a teacher at her school. Being acknowledged as competent teachers by staff outside the classroom was highly significant in helping the preservice teachers to construct an image of being teaching members of a school community and is an area that has not been located (or reported on) in research found in relation to initial teacher education programs.

6.2d) Relationships with Fellow Preservice Teachers not in the Immersion Pathway

As described in Chapter 1 (section 1.1) the year-long, voluntary immersion pathway is different to the four-week mandatory professional experience block that all preservice teachers must undertake. However, it should be noted that the preservice teachers in the immersion pathway also completed their four-week professional experience at the same school. Some were joined by other preservice teachers not in the immersion pathway but who were completing their mandatory professional experience. The experiences described in this section by the preservice teachers and the relationships that they formed with fellow preservice teachers who were completing four-week mandatory professional experience blocks in their schools can be understood through the preservice teachers' developing knowledge about what is required to act and be recognised as a competent member of a school community (Wenger, 2000). Interactions with fellow preservice teachers provided preservice teachers in the immersion pathway with opportunities for reflection on their professional practice and their sense of belonging in their school. The participating preservice teachers described that they had taken on 'advisory roles' for their fellow professional experience preservice teachers on the issue of dealing with difficulties and barriers that the preservice teachers in the immersion pathway themselves either had or were facing with students in their class, as Emma described:

One was next door to me when I was in my Year 5/6 class. We would chat every now and then when we got the chance. I would say, 'How are you going?' She would say something like, 'These kids are hard to get your head around.' Or, 'This kid did this', and so on. I had to kind of encourage her and tell her that in the first few days you see it all but then you get used to it and you've just got to build up those relationships. I think she did really enjoy her prac and it was beneficial for her but she did struggle in the first few days and first few weeks to manage the behaviour (Emma, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Emma, like the other preservice teachers in the research, positioned herself as somewhat of an expert who was able to support and encourage a new preservice teacher in the school in the same way her supervising teacher would have done with her at the beginning of her time in the immersion pathway. Having been in the school for several weeks, Emma identified herself as no longer a new preservice teacher but as a teacher at the school, indicating to this new fellow preservice teacher that she had an established position there. In Emma's case, her constructed self-image in the school community based in part on her growing competence as a teacher in the classroom and the acceptance showed to her by her supervising teacher and classroom students had positioned her to move away from thinking of herself as a new-comer and to align herself in the school community as someone who has knowledge that could be shared with fellow peers in the form of professional guidance. Jennifer also established a working relationship with a four-week professional experience, fellow preservice teacher who was doing her professional experience placement in the same classroom as her. She compared their relationships with the students in the class and perceived that the students showed her more respect than they showed the fellow preservice teacher; which she described as probably due to her being involved with this group of students since the first day of the school year:

Another prac student entered the classroom and I had been there the whole time while she hadn't. When she walked into the classroom they [the students] looked at her as though she was someone else who was coming in, and that she was only going to be there temporarily. But they would come up to me and ask me questions that they would normally ask the normal classroom teacher. And they would give me the respect that they

would give the normal classroom teacher. And I guess watching how they behaved with other people showed [to me] that I had crossed a boundary, a barrier without really realising that I had crossed that barrier (Jennifer, Interview 2, July, 2015).

The barrier that Jennifer is describing is her membership into the school community. Having been at her school since the first day of school, she had become accepted as another staff member who was not likely to leave the class after four weeks. She had established herself in the class, she imagined herself as a teacher alongside her supervising teacher when she was interacting with students in the classroom and subsequently her students seemed to view her as being a teacher.

Being recognised in the school community went beyond the classroom level. Renae, for example, described how she was mentioned at a staff meeting which included all of the teachers at her school but the fellow preservice teachers on their four-week placements were not mentioned by name:

...then I waited for them to welcome the other preservice teachers and they didn't get a mention at all. So, it was kind of awkward in my position because I sort of looked over at the preservice teacher I knew and she sort of looked at me and went, 'Hmm.' Um so that was um, like that made me feel really welcomed (Renae, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Even though Renae saw that being recognised by the deputy-principal by name while the other preservice teachers were not was an awkward situation, she also expressed a feeling of pride at being recognised and welcomed at the school. Carter (2012) noted that preservice teachers perceive induction processes such as a formal welcome to their school as a positive way to begin their placement and a way to accelerate their participation in the school community. Renae had experienced her induction several months prior to this meeting as was duly acknowledged. This kind of recognition in front of peers helped to increase her sense of identity as a teacher at the school that the others did not share and provided her with an opportunity to observe the diverging path that she and a fellow preservice teacher participating in school-based professional experience had encountered at the same school. She appeared to feel that she was not a temporary visitor at her school but rather a recognised and

established presence in the school community in comparison to her fellow preservice teacher.

As well as contact with fellow preservice teachers on professional experience the preservice teachers had contact with colleagues at the university. Several of the participating preservice teachers in the immersion pathway had third-year preservice teacher peers approach them for advice about entering the immersion pathway in the final year of their BEd degree. Renae felt that she was able to act as an advisor and offered guidance about the immersion pathway:

A few of them came in [to the library when she was studying there] in a little bit of a panic saying, ‘we wanted to do the immersion pathway but we’ve been told by somebody else [another fourth-year student] that we’d be mad to do the immersion pathway.’ And we asked who that fourth-year student was and he didn’t even do the immersion pathway himself. So, we said, ‘Why are you taking his advice because he didn’t even do it? If you want to know the truth of it, come and ask us because we are all doing it.’ (Renae, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Renae’s active engagement in her school community and her evolving self-image as an experienced preservice teacher in the immersion pathway helped her to develop an awareness of the depth of her knowledge about her role in the pathway and think about how she could assist her teaching peers to better understand that school-based professional experience. She saw herself in a position of authority about the immersion pathway and was confident enough to be able to dispel gossip about what happens in the immersion pathway because she had experienced it and this gave her a certain expertise about the pathway. Each of these examples provided in this section illustrates a unique form of professional transformation about what it means to be a teacher as the preservice teachers in the immersion pathway engaged with fellow preservice teachers not in the immersion pathway as part of their everyday practice of being a teacher.

6.2e) Relationships with Students

One of the more complex and rewarding relationships the preservice teachers described were the relationships they developed with students both in their classrooms and in the broader school community. Being accepted in a teaching role at a school was a highly significant enabler for the development of preservice teachers' identity within a school community, as described by Emma and Jennifer:

At the Senior Athletics day, it felt more like I was part of the school because so many kids recognised me as well. So, kids from my previous class, as well as kids that I'd gotten to know through the inner-school sports program and other ones that were going to be in my class and siblings of other students. So, I really felt a part of the school because I was recognised by so many of the students (Emma, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Some of the students I don't even know personally will address me with my name. It goes to show that when you become part of the school community from Day One...regardless of your 'status' as a teacher...students will take an interest in you and will respond to you more positively (Jennifer, Online discussion board, May 2015).

Jennifer's commentary about the acceptance that students at her school showed toward her included a reference to the particular characteristic of the year-long immersion pathway where preservice teachers are at their school (for not only the student-free day blocks) from the commencement of the school year.

As a consequence of the acceptance shown to them by students at their schools the preservice teachers grew in confidence with their teacher identity in the sense that they were being seen as a teacher at those schools rather being seen as a student teacher, as expressed by Jennifer:

The students know that I'm a teacher. They don't know me as a practicum student (Jennifer, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Over the year-long immersion this kind of acceptance and recognition gave the preservice teachers a growing sense of confidence in seeing themselves as teachers and a sense of belonging in the school community. This aspect of preservice teachers in the current research perceiving themselves as being good teachers for their students is a finding that Hong (2010) made in relation to preservice and beginning teachers that when they demonstrate the ability to build professional relationships with students their confidence in being a professional teacher grows. Furthermore, the preservice teachers in the immersion pathway demonstrated a developing awareness of their role as a teacher as a result of their working with students (Appl & Spenciner, 2008). Therefore, in-class acceptance was highly significant. The preservice teachers described the extra time they put into their preparation and teaching and in building relationships with the students to ensure quality learning, as Sabrina and Emma described:

I kind of really, really tried to incorporate a lot of the interests in their lives in my teaching. And building those relationships as I taught and, you know, joking and those kinds of things to really build a stronger bond with them because they really appreciate those things quite a lot. So, I think it really had a lot to do with my progression of how much I taught. The more I taught, the more I felt that bond with them. And the more I put into the lessons I was teaching too. They appreciate the effort that you put into their learning, I think (Sabrina, Interview 2, July, 2015).

He [the student] came in and he'd had a disagreement with one of the boys and he started kicking the door and throwing things around. So, because I had built that relationship with him, I was able to speak to him calmly. I had enough of a relationship with him to calm him down, be able to get them [the other students in class] settled, and be able to sort things out with this other boy who's the one who only stays to about twelve o'clock. So, usually if you speak to him he automatically blows up like you're picking on him. I was able to speak very calmly and fairly to all of them [students in the class] and the situation got resolved and that was only because I had built that relationship with them and the relationship only came because of the length of time I was able to spend with them. I was impressed with the way I handled that situation. I was quite thankful for how the relationship

had changed. Especially with the boy who was kicking the door because he's one of those ones who if he doesn't want to do it then he's just going to chuck it in so he can leave. But I noticed that the longer he was with me, the more he would respond to me (Emma, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Emma described her utilisation of effective behaviour management skills that she had developed during her engagement in the classroom. She perceived that she had advanced in developing these skills only because of the length of time she had in the classroom to build a relationship with one particular child (and the class group of students) in the context of dealing with a difficult situation. Renae also described that the fact of being in the school community over an extended period of time was influential in helping her build relationships with students in the class to the point where one particularly difficult student responded very positively to her as a teacher in that class:

I have a particularly tough child in one of my classes and the time that we've spent there has let us develop that relationship. He is even asking me how my week at university was, and asking me how I went on one of my presentations because I had discussed that with him while he was having a particularly tough day...so, that constant rapport building that we can do with the students and the teachers has been more in-depth this time around (Renae, Interview 1, April, 2015).

Emma summed up on how being in the school community allowed her to build a strong relationship with students and how they related to her as a teacher with some authority:

...I think it's probably just the consistency of having you there so they realise that this person has got a bit more authority...they'll come up and talk to you more because they recognise the face, you know, I'm able to tell them that I'll be here all year so they bother to make that effort as well because they know that I'm going to be there all year (Emma, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Through their constant presence in the school community the preservice teachers were able to observe their supervising teachers' interactions with students and learn

new and successful techniques for working with students, as shared by Sabrina who described how observing her supervising teacher changed her approach to how she engaged with students in order to develop a greater sense of belonging with that class group. Sabrina initially held the perception that she needed to be very strict when working with students but from observing her second supervising teacher she realised that:

...it maybe taught me to have a little bit more fun with them, muck around with them a little bit more (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Being able to have fun and be friendly with students was a big transition in thinking about teaching for Sabrina. She began her time in this class as being: *completely shocked with how my second mentor [supervising] teacher worked* (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015). Sabrina soon warmed up to the idea that teachers can have fun with students and that these kinds of relationships: *kept them more engaged* (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015). Sabrina's experience of wanting to be perceived by her students as a kind and friendly teacher who was willing to close the emotional distance with her students (De Jong et al., 2014) was a renegotiation of her approach to relating with them. As a result, the students responded positively to her presence in the classroom.

Emma also described that after observing her teacher closely and then aligning her approach with how the classroom teacher interacted with the students allowed her to develop deeper relationships with them:

And they [students] had a particularly bad day recently where they misbehaved for that [LOTE] teacher but then once they were back in the class with us we had a group discussion and spoke to them about how that's not on. And then I had them for that lesson and they were beautiful for me and they all cooperated (Emma, Interview 1, April, 2015).

Emma had taken her cue from the classroom teacher in this episode who seemed to demonstrate firm but fair actions in response to student misbehaviour. As a result of being seen as one with her teacher, the students responded to Emma in a positive way. She followed up these observations of her relationships with the students, identifying herself as a: *stable, positive role model in their lives* (Sabrina, Interview 1, March,

2015) who had their best interests at heart. One might argue that the preservice teachers molding their teaching approach to that of their supervising teachers illustrates the power relation between the two; that the preservice teacher is restrained in developing their own style of teaching. However, a counter argument would be that for a consistency in student learning, having the stability of the same teaching approach in the class was the least disruptive one.

In the immersion pathway, preservice teachers had time to learn how to behave as teachers by observing how it is done by expert teachers (Edwards & Protheroe, 2004). Emma revealed that she followed her supervising teacher's lead in order to build stronger relationships with her students and better manage the classroom learning environment. The preservice teachers all described a period of transition in building relationships with students. Upon reflection of her time at her immersion school, Jennifer described her initial interactions with the students who rejected her straight-out before easing into the adjustment of having her in the class as one of their teachers:

They were her kids [the supervising teacher's] and they weren't my kids and they felt that too. So, when we started off they used to ask when the [supervising] teacher was coming back and say, 'We like her more than you.' And I said, 'Thanks guys, unfortunately you've got me for eight weeks so deal with it.' So it was a real adjustment period there but I managed to win them over (Jennifer, Interview 3, November, 2015).

These interactions occurred when Jennifer changed class groups at the halfway point of the immersion pathway and even though she was still placed in the same school community for the second half of her year-long immersion pathway experience she had to learn how to gain the respect of these new students in a new classroom-based CoP.

Jennifer's example describes the transition from peripheral to nearly complete participation in the classroom as a teaching professional. All of the preservice teachers described that they were able to develop relationships with students at a depth not possible in a four-week professional experience block and felt rewarded by this opportunity. The students and teachers, in their respective classrooms, acknowledged the relationships that the preservice teachers had built by showing their appreciation

in the farewell parties that their class groups held for the preservice teachers at the end of a term or at end of the year. These celebrations sometimes surprised the preservice teachers as it was not until then that they were able to see how strong a bond they had forged with a class group:

I didn't realise how strong a connection I would have with those students. And that wasn't really until it was my last day on Monday of last week and I realised how they were reacting and how upset some of them were. I had had letters with students writing, 'Thank you for teaching us' and 'We'll miss you.' But some of the content of the things these kids were writing, it hit me that day how well I connected with them (Emma, Interview 3, November, 2015).

I was almost in tears. It made me feel like I had made a big difference to their year. They had accepted me as a teacher and as somebody that they could respect and were happy to learn from. So it was a big moment I think for me (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015).

These findings concur with those of Appl and Spenciner (2008) who found that preservice teachers gained in teacher identity through building healthy relationships with students. Through establishing such relationships the preservice teachers developed a greater insight in what it means to be a teacher. As well as the relationships they made with students the preservice teachers in the current research also referred to relationships they made with parents as described below.

6.2f) Relationships with Parents

Establishing relationships with parents was described by the preservice teachers as being valuable but these relationships were not always easy to establish particularly when parents were not often visiting the schools or classrooms. Emma recalled her experience:

I haven't got to do as much with parents as I probably would have hoped. But I think a lot of that had to do with the particular level that I had. Very few of the older students' parents come in to see you. There really was

only one who came in consistently. I look forward to hopefully getting to communicate with the parents a lot more (Emma, Interview 2, July, 2015).

The infrequency of her interactions with parents affected Sabrina's confidence in relating to the parents of students from her class:

There are not a lot of one-on-one conversations with parents that I really see [with the supervising classroom teacher]. So, with parents I don't have that much confidence (Sabrina, Interview 1, March, 2015).

Sabrina's teacher contacted the parents through emails, which limited Sabrina's chances of personally interacting with them at the classroom level. However, she seemed to resolve this issue for herself through her involvement in extracurricular activities at her school:

With the support of parents and the community, there is this program called 'Kitchen-Garden' and for one term they run five weeks in the kitchen for one-lesson-a-week and five weeks in the garden at the school. In those lessons we had quite a lot of parent helpers and especially in the Cooking classes, the kids went out to eat and the adults stayed and they cleaned up. I was really able to talk with quite a few of the parents in that respect. And it was nice, kind of, they were very friendly and like, 'Oh, how much longer have you got to go?' and 'From my son [or my daughter] I've heard lots about you' and 'How much longer is your prac?' (Sabrina, Interview 2, July, 2015).

The access to parents that Sabrina's participation in volunteer activities provided matches the finding in a study by Coffey (2010) informing that during a graduate school teaching program preservice teachers had opportunities to engage in conversations with parents and volunteers within a school community which provided further enhancement to their learning and their professional identity.

Through her school-based experiences Jennifer described that the parents of some of her students at disadvantaged schools acted with what she initially perceived as neglect of their child's welfare. Yet, nearing the end of her year-long immersion at her school she reconsidered her opinion about the actions of some of the parents:

I was thinking, well, some parents try the best that they can but due to unforeseen circumstances and personal opinions and different parenting skills, it just doesn't happen [what she perceived as good parenting]. And a particular part that I think is really important might not be important to them. I was able to come to terms with that fact and find some level of comfort in the fact that I had some understanding about it (Jennifer, Interview 3, November, 2015).

In the immersion pathway, the images and beliefs preservice teachers brought into their school communities, at times, appeared to act as filters for new learning (Mewborn & Tyminsky, 2006) and preservice teachers' participation in school-based CoPs gave them opportunities to analyse their beliefs so that these beliefs could be developed and amended. Jennifer's reflections on parent-child interactions were influenced by the length of time at her school where she moved away from her earlier idealised image of parental care for children toward a more realistic outlook of her role as a teacher in relation to parents' behavior regarding the well-being of their children. In the three accounts recorded above, Emma, Sabrina, and Jennifer were the younger, single preservice teachers who did not have children of their own. Not only were their interactions with parents somewhat limited during their participation in the immersion pathway but it seems to be that they lacked the life experiences that three mature-aged mothers who were also preservice teachers in the pathway exhibited.

One of the preservice teachers, Sabrina, shared an account of the influence that one of her own parents had upon her teacher identity development. Sabrina, in a moment of personal conflict about whether teaching was the right career choice for her, recounted that her mother's support and advice helped her to form a stronger teacher identity and a greater sense of belonging in the profession:

I had a conversation with my mum about how I was having an awful time and I said, 'What am I doing? I thought I was doing well. And I can't even handle one week in this classroom and I'm supposed to be able to be there for eight weeks.' And my mum said, 'It's not about what you want as a teacher or how you imagined it to be. You need to think about these kids and how you're going to teach them.' That conversation with my mum was important and I was just in tears because I had no idea what I was doing.

But by the end of it I had one of the best times (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015).

It can be argued that identities are constructed in the various domains of everyday life (Holland & Lachicotte, 2007). Some studies on teacher education strongly suggest that preservice teachers need to consider the child in a holistic way, working to address their social and emotional well-being as well as their academic growth (Forlin & Chambers, 2011; Taylor & Ringlaben, 2012). However, until very recently (Day & Kington, 2008; Hong, 2010) less attention has been given to the emotional welfare of the preservice teacher as they undergo an enormous transition from being a student to being a teacher. Without the kind of support Sabrina is describing attrition rates of early career teachers in Australia (Buchanan et al., 2013) may continue to remain high. Sabrina's remarks indicate that teaching goes beyond the school yard. Personal relationships outside the immediate school also contribute to shaping teacher identity; having strong support from home, allowed Sabrina to develop a level of confidence that helped her to complete the immersion pathway experience successfully.

An unexpected consideration of the current research was that three of the six preservice teachers (Katherine, Renae, and Roberta) were parents. Although they did not often refer to being parents in relation to most of their relationships and decision-making about teaching Katherine, Renae, and Roberta indicated that the experience of being a parent helped them to engage with students and parents due to the knowledge and understanding they had of themselves as parents. The findings in the current research concur with those of Bukor (2015) who found that preservice teachers' family relationships and their life experiences of being a mother had a profound effect on shaping their teachers' identities and feelings of competence as a teacher. Several examples of how the life experiences of mothers who are preservice teachers contributed to the formation of relationships with both students and parents in school-based communities are provided below. Katherine, for example, who was in her mid-forties with two children described that being a parent helped her build relationships with her students. She described how working through concerns she had with her own children helped her work through how to help students in the class:

I definitely think I have benefited from having had children and it has helped me build relationships with my students. 'A' [her son] suffers from

anxiety and sees a psychologist who helps him with this. I have therefore been exposed to strategies to aid this. This has also helped me with the understanding of students' behaviours in some cases (Katherine, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

Katherine related her personal experiences not only to the students in the class but also to helping fellow preservice teachers:

...I recently had to deal with a girl who has learning difficulties which has in turn given her anxiety when doing assignments. I used some of the calm-down techniques I use with my son and we talked through what her problems with the assignment were and we talked through why she was feeling the way she was. If not for having similar issues with my son, I may not have been able to manage that situation before it escalated (Katherine, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

Here Katherine speaks directly about her identity as a parent in relation to developing relationships with staff, students, and fellow preservice teachers and how she has drawn on her parenting skills and experiences not only in relation to her developing teacher identity but in supporting others.

Renaë described that being a parent gave her a background understanding of and experiences about building relationships with students. She described that she drew on experiences with her own children and this allowed her to be up-to-date with what interested children which, in turn, helped her to build a bridge in establishing good relationships with the students in her class:

I think definitely having children makes relationships easier to form as you can draw on your own personal experiences. I have a few boys in my class who play footy [Rugby League] and a lot more who watch it on television. My own kids love the footy so the boys [in my class] and I have conversations about the Broncos [a local Rugby League team] and other footy players. They enjoy wrestling as well and the boys in the class were surprised that I could name a number of WWE [World Wrestling Entertainment] wrestlers!! This provided further opportunities to build these relationships. The girls and I have conversations about Taylor Swift,

One Direction, and many TV shows on the Disney channel. I am confident in talking to all of the children and feel I am up-to-date with the latest songs, television shows, sports, toys, etc. relating to their ages (Renaë, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

Like Katherine, Roberta described how her experiences as a parent helped her to identify more closely with the children in the class. Roberta was a mother with two children who brought her experiences of being a mother into the classroom to share with the children (for example, talking about current sport and entertainment of interest to the children in the class). She further described that being an older preservice teacher and a parent helped her to connect with the children:

I definitely think my age and having children has impacted on my placements. I feel because I am a parent I have been able to connect with my students on a deeper level, both emotionally and academically. I am able to use my children in stories to form connections and to emphasise a point with my classes...I think just having such an in-depth practical knowledge of how children think greatly influences the way I teach and treat each child in my class. I can 'read' them very quickly to determine the sort of day we are going to have (Roberta, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

Roberta described two specific examples of how she used her relationships with her children to encourage the students in her class:

When discussing homework expectations and how to be successful learners I use my children as an example...I say [to the students], 'when 'K' [her daughter] has homework she always sits at the kitchen table so I am near her if she needs help'. Or, 'I know doing homework is hard to fit in sometimes...we struggle at my house as well but we fit it in around our activities' (Roberta, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

And the following:

When children are not feeling great/tired/over it, I say, 'Oh, my goodness! You know 'K' [her daughter] was telling me this morning that she had a headache but as soon as she had a drink of water it felt better.' Or, 'I am

really tired too because ‘C’ [her son] is sick but I’m still working hard today, aren’t I?’ (Roberta, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

In the above examples, Roberta was bringing small samples of her personal life into the classroom that the children in the class would be comfortable identifying with. The students can relate to the struggles that Roberta’s children experience and, for Roberta, this helped to build a strong bond with the students. As well as developing relationships with the students, Roberta described how being a parent helped her in building relationships with students’ parents and how parents identified her as a ‘teacher’ rather than as a preservice teacher:

According to my teacher mentors [supervising teachers], parents are also more responsive to me and treat me more like a ‘real’ teacher due to my age. Maybe that’s because they think I am already a teacher! (Roberta, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

And in an interaction with a parent:

A parent this week asked [me] if Ms. ‘S’ [her supervising teacher] was going on leave and was I taking over? I explained that I was on placement and the parent was surprised. She said her child gave them the impression I was a teacher in the room because of all the learning they do when I teach (Roberta, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

And finally, Roberta described how staff at school referred to her identity as a parent in relation to having an understanding of how to support students in class:

A behaviour consultant at the school asked me to sit in on a Stakeholder’s meeting of one of my students. [She] explained that she normally wouldn’t ask a preservice teacher [to join the meeting] but as I had children she thought I would be able to empathise with the parent during the meeting and not make the parent feel uncomfortable. The parent agreed. She said if I was a younger preservice teacher she would have said ‘no’ as she didn’t think they could comprehend the issues a parent of a child with ASD [Autism Spectrum Disorder] faces (Roberta, Online discussion board, August, 2015).

It should be noted that these three preservice teachers talked about how their identity as a parent had an impact on their identity as a teacher through their postings on the online discussion board toward the end of the research. While the three preservice teachers did not mention their identities as parents as such in the interviews it is probable that this background story was an ongoing and contributing factor in helping them to position themselves in their school communities throughout their engagement in the immersion pathway. This is an under-researched area of teacher identity that warrants further investigation. The preservice teachers in the current research came to understand the value of developing relationships with all members of a school community. For preservice teachers in the immersion pathway the meaningfulness of being a member in a community could be found in the continual process of renewed negotiation of their interactions with others. By negotiating their identity and practice they could generate new relations with and in their social world (Wenger, 1998, 2000) at their school and gain acceptance as members of their school community. Through their relationships they were able to learn more about the workings of a school community and what it means to be a teacher. Understandably relationships with their supervising teacher(s) and students were highly significant for the preservice teachers in their identity development. Additionally, developing relationships with senior staff and parents in the school community contributed to their overall sense of belonging in their school. Another significant area that contributed to their sense of belonging was their teaching practices in the classroom and school community. This aspect of teacher identity development for the preservice teachers in the research is described below.

6.3 TEACHING PRACTICE

Although time spent in the immersion pathway was not meant to be devoted specifically to teaching, the preservice teachers in the current study did, in fact, spend time teaching. This section identifies the teaching practices undertaken by the preservice teachers; these practices are broken down into three categories: classroom management (section 6.3a), behaviour management (section 6.3b), and teaching duties (section 6.3c) both in the classroom and in the school community. The following section looks at the theme of classroom management in relation to the preservice teachers' developing teacher identity.

6.3a) Classroom Management

Classroom management refers to the preservice teacher's creation of an environment that allows for learning. Classroom management involves preservice teachers' observations in the setup and organisation of a class at the beginning of the school year, practised throughout the year. While each preservice teacher had her own perspective of the role(s) that she should fulfill in her classroom community, her participation can be considered to be on the periphery as she was not part of the core teaching staff. Each of the preservice teachers was a volunteer in her school community and aimed at gaining enough knowledge, understanding, and confidence to take on the role of teaching in her future professional career. A key element of the immersion pathway was to allow for the inclusion of preservice teachers in the setting up and organisation of a classroom in the first three student-free days of the school year to help them understand the reasoning of teachers for the formation of a classroom layout and behaviour management plan. Preservice teachers in the current research were often involved in the design and implementation of class setup and organisation with their supervising teacher(s) rather than only observing this aspect of classroom management. This access given to them by their supervising teacher(s) helped them to shift more from peripheral participation in the class and closer to full participation in the class. Jennifer, for example, described how these setup days provided her with key knowledge about how she could set up a classroom of her own in the future:

I know how to set up a classroom because I've had those experiences first-hand already and I haven't even been out in the real world with my own classroom yet. But I have seen how it can be done (Jennifer, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Renaë was also an observer not only of how to set up a classroom but of how to be flexible as a teacher to make the classroom more student-friendly and attractive as a learning environment when her supervising teacher's class was placed in a temporary classroom:

On the first student-free day we were actually moved from our classroom, kicked out because they hadn't finished the new building. So, we had to be moved from our room for another group to use the room. So, we were

put into this little, tiny, L-shaped room. We didn't have a whiteboard, we didn't have a projector, or anything like that. So, I was given some input into how to make the room attractive for kids and inviting. So, that was really good (Renaë, Interview 1, April, 2015).

Other preservice teachers in the current research were given opportunities to participate in setting up their classrooms. Emma, for example, described setting up and organising classroom activities to suit her teaching style and how the students responded positively to her as their teacher because of this:

So because I was the one who organised it I felt like the kids were a lot more responsive to me after that because they knew that it was my decision to do that. So if they had questions they would come to me rather than their normal teacher because I kind of facilitated that. So I felt that by [my supervising teacher] giving me more say and helping me to take more initiative, I was more willing to take risks because I was already familiar with the kids (Emma, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Emma described that she felt prepared to take risks because the students had become used to having her in their class. In some sense, setting up a class is in itself a risk but she felt that this was a risk worth taking because she 'knew' the students and they knew her. So, she had that insider information about what would work for them and her as their teacher. Maaranen et al. (2008) suggested that preservice teachers preferred to implement class management styles that were based on their own traditional schooling as they were seen to be familiar and more comfortable approaches rather than try to experiment with more risky approaches that they were less familiar with. Yet, Emma demonstrated that when preservice teachers have a strong sense of belonging in the classroom they may be willing to try different things beyond their comfort level. Sabrina had also been given an opportunity to be included in the setting up of a class. As her professional identity evolved Sabrina spoke with more confidence about her ability to offer her opinions about class setup and organisation and she was capable of explaining and supporting her opinions more because of her growing experience with students in her class:

I was able to give my opinions as to where kids should sit, where some kids would fit in their seating arrangements and those kinds of things with

organising the class. 'Cause I knew those kids then, when she'd [my supervising teacher] ask me, 'Oh, I'm not happy with that setting. What do you think?' I was really able to give my opinion and my understanding of what I thought would work because I knew those kids. And having that opportunity was really good, really thinking about, 'I know this kid talks a lot and this kid doesn't', and thinking about all those kinds of things like, 'This kid's rowdy and he needs to be up the front but this one's not so bad so he could sit up the back.' Those kinds of things, it was really interesting to think about those organisational ideas (Sabrina, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Like Emma, Sabrina placed a high value on knowing the students in order to get the seating arrangement right. Having been in the immersion pathway for an extended period of time by this stage she felt confident in giving her supervising teacher advice when they were working out a new seating arrangement. In addition, it must be said, the supervising teacher felt confident in asking Sabrina's opinion; it is probable that such an exchange of opinions would occur in a shorter professional experience placement. Katherine also described contributing to the setup of her class:

We moved the configurations of their desks around and then they had to do a presentation and all the desks got pushed into one long line. And I said to my teacher, 'That actually is not a bad configuration' (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015).

The preservice teachers provided logistical reasons for the classroom arrangements and identified the importance of their relationships with the students as supporting reasons for their decisions regarding setting up the classroom; indicating that because they knew the students, they knew what would work best for them in their learning. Having this hands-on experience of setting up the classroom gave these preservice teachers confidence and a sense of belonging in the class. In accord with Harlow and Cobb's study (2014) the 'hands-on' experience of preservice teachers in the current research gave them a sense of belonging as teachers in the classroom and a stronger image of self-competency in that aspect of their teaching. They seemed to view themselves as being more fully-fledged participants in the role of being a teacher, more involved, and less on the periphery for having been given access to participate in the setting up and organisation of the classroom.

As described earlier, the preservice teachers spent time in the school through engagement in the immersion pathway but also for their mandatory four-week professional experience placements. Because they had been in the school since the beginning of the year they were familiar with the class, the students, and the supervising teacher's approach to teaching. Preservice teachers' participation in classroom-based CoPs through the immersion pathway can be described as situated learning (Lave & Wenger, 1991). Learning in situ, or 'learning by doing', for these preservice teachers was characterised by their gaining mastery of knowledge and skills so that they could move away from the periphery of that practice as a new-comer and toward full participation in the sociocultural practice of the community. Emma described the freedom given to her by her supervising teacher to arrange the class layout for her professional experience placement (prac) and how this helped her to develop and explore classroom organisation to suit her teaching style:

With the setting up and the organisation of the class, I feel like I had a lot more say as a teacher when I was on my prac. I did help set up the class more because my teacher just wanted it in rows to start off with. And when I took over the class at the end of the second week I completely reorganised the class (Emma, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Emma recognised that being in the school since the beginning of the year and therefore, witnessing the organisation of the class had provided her with a greater understanding of the logic behind her supervising teacher's decisions in setting up her class. Having this prior knowledge made Emma feel confident that she would be capable of successfully setting up or reorganising a class after she completed her professional experience. Emma's description was consistent with the different expectations of the different school placements for the research participants. As outlined earlier, unlike their participation in the immersion pathway, it is expected that fourth-year students will 'clock up' a significant amount of their professional experience placement actually teaching and so it would make sense that her supervising teacher would expect Emma to manage the classroom and to explore her teaching differently than would be expected through her participation in the immersion pathway. A key aspect of setting up a classroom is deciding on effective behaviour

management strategies to use. As described below, the preservice teachers described a variety of behaviour management strategies they used while on their placements.

6.3b) Behaviour Management

Behaviour management is focused on student behaviour and in particular how the teacher manages to encourage all students to learn and to behave in an appropriate manner. The schools in the current research all had a school-wide behaviour management system in place. In this type of management system the school has a policy that guides all staff, students, parents, and other community members on behaviour that is expected at the school. These professional resources were considered by the preservice teachers to be valuable tools for the development of their professional practice and sense of belonging in the teaching profession. Tools serve a purpose for community membership (Douglas, 2014; Wenger, 1998) and can be used to shape teacher identity and practice through a process of reification and negotiation. The preservice teachers described that they, and all teachers in the school, were issued with behaviour management documents by the school administration. Being given this formal document upon induction into a school can provide an opportunity to a preservice teacher to feel more professional and accepted as a member of a school community (Carter, 2012). The issuance of behavior management documents to the preservice teachers represented a level of acceptance in their school community and access to professional artefacts which could help them to understand how to mediate relations (Wenger, 1998) with students and manage student behaviour. For Roberta, the whole school prospectus that she was given contributed to her knowledge about teaching practice and administrative expectation of the role of teachers in their professional capacity at her school:

It's like a bible of how the school operates. I felt that that just in itself helped to prepare me more. I feel more like a professional because I've got that information in my hands. I know what the expectations of the school are. So, when I am there teaching, I am confident in the ability that I am teaching exactly how the school expects its teachers to teach. So, that's really helped me with my growth as well (Roberta, Interview 1, April, 2015).

All teachers followed the strategies for implementing these policies in the classroom and as Roberta suggested above, this tool bound the community into understanding and implementing a plan that was consistent for all members of the school community. Roberta's understanding of the significance of the whole school prospectus to the whole school community and her position in the school as a user of this professional artefact is complemented by Lave and Wenger's (1991) description of artefacts as the 'technology of practice' that makes access and participation in a community transparent to its members. In the enactment of the policy the preservice teachers in the study shared a number of school-wide behaviour management strategies that they observed. Katherine, for example described a 'gold star' rewards system:

...they did what they call a 'gold star' day. It's a really good behaviour management system that they have going where they try to get the children to behave in an acceptable manner so that they earn a number of points (Katherine, Interview 1, April, 2015).

A similar rewards system was described by Renae:

The school has like a school-wide behaviour thing: Gold, Silver, and Bronze awards. So, to get a Gold award you have to get a certain amount of ticks and you can get five ticks a day for being respectful, being a learner, being organized; a bonus point which you get for not constantly calling out, not throwing things or something like that, and being safe. So, they are based on school rules of being safe, being respectful, and being a learner. If you go to Step One you automatically lose a tick and at the end of the term, how many ticks you had dictated whether you got a Gold, Silver, or Bronze award and whether you participated in the end of term rewards, which was usually a disco, or other thing (Renae, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Understanding the school policy gave the preservice teachers entry into the school community and afforded each of them opportunities to participate in an ongoing process of negotiating meaning. In their daily school experiences the preservice teachers used behaviour management strategies to negotiate their role as teacher with their students and to interact with members of the community as members of the community. These tools provided them with guidance not only about what they should

expect from students in terms of what was acceptable student behaviour but also what was expected of them as teachers (Bobbitt Nolan et al., 2011) as they were obliged to follow the rules and behaviour management procedures like everyone else at the school and as a consequence they were included as members of the school community. The preservice teachers described their observations of how individual teachers applied the policy in their classroom as school rules and how they emulated their supervising teachers' behaviour management practices. Rather than reporting on the behaviour management strategies that they had learned through university coursework several of the preservice teachers referred to their interest in observing and emulating their supervising teacher. Pellegrino's (2010) study found that through their actual participation in the classroom preservice teachers reported that they were able to understand how to use behaviour management strategies and that this learning was influential in shaping their teacher identity. Pellegrino's study cited that in relation to behaviour management strategies the preservice teachers' university classes were not as useful as real classroom experience. Sabrina, for example, learned to emulate her supervising teacher's use of praise to connect with students and to listen respectfully to students about issues they might have:

What I've learned this year is praise...my teacher, she praises the kids very well. She always explains to them what she's happy with and not just like, 'Good work!' It's a lot of, 'I really appreciate you doing this', or 'This has helped me so much', and giving them context to the actual praise. So, they understand why they're being praised for what they're doing and why their good work is appreciated. Also, like in the opposite way, when they're in trouble or when they've done the wrong thing she always [communicates to them with] questions, 'Do you understand why?', and 'Do you think that's reasonable?' And they're given that opportunity to understand to learn from their mistakes I suppose rather than just being yelled at. She's like, 'I'm there. I'm willing to listen to what you have to say.' She will say like, 'Do you understand why I'm moving your name down the list?' or whatever they have to do. She'll say, 'Do you understand?', and 'Do you know you'll get the opportunity to move it up, and we'll be able to work on this?' So, I have never seen that before but it has worked very well. They respect that a lot I think (Sabrina, Interview 1, March, 2015).

Sabrina described her observations of the teacher's interactions with the students as a kind of behaviour management strategy that she had not seen before, but appreciated its effectiveness. Sabrina seemed to admire her supervising teacher and perceived her to be a 'good' teacher who had earned the respect of her students (Furlong, 2013) and she wanted to command the respect of her students in the same way. Through her construction of new knowledge gained from observing her supervising teacher's use of language in the classroom with students, Sabrina appeared to be on a trajectory of planning to use that type of language in the future with her students. She had, in effect, engaged in a process of appropriation (Rogoff, 1995) whereby she would make her supervising teacher's language strategies and forms of praise her own.

Over time the preservice teachers gradually began using their own style of behaviour management particularly when they were completing their professional experience placement, as described by Katherine:

I think the big difference for me was in a prac with your [supervising] teacher...you've got to do a lot of emulating. By being in the immersion pathway, you can start off doing that. Actually, you can bring your own style into it. So, by the time you take over the students are used to both styles of teaching. And my [supervising] teacher said to me what was very successful was the fact I kept a lot of the procedures in place that she had. Because I had known the children for so long and her, I was able to put in place some of my own in there as well (Katherine, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Katherine described that by being at the school through the immersion pathway she had an extended time to really study how her teacher managed the behaviour of the class. She initially took on this style herself, emulating her teacher's approach, but over time found her own feet and began to develop her own style while still maintaining much of what the teacher had established in her class. In line with findings by Chong et al. (2011a), through her immersion pathway experience Katherine was developing herself as a role model for the management of student behaviour. This procedure appeared to be a sort of blending of the teacher's style and her style and because the students had become familiar with both; she experienced a successful outcome for behaviour management. This was a common theme with the preservice

teachers. Renae and Katherine discussed their experiences of learning how to manage student behaviour when resolving what Correa et al. (2014) and Tripp (1994, 2012) would describe as critical incidents in classroom behaviour that allowed them to test out and negotiate their teacher identity further. Renae, for example, described a significant juncture for her when she demonstrated not only to herself but to her students that she could manage their behaviour in class. Although Renae showed some reluctance initially in breaking away from her idealised image of nurturing her students during their learning (Darling-Hammond, 2006) she came to understand the realities of an everyday teacher's work and she saw herself as having crossed a threshold. By doing so, she gained much confidence in her teaching ability and appropriately used a tool of teaching and learning in order to identify herself as a teacher with her students in the classroom:

She [supervising teacher] told me not to take any of their rubbish and just follow through with the whole behaviour management system that the school has going and that's in the classroom as well. So when I was in the room by myself, which was quite a surreal feeling they tested me and I thought, 'Right, this is it. I'm just going to have to do it.' And I did it. I got a few kids onto Step One and they were spoken to severely the next day by my teacher. But after I put them on Step One they knew, and the rest of the class knew that what I was saying, was going to be followed through (Renae, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Renae used the school's behaviour management system with her students in order to handle classroom related behavioural issues. By placing students on 'Step One' of that system, she demonstrated to her students that she was not only a teacher in that classroom but that she was willing to enforce behaviour management processes. Her implementation of the behaviour management system exemplified her participation in the reification of a cultural tool (Wenger, 1998, 2000). That is to say, by practising the use of that tool, she gave its function a concrete meaning in her classroom which was understood by both her and her students.

As their time in the immersion pathway progressed, the preservice teachers' confidence in their ability to manage the classroom grew. Katherine described confidence in her knowledge of the class rules and routines and described that she

realised how this influenced the way students treated her in class when she compared her experience to a relief teacher (supply teacher) who joined her class:

I guess for me the big one being in this immersion pathway would be the establishing and maintaining of the class rules and routines I've actually seen, because we never do pracs from the start of the year. And I believe that my teacher has been really successful in it. I think it has been a big difference to the students and their learning. I've noticed that we seem to be able to get more done with them. Like work that they are doing. We're getting a lot more out of them before we have any mini-crises. And that has just been said by a number of teachers, who have known the kids, about how well and settled they are. It does show however, that when we have somebody in to replace us, such as a supply teacher, how the change to their routine, even so small can make a difference (Katherine, Interview 1, April, 2015).

Katherine described how one day when the teacher was away a supply teacher came to teach the class. The students began to misbehave but Katherine managed to get them under control by reminding them of the class rules and routines. Several of the preservice teachers noted critical incidents, such as misbehaviour or the potential for misbehaviour during teaching practice. This came about early on when they were given the opportunity to manage student behaviour independently from their supervising teacher's intervention. As with the 'supply teacher' incident described by Katherine, the students began to misbehave, almost as if they were testing the preservice teachers' ability to manage the classroom. Developing the skills to manage student behaviour was encouraged by their supervising teacher(s) and allowed the preservice teachers to test out these skills in a safe environment:

I've only just got to stand there and put my hand on my hip and they will start to pull themselves back in line. So, I guess I'm really lucky in that way that she's [supervising teacher] really wanted me to immerse myself properly in the classroom. And she has made me get them to respect me rather than just being respected because of the fact that they've been told to respect somebody. So, I'm very lucky. I could not have asked for a better mentor teacher (Katherine, Interview 1, April, 2015).

The above comments highlight the importance of the preservice teachers' relationships with their supervising teachers. Over time it became evident that the supervising teachers were confident enough in the preservice teachers' teaching skills to allow them to take over their class and engage in LPP (Lave & Wenger, 1991). That is to say, through their engagement in social practices in their school-based CoPs, the preservice teachers were moving away from the periphery of that practice as newcomers and toward full participation in the sociocultural practice of the community. This was a significant part of the immersion pathway placement and the preservice teachers responded to the support of their supervising teachers through feelings of greater confidence in their sense of ownership in teaching. The supervising teachers are indicating that they felt the preservice teachers in the immersion pathway were closely approaching being classroom ready; these findings support research done by Forlin and Chambers (2011) and Taylor and Ringlaben (2012) which stressed the importance of developing classroom ready preservice teachers for the facilitation of learning.

Another key aspect of behaviour management that the preservice teachers came to understand was the role of positive relationships with the students. Negotiation of the meaning that the preservice teachers developed with students in relation to their role as classroom teachers was the result of a continual process of renewed negotiation. Preservice teachers' efforts to improve their relations with students resulted in the production of new relations (Wenger, 1998, 2000) and deeper acceptance as school community members. On a day when one student was leaving the class group to return to his former home country for a family trip, that student acknowledged his appreciation of Katherine's effort to build a relationship with him: This quiet boy had Autism and did not usually speak in class but he made the effort to thank her, talk with her, and engage her in a long conversation for the first time before he went away:

He's autistic and he doesn't say an awful lot. And you don't always know when he's listening or whether he understands what you're saying. But he's a very touchy-feely person, if he likes you he touches. So, he gave me a hug and he actually didn't speak most of the day. He'd have his hand on my arm or if I was sitting down he'd have his hand on my knee and he'd be following me around. And at one point he just turned to me and had a conversation with me. For five minutes he looked me in the eyes and had

one proper conversation. And I thought at that point he has accepted me. He's seeing me more than somebody who's just coming into class and is seeing me more as a teacher and somebody that he feels comfortable with (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Katherine's effort to build relationships with her students was successful and this was evident in the rewarding response of one of the more challenging students in her class. This effort was rewarded by unexpected behaviour from a student who generally was not inclined to become involved with the class. Sabrina also described how she had made a committed effort to build a relationship with a student of hers who had Asperger's syndrome by engaging him through little chats over an extended period of time, and eventually he started to respond to her positively:

I sat with him at different points and chatted with him. He was like the kid who protected me on oval duty; he made sure no balls would hit my head when I was on oval duty. He would wander around and while at first he didn't talk he soon warmed up and we had chats. But it still took a good two to three weeks on that prac where I was there full-time to really get to know him. I think with those kids it's so easy just to yell and think it's his ASD/Asperger's. It's just how he is and he's always going to be that way. But I think I learned a lot about how rewarding those relationships can be (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015).

De Jong et al. (2014) described that students were more positively responsive to preservice teachers who they perceived to be kind and friendly. The professional attitude that both Katherine and Sabrina displayed toward their students with learning difficulties can be described as being considerate and caring and it appeared that their approaches to building relationships with students resulted in strong affiliations. They and the other preservice teachers in the research described several different ways of managing student behaviour. They identified that they needed to be knowledgeable about the school-wide policy on behaviour management but that teachers could individualise strategies to what worked most appropriately with their students in their classes. There was a perceived difference for them while in the immersion pathway and their professional experience placement as their role in the classroom shifted from one space to another. The preservice teachers described that a significant element for

effective behaviour management was developing positive relationships with the students and developing confidence in using their own style of behaviour management but within the processes and procedures already established by their supervising teacher(s). The following section explores the preservice teachers' developing identity specifically through their teaching duties.

6.3c) Teaching Duties

Teaching duties for the preservice teachers in the current research entailed the practice of classroom teaching, the development and management of resources for teaching and learning, and the knowledge gained from teaching experiences learned from involvement in school-based communities. Classroom teaching practice was an area of growth in teacher identity for all of the preservice teachers. Jennifer described that her evolving teacher identity came from small-group, work-based teaching to teaching full lessons which was particularly realised during her professional experience placement:

When I first started I was given small-group work and the occasional full class lesson. But by the end of my prac I had a full week teaching, all day, every day, for the five days. So, I managed transitions, I managed lunch breaks with duty, and all that sort of thing. I taught all the time from the moment the students walked into that classroom to the moment all the students had left the classroom. I was the teacher in that classroom. That was more than I ever taught in my life so that was a great experience (Jennifer, Interview 2, July, 2015).

According to Daniel et al. (2013) preservice teachers need time to rehearse the core skills of teaching in classroom situations and Jennifer's confidence in relation to her teaching duties aligned with this argument. Through a process of LPP (Lave, 1996; Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1998, 2000), transitioning away from their dependency on the supervising teacher(s) to teaching in their own right was pivotal in helping the preservice teachers' identify themselves as teachers and engage closer to full participation in their role of teacher than at the beginning of their immersion pathway experience. Similar to Jennifer's account above, the opportunity to enact full participation as a teacher came for Renae with an afternoon of solo teaching. In

allowing her to take over the class, Renae described that she felt her supervising teacher, the principal, and the deputy-principal were acknowledging not only her ability to teach but her membership in the class as a teacher:

On the third Monday of my prac my teacher was really sick. For the afternoon she organised for me to just teach the kids by myself. The principal and the deputy were all fine with that. So I just ran the afternoon session by myself (Renae, Interview 2, July, 2015).

This kind of acknowledgement helped to increase the preservice teachers' confidence in their teaching abilities. There were many examples of preservice teachers and their respective supervising teachers negotiating the preservice teachers' role as a classroom teacher and their teaching duties. It appeared that both Jennifer and Renae appreciated the provision of autonomy in classroom teaching that preservice teachers in Schmidt's (2010) study valued. The preservice teachers in the current research described many incidents of their developing, and developed, teaching practices and their growing sense of engagement and acceptance in their teaching roles as viewed by others in their school community. Emma recalled an incident indicating to her that she had become a capable teacher and seemingly in her view she was moving closer to full participation as a teacher in her school community:

I was finishing something; I was writing on the board and the bell rang. In the past they [her students] would usually try to get up to leave and I would say, 'I need to make sure that you've done the work.' And they worked really well through this session. I was just going to let them go and we could finish it after the break. But as the bell went, not one of them moved or anything like that. They barely even noticed the bell had rung. They just kept working through because they really wanted to finish it. And I even said to them, 'We can finish this after the break.' And they said, 'No, no, no. We'll just finish it now.' And so just every single one of them just sat there and got that finished. So, I still feel that if you set your expectations high that they will meet them (Emma, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Emma's lesson appears to have engaged the students so completely they were willing to sacrifice some of their lunch break in preference to completing their lesson with her. She described that she had set high expectations for the students' learning

and evidently conveyed these expectations in such a positive way that the students strove to meet this challenge. It appeared that through a process of negotiation with her students that she came to be perceived as a teacher who held high expectations of her students' learning. This perception contributed to Emma's developing teacher identity and her students were accepting of her actions. She conveyed a sense of satisfaction in her teaching in how the students responded so completely to the task set for them and felt she had come to possess a mutually constructed image of being a respected classroom teacher that she imagined of herself as being and that her students perceived her to be.

Learning teaching practice through working together with teaching staff at their school was referred to by all of the six preservice teachers. Professional conversations with their supervising teacher(s) helped the preservice teachers to develop their teacher identity and sense of belonging in the teaching profession. Being asked for her professional opinion gave Katherine the feeling that her supervising teacher respected her as a teaching professional:

We were sitting down and having a conversation, the teacher and myself, about particularly Geography. I said to her that really we needed to rework it [the Geography program] and she said she was thinking the same thing but she wasn't quite sure what she should do because she had been a Prep. [Preparatory] teacher for seven years and this year she's just gone to Year 4 and she said that obviously it was her first time teaching in Year 4 so she needed to get a feel for what it was. And we talked through it and looked through it and she said that when she's teaching it next year that a certain amount of the program you'd get rid of. And she said we can do that and we'd expand on these areas here (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015).

In this instance, Katherine appeared to have been accepted by her supervising teacher as a colleague. As described by Pridham et al. (2013) the level of inclusion shown by Katherine's supervising teacher toward her illustrates that participation in teaching practice-based professional conversations can act as an enabler of preservice teacher identity development and sense of belonging in the school community. The supervising teacher revealed that her own confidence level was challenged by this new

year of teaching which had created some uncertainty in her mind about the best way to go about preparing the Geography program.

Being asked for such input by their supervising teacher(s) was a common theme in the data. These opportunities provided to the preservice teachers by their supervising teacher(s) enabled them to determine, maintain, and negotiate activities and practices, and in the process, create and recreate their teacher identity (Goodnough, 2010) and enhance their sense of belonging within their school community. This supervising teacher appeared to have had a lot of confidence in Katherine's opinion to have this kind of conversation. She was revealing her vulnerability as a teacher in her uncertainty about teaching Geography. As noted by Fuller et al. (2005) when preservice teachers are seen by the school community as contributing members not only is their learning enhanced but the learning of the school community is enhanced, as was the case with Katherine and her supervising teacher. In this instance, the power differential that existed between Katherine and her supervising teacher exhibited the lowest power differential of any of the relationships that preservice teachers revealed in the current research.

Supervising teachers challenged the preservice teachers to try and teach new strategies and deepen both their level of engagement as teaching practitioners and their level of teaching knowledge in practice. In teacher immersion programs preservice teachers have greater and longer opportunities for observing their supervising teacher's teaching and for being observed, and critiqued by their supervising teacher while practising and developing their teaching skills, and this appeared to work to the preservice teachers' advantage in the current research.

In regard to her ability to plan for lessons Emma stated that she initially liked a lot of structure in her teaching. However, because she was encouraged and supported by her supervising teacher to be more independent and flexible in her teaching style she moved toward a less structured approach to teaching by experimenting with her teaching practice and reflecting on that practice:

At first it was a bit daunting because I like a lot of structure but it made me feel more like I was on my very own doing it, like I will be doing next year [once she has become a beginning teacher in her own class]. So, I was able

to test things out and see what worked and I felt I was able to be more reflective with my planning and resources because I had the freedom to do that because she trusted me as a teacher. So, I just tried things out and I was able to reflect on it more. I found it an enlightening experience to see how well uni [university] lined up with the practical side of things and what didn't line up. So, I felt I got a lot out of that, just having that freedom and reflecting and things like that (Emma, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Emma described not only the freedom to try out her skills as a teacher but also the value of taking time to reflect on being a teacher. She was considering the alignment between what she had been taught at university and what she had learned being in the school environment and was able to determine strengths and gaps that helped to inform her professional development. She embraced the opportunity to interpret and reinterpret her teaching practice in the immersion pathway. Emma surrendered her initially idealised image of highly structured teaching practice (Beattie, 2000) and embraced her supervising teacher's advice to adopt more flexible teaching practices. The conflict that Emma felt about her teaching practice as a result of her history as a preservice teacher and her experience with that supervising teacher in the immersion pathway was aligned with Trent's (2011) finding that the construction of becoming a teacher was an ongoing and flexible process. Being given the freedom to explore teaching strategies and different approaches to teaching was a common theme for the preservice teachers. Roberta benefited from being given some autonomy to prepare her lessons and she grew into her role of being the classroom teacher:

Being able to plan my own lessons contributed to my teacher identity because once the assessment finished [there is assessment for professional experience] I could teach whatever I wanted...I was able to bring really engaging lesson plans and that sort of thing. So, as far as my teacher identity went that's when I was able to say, 'Yep, this is my class and this is how it's going to run.' (Roberta, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Roberta's comments align with Schmidt (2010) who described that the provision of autonomy in classroom teaching and planning, the development of contextual teaching knowledge, and a sense of community during professional experience are highly

valued by preservice teachers in helping them to develop a sense of belonging in the community of teaching.

The following examples provided by Jennifer, Roberta, and Katherine demonstrate ways in which tools and artefacts in their classroom contributed to their teaching and learning to bring meaning to the teaching and learning goals of the lesson. These preservice teachers used cultural artefacts (Wenger, 1998) in the classroom specifically designed to be relevant and significant in the shaping students' learning. Developing resources for teaching practice was discussed by several preservice teachers. Jennifer, for example, developed a whole classroom wall display for a Science unit that she and her supervising teacher were going to teach:

I put up a big Science wall with the science vocabulary and it was like 'Top work for the week' or 'Electrifying works'. It was an Electricity unit. And I would take the children's books home. After I taught a science lesson I would photocopy the best picture or the best student work. I'd put it up on that board every day and the kids would come in in the morning and see if their work was on the board or to see what they had to do to get their work on that board. Also, I often brought in resources. Like I brought in a plasma ball one day because we were looking at how conductors worked and we had a look at the electricity moving in the ball. And we looked at circuits so I brought in a whole heap of circuits and the kids sat there and connected them (Jennifer, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Jennifer described several teaching and motivational strategies she used to engage her students in Science as well as artefacts, such as photocopying pictures or students' work to display on the wall and that motivated them to want to have their own work on the board. She brought in extra learning resources, a plasma ball and circuit boards, to enhance student learning. She appeared to have done these activities through her own initiative and in doing so identified that teaching duties extend beyond simply standing in front of a class and teaching. Jennifer's professional development as a practising teacher appeared to have evolved through mediated action (Vygotsky, 1997) when she used these cultural artefacts for teaching and learning with her students. For example, the constructed learning space in a section of the classroom, that is, the 'Science wall' and the attached students' work displayed on it, enabled

members of the school community to project a meaning from these artefacts that resulted in her being identifiable as a teacher and her being able to facilitate learning among her students. She also illustrated that part of her teaching duties included good background preparation and she was rewarded in her efforts with high student interest and participation.

Developing classroom resources was described by all of the preservice teachers in the research as being significant in helping them to feel a sense of community in their classroom. One resource created by Roberta helped her to engage her students in learning activities that also encouraged positive behaviour among students:

I presented a ‘Who wants to be a millionaire?’ game. It was a PowerPoint slide but then I had to change it and put in all my own questions. That’s how I wanted to engage the kids and because the school I was in, it was a disadvantaged school, so sometimes they are completely disengaged when they walked into the classroom in the morning. It is a struggle throughout the day to keep them interested. And because it’s like ‘Who wants to be a millionaire?’ it has prize money. So instead of that I incorporated our own behaviour. If a person answered a question right they got a green dojo for their dojo rewards (Roberta, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Roberta described using an artefact that connected students with something outside the classroom. She brought an everyday object, a game, and reified its purpose and meaning in her classroom to become a learning tool for her students. Whether the students had ever watched the television quiz show of the same name is not known but the idea of adapting a so-called ‘real-world’ activity for the classroom and aligning it with the school policy on behaviour management appeared to have been effective for Roberta. Katherine described using a teaching resource that she had learned about in her university coursework:

I implemented a Pre-spelling test and the students had never had a pre-spelling test beforehand. The first two times that I did it I got a lot of groans, and student comments such as, ‘Do we really have to do this?’ And I would say, ‘Yes, we do have to do this. This is something that I have to do as part of my university course.’ So, I was able to sort of take that

pressure off. By the end of it, the students were loving it (Katherine, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Jennifer, Roberta, and Katherine reified objects by negotiating a meaning of those objects which enabled them to be understood in a way that allowed for them to be implemented as a concrete activity (Wenger, 2000). In doing so, they demonstrated their evolving understanding of the roles and practices of teaching.

Other teaching duties that the preservice teachers engaged in were working with specific curriculums with their supervising teachers. Siegel and Callanan's (2007) study on the mediation of artefacts as teaching aids found that individuals can interpret the purpose(s) of artefacts in different ways and that artefacts must have a context for interpretation. Sabrina, for example, was asked to develop resources that applied to a teaching framework: *Curriculum to Classroom (C2C)*, which was used at a school. She used this curriculum tool in planning a Mathematics lesson:

I did a Maths lesson on Mapping, giving directions and using directional language. So, what I did was, I used masking tape and I taped a grid on the floor. I had different artefacts, not in all the squares, but in certain squares I had different things. And I had the kids write down all of their directions and everything. Originally, it was just a piece of paper that you could put on a projector and you could walk through it in that way but I found that especially directions, when they have to take ten turns, turn left, turn right, and those kinds of things, they find it hard to picture themselves doing it when they're looking at a piece of paper. They can't turn their bodies to match those directions, which is why I put it on the floor and used masking tape. It's just easier to walk through and teach that language, experience it, and put some context towards it (Sabrina, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Sabrina used the artefacts in her lesson to guide student learning, with the C2C paper document and by adding some props she reified the activity lesson plan into a fully interactive learning experience for her students. Reification shapes the individual's experience and having a tool (or artefact) to perform an activity can change the nature of that activity and a teacher's identity within the activity (Wenger, 1998, 2000). It was evident in Sabrina's account that her reification of the curriculum

document helped to shape her teaching practice as a facilitator and teaching practitioner. She demonstrated her ability to engage in practice as meaning in depth successfully. Katherine's supervising teacher gave her access to Individual Curriculum Plans (ICPs). As a tool, ICPs are used in planning lessons and activities when working with students who need more support than that of the general classroom lessons or activities. These might be used for students who have a learning difficulty (for example, where curriculum needs to be adapted to meet students' particular learning levels and needs), as Katherine described:

I had a full list of ICPs. I could use them in my planning. So, I wasn't just walking in and thinking, 'What would you like me to do?' or be at the door and have her asking, 'What can I get you to do?' I could look at my plan and I could say [to myself], 'Alright, those three boys that were on individual curriculum plans, now they need to listen to what I've got to say, they need to know the context. But when I get them to do their work they need to have it differentiated down to a level that they can work at. And I've got somebody who's available to sit down and help them do their work' (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Katherine described several aspects of her teaching duties with the three boys on ICPs. She described how this tool allowed her to quickly identify which three boys needed an adapted curriculum, which she described as *differentiated down to a level that they can work at* (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015), meaning that lessons for these students needed to be at a level different to that of the other students, one that they could work at. Katherine used the ICP as a professional artefact and demonstrated a process of negotiated meaning with her teaching practice as she sought to differentiate learning for her students by interpreting and reinterpreting the application of the C2C in her classroom teaching and learning environment. She also made a comment about *somebody who's available to sit down and help them do their work* (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015). This 'somebody' is another resource in the classroom, another person: a teacher aide or learning support teacher who can be called upon to support the students' learning.

Outside of the regular classroom environment preservice teachers experienced other teaching duties (for example, lunch time duty in the school yard). Teaching duties here

included monitoring student behaviour to prevent accidents and to ensure appropriate behaviour was carried out amongst the students. Katherine described being involved in dealing with a fight between students and accepting her role as a teacher in relation to this incident:

I actually witnessed a fight with the kids. And there was a teacher on duty who was really not confident in trying to stop this fight. So, I just kind got myself into the middle of it and was trying to deal with it when the principal came along with another teacher and she took over and sorted it all out. You know, it's going to happen at some point in my career (Katherine, Interview 1, April, 2015).

Katherine appeared to have taken a fairly philosophical view of the situation by accepting that teaching duties can include sorting out conflict between students. She had successfully aligned herself as a teaching professional in her school community and as someone who could be entrusted with various teaching responsibilities expected of a school teacher. Her experience of managing a conflict between students during her lunch duty supervision represents a tangible example of 'learning by doing' (Lave & Wenger, 1991) as she seemed to just use her common sense to deal with the problem rather than act via any particular learned safety training procedure. This interaction between Katherine and the students affirms the concept that a preservice teacher's learning can be specific to the situation in which it is learned (Lave, 1988). In the immersion pathway preservice teachers were exposed to a variety of teaching duties outside of the classroom and in Katherine's case she had the necessary confidence to manage that responsibility. What is interesting in her comment is the revelation that the qualified teacher on duty was not confident to try and stop the fight, but Katherine was. It should be remembered that Katherine was one of the older mothers in the participant pool. It would be interesting to explore how much of her parenting skills she brought into situations such as these.

This above section considered the various teaching practices in which the preservice teachers engaged. The data revealed that the preservice teachers had opportunities to experience a wide range of teaching practices from understanding school policy to managing individual student learning and behaviour. In each situation the preservice teachers described ways that their involvement contributed to the development of their

teacher identity and sense of belonging at the school. Having been in the school prior to their professional experience, the preservice teachers already felt they had a place in their schools and so could draw on that experience and knowledge to develop their lessons and take on the other duties of teaching with confidence.

6.4 PHILOSOPHY OF TEACHING

As part of the process for teacher registration in Queensland, graduating teachers must submit their philosophy of teaching as part of their application (QCT, n.d.-b). Therefore, it was not surprising that philosophy of teaching was a theme in the current research. While no set formula is expected, the philosophy of teaching statement generally contains preservice teachers' conception of teaching and learning, a description of their teaching practices with a justification for adopting a particular approach to teaching. In the many descriptions accounted for in relation to preservice teacher's philosophy of teaching the preservice teachers in the current research described a fairly deep reflection on their philosophy of teaching which may have occurred because of the extended time they spent in the immersion pathway. The findings from the current research contradict those made by Castellanos Jaimes (2012) who found that preservice teachers were providing a kind of 'lip-service' and that they were not always able to connect teaching theory and pedagogy to their own beliefs and understandings. In the current research the preservice teachers were very conscious of how they would write their philosophy statement for teacher registration. In describing their professional identity beliefs about teaching and learning the data revealed the theme of philosophy of teaching consisted of two categories: a) current teaching, and b) future teaching.

6.4a) Current Teaching

Participation in the immersion pathway placed each of the preservice teachers in a position to reflect on their professional identity, professional practice, and sense of belonging in the teaching profession as they made the transition to becoming graduate teachers in school-based communities. In terms of their role as a teacher each of the preservice teachers conceptualised themselves as a teacher, and no longer a university student, and in this sense they had developed a strong sense of alignment with the

teaching profession. As noted by Simmons et al. (1999) preservice teachers develop their pedagogical philosophies through their perceptions of their social experiences. It is evident from the varied accounts provided in this section that each of the preservice teachers in the current research negotiated and renegotiated their teaching philosophy in part due to the influence of their experiences with members of their school-based communities. While Roberta described that developing a teaching philosophy required time and experience, she also identified an awareness of what she wanted to offer her students in her role as a teacher:

I think it [my philosophy of teaching] is more along the lines of equitable opportunities for all kids. So, that's what I'm there for, to provide those opportunities and make sure that all children are treated equitably...It [school] should be enjoyable and a safe place for them to be. So, I guess that's mine and to make sure that they're fully interactive with their education. That they can see the importance and the authenticity of what we're teaching (Roberta, Interview 1, April, 2015).

A sense of confidence can play a part in the formation of a teaching philosophy as it was the case for Jennifer:

I am a teacher. I feel like a teacher and know the sort of things I would like in my classroom. Through the immersion pathway I have thoroughly developed that skill...my teacher identity is well developed at this point in time and I think as I continue to teach it will continue to develop. But I don't see myself as a prac student anymore. I see myself as a teacher now (Jennifer, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Yet, while Jennifer expressed her confidence in her developing professional identity it was evident that this identity was fragile and vulnerable to change if she was confronted with new challenges and these experiences shaped and reshaped her self-image as a member of her school community and of the teaching profession. She shared an example of a point in time during her professional experience placement at her school when she questioned her professional competency:

I was feeling kind of useless as a teacher because my class was more difficult and I was not receiving the mentoring that I had experienced in the [volunteer days of the] immersion pathway. So, I was actually thinking,

‘Am I actually worthwhile as a teacher? Is this really where I need to be?’ And then I was thinking, ‘How stupid am I thinking about if this is where I need to be when I’m four years through my degree?’ But that lasted about a week and then I managed to get that under control and that reinforced the teaching thing again (Jennifer, Interview 3, November, 2015).

It is interesting to note the difference in self-perception as a competent teacher Jennifer experienced in relation to the two different engagements at the school. Rather than being her usual confident self in the immersion pathway, Jennifer suddenly felt unsupported during her professional experience placement to the point where she felt like giving up teaching. For Jennifer, the change in her situated learning environment, with a new supervising teacher and students, affected her ability to handle her teaching practice and engage in participatory appropriation (Rogoff, 1995). The insufficient level of support provided by her second supervising teacher in the professional experience placement appeared to constrain her ability to become prepared for subsequent involvement in related teaching practices (in the second half of the year) that she perceived herself to be able to manage in the first half of the year during her engagement in the immersion pathway. Although preservice teachers in a study by Caires et al. (2012) described their growing levels of autonomy, self-confidence, and trust about the quality of the skills and knowledge that they acquired during teaching practice, Jennifer’s account of her fluctuating self-belief and teacher identity and the change of teaching environment illustrated the ongoing process of teacher identity development. One might speculate that Jennifer was under more pressure to perform as a teacher during her professional experience placement as this component of her course was evaluated whereas there was no evaluation in the immersion pathway. Participation in the immersion pathway was voluntary. The data suggested that more research into comparing preservice teachers’ perceptions in these two kinds of school engagement is needed to gain a clearer insight into the impact of each on preservice teachers’ professional teacher identity.

Written reflections in the form of journals or note-taking represented professional artefacts which assisted preservice teachers in articulating their thoughts and experiences about teaching and learning (Wray, 2007) and their educational philosophies. Jennifer felt that her use of a coursework teaching journal that she kept

for reflecting on her engagement in the immersion pathway helped to shape and confirm some of her beliefs about her philosophy of teaching:

I was reading through them [my journal entries] before I had to hand the journal back [to my university teacher] and I surprised myself with how reflective I can be and how much my reflection, especially throughout this immersion pathway, has developed who I am as a teacher because I sat there and thought about things and when I read through it again I thought, ‘Wait a minute, that still totally resonates with me. I’m still thinking about those things in the same way’ (Jennifer, Interview 3, November, 2015).

The concept of continual reflection on university coursework helped Katherine to rethink how she wants to relate to her students. For Jennifer, as noted above, and Katherine, keeping a journal of reflections-on-practice helped them to develop their pedagogical philosophies through their perceptions of their social experiences (Simmons et al., 1999) and a sense of awareness of their practice. As part of Katherine’s university coursework, and for all of the preservice teachers (as indeed all fourth-year preservice teachers in the BEd degree program), she had to complete 20 hours of voluntary Service learning in the local community. The immersion pathway provided preservice teachers with opportunities to examine their beliefs critically in relation to visions of good teaching (Feimen-Nemser, 2001). Katherine’s Service learning was working with students and staff in the Students with Disabilities (SWD) Centre. In this setting she was challenged to work with a diverse range of students and this experience made her reconsider her teaching approach which, ultimately, had an impact on her developing teaching philosophy:

I found that just writing a few notes down every day after I’d finished just helped clear my mind about what I had been doing. I did it [Service learning] in the SWD Centre. It really opened my eyes up to the individual differences of all these students, the parents, and the community. I’m from a middle-class background so I’ve never experienced these forms of poverty that in some cases I’m seeing. It has really affected me so much so I think that the way that I’m teaching is changing, hopefully changing for the better. That it’s a bit more student relationship-focused rather than just worrying about student results (Katherine, Interview 1, April, 2015).

This statement reflects a common situation cited in the literature that the majority of primary school teachers in Australia are middle-class females with Anglo-Australian backgrounds who have had little exposure to children with backgrounds as diverse as what they witness during their school-based professional experiences (Connelly & Joske, 2001; Hodgetts, 2010). The extended period of time spent in the school communities contributed to the preservice teachers' developing awareness of students' learning needs and sense of well-being (Appl & Spenciner, 2008) which helped to shape how they related to students. Like Katherine, Jennifer also experienced immersion in a so-called disadvantaged school community and this placement affected the formation of her philosophy of teaching. Jennifer wanted to help her students develop confidence and make a difference in students' lives. Through this placement she began to perceive herself as someone who could help her students to develop holistically:

We [she and her supervising teacher] asked the students what they were good at and one of the kids said, 'I'm good at spending my mother's money.' Whereas she didn't know that she's a good reader or that she has very neat handwriting or that she has a way with people. So, it's important that they [students] have that sense of accomplishment, that belonging within them. And it's important that I provide that for them. It's not always academic, especially in the lower socioeconomic schools that I've been in. It's more about developing them as a person. And I know that I can do that through my practice as a teacher (Jennifer, Interview 2, July, 2015).

For Renae, her engagement in a disadvantaged school gave her a strong sense of responsibility toward her students' welfare. She felt responsible as a teacher to offer her students some things that their home life might be deficient in giving them:

Their achievements and accomplishments should be celebrated, not only within the classroom but within the whole school and the wider community so that they get that feeling of success because for a lot of these kids, they don't get it at home. So, I think that by having a classroom that provides that and encourages that then you're more likely to have children that will try that little bit extra harder maybe because they know that they're valued and that you want them to be there, whereas at home they might not get that (Renae, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Correa et al. (2014) suggested that preservice teachers tend to enter teacher education with an idealised image of teaching with little knowledge of the everyday realities of a teacher's life. Despite all of the preservice teachers involved in the immersion pathway having prior short-term placements in schools of various socio-economic status Katherine, Jennifer, and Roberta provided insights into the depth of awareness that they gained by being immersed in a disadvantaged school environment for an extended period of time in the immersion pathway and how this exposure contributed to the way they perceived their teaching philosophy.

Several preservice teachers raised the point of needing to be flexible in their approach to teaching students. McDermott (2008) found that developing a philosophy of teaching is not a static thing and that it shifts over time and in relation to preservice teachers' engagement in different contexts and different relationships made along the way that contribute to shaping their beliefs. Preservice teachers in the immersion pathway showed the evolving nature of one's professional philosophy based upon a variety of contexts and relationships in their school-based community. Katherine, for example, became aware of her evolving belief in the importance of her role as a teacher to adapt to student needs in relation to specific situations:

I am into believing that...I'm the one that has to adapt to the students. The students shouldn't have to adapt to the teaching because I'm seeing kids that have got all different kinds of issues. And some of the issues are school-related and learning-related (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015).

Likewise, Sabrina described that in order to be successful as a teacher she had to be flexible and adaptable to students and their needs:

To have to completely 180 [degrees] and turn around what my perceptions were, it was difficult because you can't just change what these kids have had for seven or eight months of the year into something that I liked to do. They couldn't adapt to a new teacher. So, probably the most significant thing was changing how I taught and changing the things that I was doing in my lessons, the way I spoke to these kids, making sure that I catered for these kids in a different way to what I had done previously (Sabrina, Interview 3, November, 2015).

The realisation that Sabrina came to about the importance of relationships with her students was congruent with the finding made by Harlow and Cobb (2014) that preservice teachers described the need to build strong relationships with students to create effective learning environments. Sabrina recognised that she and her supervising teacher appeared to have divergent approaches to teaching the students in this classroom. Yet, she successfully modified her approach to teaching to better relate to the teaching style of her supervising teacher and how it influenced student learning in this classroom environment throughout the year until that point in time.

On the whole, the preservice teachers in the current research gained considerable understanding of what it means to be flexible as a teacher and the effort they made to reimagine themselves in their role as teachers as they continued to develop their teacher identity. Katherine's example mirrored that of the other preservice teachers above in that she came to appreciate that the needs of her students go beyond the classroom walls:

...there will be...situations that have to do with their families at home. And I think that the education system doesn't really fit all of those. And I think it's up to me as a teacher to help them to get the education that they need and the sense of belonging, that sense of community by the way that I make sure that I differentiate to all of them (Katherine, Interview 2, July, 2015).

One of the few times the preservice teachers mentioned age in their reflections occurred in relation to their developing philosophy of teaching. Age and experience can be influential forces on one's self-belief in being a teacher but little research has been conducted in this area. Sabrina referred to her youth in regard to her confidence in her professional identity. She compared her age and life experience to that of some of the older preservice teachers participating in the immersion pathway:

It's a different perspective because being that bit older you are sure of yourself. You know how you work and how best you work, whereas you are still learning and growing when you're 22. I am turning 23 this year and you are just not as sure of yourself, I suppose (Sabrina, Interview 1, March, 2015).

As earlier data revealed, however, age was not necessarily a factor in confidence levels. Roberta, one of the older preservice teachers, began her immersion pathway placement in an unsupportive environment. She described her place in this learning situation where she felt she was ‘part of the furniture’ and so not appreciated or supported in her teacher identity development. Age may have been a factor, in that the supervising teachers may have expected Roberta to be more like them, but the factor of age was not mentioned by Roberta in this situation and so it must be left to speculation.

As well as reflecting on their current roles as teachers in the immersion pathway, the preservice teachers reflected on what their future teaching selves would be. A common goal for each of them was to become beginning teachers the following year. Therefore, their thoughts and perceptions were sometimes focused on their future teaching which impacted on their currently developing philosophy of teaching, as described below.

6.4b) Future Teaching

Looking to their future in the teaching profession some preservice teachers in the current study gained greater clarity in their professional identity and their sense of belonging. Moseti Ongaki (2014) suggested that without explicit guidance when writing a statement of teaching philosophy preservice teachers may struggle with explaining how their pedagogical philosophies are related to their epistemological beliefs or their perceived future effectiveness as teachers. However, in the current research there is substantial evidence that the preservice teachers were able to eruditely explain their developing philosophy of teaching orally and relate their beliefs to their future as teaching professionals. Several of the preservice teachers in the current research made reference to the developing professional philosophy evolving over their participation over an extended period of time in the immersion pathway. An extended period of time immersed in a school-based community helped Roberta, for example, to develop the mindset that she would be competent in managing her teaching practice in the future. Roberta’s perception about her teaching competency and level of confidence at the end of her immersion pathway experience contradicts O’Neil and

Stephenson's (2013) findings that on the whole preservice teachers left teacher training only somewhat prepared to manage classrooms near the end of their university studies. Although she recognised that there could be moments of doubt awaiting her the following year when she becomes a beginning teacher she reflected on her ability to manage her teaching practice this year confidently and to become aligned to her school community practices due to her participation in the year-long immersion and her sense of growing alignment with the teaching profession and in wanting to become a teacher in the future:

I know that as I go into next year, as a beginning teacher I still may have some of that self-doubt. I don't doubt that whatsoever because the stakes are going to be a little bit higher next year. But I know that while that will be in the back of my mind I can say, 'You know what? I did it.' By the end of last year I could do that so I know that I can start off the year with that confidence in myself (Roberta, Interview 3, November, 2015).

For Emma, her immersion in a disadvantaged school gave her a sense of understanding about the best school setting for her future teaching career:

After being in this course, I still love kids, I still want to make a difference but I want to do it in these schools with these kids because that's where it's needed. I suppose that's part of my professional identity, wanting to make a difference in those particular schools (Emma, Interview 3, November, 2015).

Exposure to a specific community at her school made Katherine realise the direction that she wanted to move toward in her future teaching career. She experienced a strong connection with staff at the SWD Centre at her school:

I actually see long-term me heading down that path because that seems to be something that fits quite well with my philosophy of teaching really that anybody can learn and we've just got to find the right way to teach. So, that's what I was talking about with the lady the other day. Asking the SWD teacher, 'What can I do after I graduate to be able to get into this kind of centre?' (Katherine, Interview 1, April, 2015).

For Emma and Katherine their construction and reconstruction of their self-image of being a teacher over the year led them to reshape how they wanted to be involved in the teaching profession. The abovementioned experiences of these two preservice teachers affirm the notion that preservice teachers learn things which are specific to the situation in which they are learned (Lave, 1988) during their professional experience. In Emma's case, the issue was with where she would like to teach; whereas for Katherine the issue was about what type of teacher she would like to be in the future.

One preservice teacher's engagement in the immersion pathway cemented her interest in raising the expectations that students have of themselves in order to prepare them for their future in classrooms and post-school life. Emma's student-oriented teaching philosophy was an aspect of her developing professional practice:

My philosophy would be to do with my expectations with every student and helping them to increase their expectations that they have of themselves. To expect more from themselves and to believe more in what they can achieve and what they can do with their lives. And to be that stable, positive role model in their lives and show [them] that love for learning and that learning is not restricted to Maths and English. But that it's a life-long thing that you should enjoy, in getting better and knowing more, seeking knowledge, and things like that (Emma, Interview 1, April, 2015).

In her immediate teaching future Sabrina had made a plan to cultivate relationships with her students and focus on the setup of her classroom so that she could offer a supportive learning environment. She felt that these elements of her developing teaching practice were important foci for when she teaches in her own classroom next year as a beginning teacher:

Taking the time and building that rapport and relationship with your children is going to be like my Number One initial thing with setting up my room and meeting a new class and that kind of thing because I think that it sets the expectation but it sets you up for the rest of the year. Your life is so much easier when you have a class that respects you and you

respect them. They are more willing to try new things and work harder for you when they know you appreciate it (Sabrina, Interview 1, March, 2015).

The extent to which preservice teachers in the immersion pathway perceived their supervising teachers as actually meeting their 'idealised' standards impacted how they saw their future selves as teachers (Furlong, 2013) and their developing philosophy of teaching. Sabrina felt that she owed much of her student-oriented teaching philosophy to the relationships she observed in the classroom between her supervising teachers and students in her classrooms. These relationship dynamics became a strong influence on her developing professional identity, her thinking about teaching, and how she wants to be seen by her students:

She's [her supervising teacher] really given me a lot to think about and shown me the kind of teacher that I would like to be. I'm basing a lot of my beliefs and values as a teacher on how she runs her classroom because I've never seen a class that adores their teacher as much as these guys already adore her (Sabrina, Interview 1, March, 2015).

Like Sabrina, Jennifer commented on her interest in developing a teaching philosophy that was student-centred and future focused. She perceived her role as a teacher to include the job of motivating her students to develop a respect for and interest in learning in order to better their future lives:

In my current class I've got one boy and he lives with his grandparents and school finishes at 2:30. But by 3:00 he is in plain clothes back in the school grounds riding his bike around. So for him, it must be his safe place. I want to be part of that and help him to learn and give these children the best opportunity to learn because in lower socioeconomic areas education seems to be the way that they will move forward (Jennifer, Interview 1, April, 2015).

A philosophy of teaching that considered aspects of future teaching gave preservice teachers greater clarity in their professional identity, competency in their teaching practices, and a stronger sense of belonging in the teaching profession. In relation to their philosophy of teaching, data revealed preservice teacher appreciation and interest in working in disadvantaged schools in their future, their interest in meeting their

students' needs in the classroom and in helping their students to become aware of the value of education in their future lives.

6.5 CONCLUSION

This chapter presented the findings of the research. The overarching focus of this research was teacher identity development, which included a major theme, a sense of belonging and three themes, relationships, teaching practice, and philosophy of teaching. The data revealed that preservice teachers gained confidence and a broader range of skills and experiences through their participation in the immersion pathway than would have been available to them had they engaged only in the mandatory professional experience placements. In each situation the preservice teachers described ways that their involvement contributed to the development of their teacher identity and sense of belonging at their school. This extended time in their school helped them to understand more fully and deeply what teaching involves and what it means to be a teacher. Their time in the immersion pathway helped to shape their teacher identity particularly when they could perceive themselves as being accepted as a member of the school community. During the preservice teachers' engagement in the immersion pathway, several of these individuals discussed situations in which they held divergent perspectives on issues, such as how their supervising teacher(s) should behave and the compatibility of a supervising teacher's teaching style with their own teaching style. These experiences appeared to contribute to preservice teachers' professional identity development. In the main, each of the preservice teachers in the current study shared substantially positive interpretations of their experiences with the researcher which helped to enable the development of their professional identity, professional practice, and sense of belonging in their school community. However, there were various incidents discussed in this chapter which bring attention to preservice teachers' experiences that negatively affected and constrained such development at various points throughout the year-long immersion.

The following chapter provides a discussion of the major findings from Chapter 6 under the major theme and themes derived from the data, accounts for limitations in the current research, presents the conclusions of the study, and makes recommendations for future research in the area.

Chapter 7: DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of the current research was to explore fourth-year preservice teachers' identity development through their participation in a year-long immersion pathway. Through the discussion of the findings it will become apparent that belonging in the school community was crucial in contributing to preservice teachers' developing sense of a professional teacher identity. Findings from the current research align with the research findings of Wenger (1998, 2000), Battey and Franke (2008) and others who described identity development as forever evolving and changing. Section 7.1 presents a discussion of the findings from the current research in relation to the concepts of legitimate peripheral participation (section 7.1.1) and identity development over time (section 7.1.2). In section 7.2, the various school community-based relationships which contributed to preservice teachers' development of professional teacher identity is discussed. The discussion on relationships is divided into the following subsections: relationships with supervising teachers (section 7.2.1), relationships with fellow preservice teachers (section 7.2.2), and relationships with students (section 7.2.3). Findings in relation to the development of preservice teachers' philosophy of teaching and shaping of beliefs about teaching and learning is considered in section 7.3. Section 7.4 presents a discussion on important findings about the personal characteristics of age and parenthood as aspects of identity development. Findings from the current research contribute to scholarship in several significant key areas and are outlined in section 7.5. Limitations of the current research are discussed in section 7.6. Recommendations for the education of preservice teachers are presented in section 7.7. Section 7.8 provides the conclusion of the chapter in relation to the key findings of the current research.

7.1 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion covers findings in relation to LPP (section 7.1.1) and preservice teachers' transition in the immersion pathway away from the periphery of practice as

new-comers and toward full participation in the sociocultural practice of the community. The extended length of time in the schools significantly influenced preservice teachers' identity development, which is discussed in section 7.1.2.

7.1.1 Legitimate Peripheral Participation

A significant overarching theme in relation to developing teacher identity was preservice teachers' sense of belonging in their school communities. Being immersed and accepted into school-based CoPs (Wenger, 1998) allowed the preservice teachers to see and experience what it means to be a teacher. The data revealed that the longer the preservice teachers participated in the school community, the greater their sense of belonging in the community grew and the more expansive their perceptions of self as teachers grew. While not fully teachers in the schools, the preservice teachers' sense of belonging lines up with the notion of LPP (Lave, 1996; Lave & Wenger, 1991; Wenger, 1998, 2000). Lave and Wenger (1991) described LPP as something more than simply occupying a particular role in a community. Instead, it involves a process of engagement where participation means simultaneously engaging in several roles. Through such engagement, preservice teachers learn the subtle ways of being within that community where their learning becomes an integral and inseparable aspect of the social practice of teaching.

Wenger (1998) described that belonging in a community involves three modes: *engagement, imagination, and alignment*. *Engagement* is the 'active involvement in mutual processes of negotiated meaning' (p. 173). For the preservice teachers, engagement came about through the relationships they formed with various members in the community, particularly with their supervising teachers who provided guidance on the day-to-day dynamics of being a teacher. Through their relationships the preservice teachers were able to negotiate a place for themselves as teachers within each unique classroom and school community. When their position was accepted by the school community the preservice teachers gained in positive development, whereas conflict created barriers. Hodkinson and Hodkinson (2004) and others (Graham & Roberts, 2007; Mueller & Hindin, 2011) suggested that power is an influence on these relationships and, therefore, can work to support preservice teachers or cause them to feel marginalised. While five of the preservice teachers experienced positive

relationships with their supervising teachers, initially in her placement Roberta did not have a positive experience with her first supervising teacher in the immersion pathway. The conflict between the teachers in the classroom she was initially assigned to compromised her engagement in the classroom community. When she was moved into another school she experienced a positive sense of belonging. As a result, Roberta felt connected and engaged in the classroom and the school community.

A sense of belonging through *imagination* refers to a 'process of expanding our self by transcending our time and space and creating new images of the world and ourselves' (Wenger, 1998, p. 176). Imagination in this sense includes the production of images of self and the world, and the major image-makers and identifiers of acceptance for the preservice teachers were found through professional artefacts. Artefacts can be interpreted in different ways by different people in the same community (Day & Kington, 2008; Siegel & Callan, 2007; Wenger, 1998, 2000). For one preservice teacher in the current research, Emma, her inclusion in a school staff photograph was one artefact that contributed to her sense of belonging and development of a teacher identity at her school. Two important points in relation to this artefact contributed to her sense of belonging. One, the fact that this artefact was on display for the rest of the year at the school for all school community members to see legitimised her belonging; and two, that she as a preservice teacher was invited to be in the photograph by the principal of the school. Having this senior staff member issue the invitation is an example of a consolidating experience of a preservice teacher's sense of legitimacy in the community.

Another artefact was a teacher's name badge. One of the preservice teachers, Jennifer, received a name badge with the title of *prac teacher* rather than her name. While on one hand, the badge gave Jennifer a legitimate place in the school, on the other hand not including her name on the badge made her feel as if she was a nameless person in the school and that she did not fully belong. In another example, Roberta was never issued with a teacher's badge (or identification badge) at her school so she started wearing her university's student identification badge which included her name and photograph thereby creating for herself a perception of LPP in the school community. Having a continuous physical presence in the school was a symbolic way for the preservice teachers to be identified by others as being in the community for

reasons more than simply occupying a particular role (Lave & Wenger, 1991). Their presence whether in person, as a photograph on the wall, or via possession of a teacher's badge, gave the preservice teachers a sense of legitimacy in their school community. Burke and Stets (2009) described that it is the individual's perception of who they are and how they are situated in a community that is central to identity formation and this was the case for the preservice teachers in the current research.

A sense of belonging through *alignment* refers to the 'coordination of...energies, actions, and practices' of the community (Wenger, 1998). In this form of belonging, the preservice teachers aligned their behaviour with expected rules and practices of the community. Without doing so, they were positioned to fail in their pursuit of becoming teachers. Roberta, for example, commented on the school prospectus that all teachers used, describing it as a 'bible of how the school operates'. Having the support of this artefact allowed her to believe that she was 'teaching exactly how the school expects its teachers to teach' thereby aligning herself as a teacher in the community. The school prospectus was information specific to her profession and her possession and use of it allowed her to experience a feeling of confidence in how she approached teaching and learning.

The preservice teachers took proactive steps to engage with members of the community from the very early stages of their professional experience in the immersion pathway through participation in PD sessions during student-free days and many other activities throughout the year. The data revealed that the longer the preservice teachers engaged in their school community, the stronger their sense of belonging grew. Darling-Hammond (2012) suggested that one of the main problems facing teacher education programs is that teacher education is too theoretical and not enough time is given to practising the theories learned in a concrete way. It was found in the current research that participation in the immersion pathway assisted the preservice teachers in understanding the connections between teaching and theory as reflected in their developing teaching philosophies. Beattie (2000) noted that many preservice teachers initially understand teaching as showing, telling, and performing, partly due to the limited time they actually spend in school communities before they graduate. By being immersed in the whole school community over a year, the preservice teachers were able to develop a teacher identity that went well beyond a

simple traditional image of a teacher being someone who stands in front of a class of students and tells and shows them what to do. The year-long immersion allowed the preservice teachers to appropriate the ways in which experienced teachers talk, act, and be teachers. It allowed them time to evolve into their role of being a teacher (Wenger, 1998) where they were becoming experts in their community through their evolving knowledge and understanding of school dynamics.

7.1.2 Time for Identity Development

Time to become a teacher was a major factor in supporting the preservice teachers' developing teacher identity. While the length of time in their school was important so was the time placement for engagement. In particular being placed in schools in the student-free days at the beginning of the school year was described by the preservice teachers as extremely important for them. Traditionally, professional experience placements occur at the end of a university semester, at a time when schools are near the end of their second term (around the halfway point of the school year) and have firmly established classroom rules and routines. Preservice teachers who generally only engage in professional experience at the beginning of a school year do so because their course has been interrupted for some reason and they are making up coursework to complete their program in a timely manner. Once this professional experience is finished, they leave the school. The research participants, however, stayed on in the school not within the capacity of completing professional experience practicum blocks and a final internship but as volunteer teacher trainees. The student-free days provided them with opportunities to understand why their supervising teachers adopted the classroom management rules and routines they did, allowed them to understand how to develop curriculum with peers, and helped them to understand the school culture. More importantly, being in the school from the beginning of the year gave the preservice teachers a perception of presence in the schools as it was during this time that acceptance was shown to them by the school community.

Perception of self as a teacher is particularly important for preservice teachers to have at this point of their teacher education. As fourth-year university students they were on the brink of entering the teaching profession as graduate teachers. A part of feeling prepared for their first year of teaching is related to how graduate teachers

perceive themselves to be teachers (Poulou, 2007). The preservice teachers in the current study described themselves as being very ready for their roles as teachers and this perception of self was due to their immersion in a school community. An example of this was described by Sabrina who at the beginning of her immersion perceived herself as ‘always being the baby’ because of her young age. However, by the end of her placement she was able to appreciate how much she had grown into becoming the teacher she wanted to be. A consolidation of acceptance was shown by the school community in that each of them was offered employment at their school upon their graduation.

Participation in the immersion pathway allowed the preservice teachers to develop relationships with many stakeholders in the school community. Findings suggested that the various relationships the preservice teachers developed provided them with vital clues on how the community functioned and, therefore, how they should behave as contributing members of the community. The preservice teachers noted that conversations with staff at the front office (reception) of the school, experiences with teacher aides, other support staff, and generally with all staff in the lunch room allowed them to truly belong in the community and thus positively impacted on their developing professional teacher identity. Wenger (1998) suggested that learning to become a member of a community is an *interplay* between social competence and professional experience. The impact of relationships on preservice teachers’ teacher identity development and sense of belonging is discussed below.

7.2 RELATIONSHIPS

The theme of relationships, out of the three themes to emerge from the data, was highly rated as being critical to the preservice teachers’ developing teacher professional identity, to their developing teaching practice, and overall to their sense of belonging in their particular school community. The significance of the influence that relationships can have on the development of teacher identity was noted by Beattie (2000, p.4), who stated, ‘the idea that learning takes place in relationships, and that the self is formed, given meaning, and understood in the context of its relations with others, is central to the process of becoming a teacher and of learning to teach.’ How the preservice teachers perceived and positioned themselves in the various community

relationships was essential in contributing to the development of their professional teacher identity, allowing them to ‘negotiate meaning’ (Wenger, 1998) about what it means to be a teacher. Waddell (2010) suggested that a recognised way to retain teachers in the school system is to support them in a context that fosters positive relationships. In a school community interpersonal relationships are a primary influence in the formation of teacher identity, especially cooperation with others, such as with the students, school teachers, university lecturers supporting school placements, and preservice teacher peers (Timostsuk & Ugaste, 2010). It has been found that preservice teachers who value school community-based relationships during their professional experience gain positively in relation to the development of their professional identity (Joseph & Heading, 2010; Mutton et al., 2010).

7.2.1 Relationships with Supervising Teachers

One of the most significant relationships for the preservice teachers in the current research was the one they had with their supervising teachers. The preservice teachers learned to negotiate with their supervising teachers on strategies about how to teach, how to interact with students and other school community members, and generally how to behave as a teacher. These opportunities not only led the preservice teachers to hone their teaching skills but also led to them to be perceived by others as a teacher rather than as a preservice teacher. They often described themselves as a ‘colleague’ in the school. These findings align with other research (Edwards & Mutton, 2007; Ferrier-Kerr, 2009; Serota & Bennett, 2007) which demonstrated that sound professional relationships with supervising teachers are central to the growth of practices, beliefs, and identity as a teacher.

Ferrier-Kerr’s (2009) research highlighted the importance of personal connectedness, noting that for preservice teachers, ‘connecting’ and ‘clicking’ with their supervising teacher was crucial in establishing a strong professional relationship. When there were problems developing these relationships, teacher identity was compromised. One of the preservice teachers in the current study, Roberta, changed schools halfway into her year-long pathway due to a problematic and unprofessional situation that she felt she was being drawn into against her will. This situation resulted in her not being able to connect with that particular supervising teacher and influenced

Roberta's perception of feeling devalued in the classroom. In this case Roberta did not have a role model to provide her with guidelines on how to behave appropriately as a teacher, but she knew enough that what she was experiencing was having a negative impact on her learning. Chong et al. (2011b) found that preservice teachers expect that their experiences in schools will contribute to their professional growth as teachers. When this did not happen for her, Roberta requested to change her situation to another class (with a new supervising teacher).

Important for preservice teachers, in relation to their observations of expert teachers in schools was having supervising teachers who adopted the role of mentor and encouraged the preservice teachers to take chances in a supportive and safe environment. The preservice teachers in the current research all described situations where they felt trusted and supported by a supervising teacher which helped them feel confident in what they were doing. These findings concur with that of Correa et al. (2014) who found that preservice teachers gained confidence when resolving 'critical incidents' in classroom behaviour that allowed them to test out and negotiate strategies to work with students. Preservice teachers in the study by Correa et al. who felt supported took on more risks in trying out new strategies and techniques for teaching. Similarly, preservice teachers in the current study who felt supported were prepared to take risks in their teaching. Katherine, for example, felt challenged by the idea of teaching a group of students with learning difficulties but once immersed in teaching them she determined that this was an area of teaching she now wanted to pursue for her career. Without being given the opportunity and support to take risks preservice teachers are in danger of limited professional growth.

It should be remembered, however, that participation in the immersion pathway is not evaluated as a coursework assessment by the supervising teacher so the preservice teachers were able to develop a different kind of relationship with their supervising teachers than they might have done during a mandatory professional experience block practicum or final internship. Being in a pathway that is not evaluated by their supervising teacher(s) (and is a voluntary part of their university degree program) may have relieved some pressure on the preservice teachers that allowed them to feel more confident to take risks that they may not have taken on during a mandatory professional experience placement. Although it was not the focus of the current research such a

comparison of perspectives of preservice teachers and their supervising teacher(s) in regards to this different kind of professional relationship warrants further research.

7.2.2 Relationships with Fellow Preservice Teachers not in the Immersion Pathway

Engagement in the immersion pathway differed from a mandatory professional experience placement in that the preservice teachers volunteered to participate in the immersion pathway in non-teaching roles, although they were engaged in teaching as negotiated with the classroom teachers. However, it is probable that the research participants' sense of belonging was enhanced through the combination of being in the same school for both their engagement in the immersion pathway and for their professional experience placement. Indeed, some of the participants in the research commented on a comparison between themselves and fellow preservice teachers (who were not in the immersion pathway) at their school for their professional experience. The research participants described themselves as being more involved and immersed community members of the school compared with colleagues who had only arrived at the school for professional experience and were only going to stay for their mandatory four-week placement. Having established their place in the school since the beginning of the year, the research participants could use that sense of belonging to settle more quickly into their professional experience placements. They commented on how they helped their colleagues as comparative experts about the school culture and community.

The preservice teachers in the current research felt confident enough in their capabilities as a teacher at the school that they, in turn, acted as mentors to fellow preservice teachers who came to the school for their mandatory professional experience placements. The research participants took on advisory roles and supported their fellow preservice teachers who were not in the immersion pathway but facing difficulties or barriers with students in the classroom in the same school community. Because they had been at the school since the beginning of the year the research participants were able to develop a rapport with the staff and students that their peers did not share. Nor did the professional experience preservice teachers know the school community in the same way and with the same depth as the immersion pathway

preservice teachers. The consensus was that engagement in the immersion pathway had provided the participants with time and opportunities to develop the skills and practices to confidently identify themselves as teachers in the school who were clearly approaching being classroom-ready on a much deeper level than their peers.

One of the preservice teachers, however, reported that she struggled on her professional experience when she compared expectations for this assessed engagement with the unassessed engagement of participation in the immersion pathway. There has been no research located by the researcher which specifically explores the development of preservice teachers' sense of belonging in a school through this dual role of immersion and professional experience. These findings suggest that consideration needs to be given in teacher education to provide preservice teachers with more opportunities to participate in schools beyond the required assessed professional experience placements to assist them in developing a sense of belonging at the school. The current research would suggest that there may well be a difference that is worth exploring particularly as some of the preservice teachers in the study struggled on their mandatory professional experience placements in comparison to how well they managed their experience in the immersion pathway. The stakes for professional experience were higher for the preservice teachers because it was an evaluated, mandatory component of their course whereas participation in the immersion pathway was voluntary with no assessment attached. O'Neill and Stephenson's (2013) research revealed that on the whole preservice teachers leave university 'only somewhat prepared' to manage classrooms and that those who have high confidence near the end of their coursework experience also had decreased levels of confidence in their ability to manage disruptions to class routines and noncompliant behaviour. Their study found that new teachers felt confident that they knew a wide range of strategies and how to use them from what they had learned at university; they felt confident that they could use these teaching strategies. In the current study a lack of confidence in managing student behaviour had the potential to undermine such confidence. Emma, for example, described that she felt a different pressure on her to perform as a teacher on professional experience than she did through her engagement in the immersion pathway. The other participants in the research did not experience the degree of concern expressed by Emma but there was general agreement that being

in the immersion pathway was different to being on a mandatory professional experience placement.

7.2.3 Relationships with Students

Relationships that were developed with students were perceived by the preservice teachers as being very important to their teacher identity development. Indeed it was their being perceived by students as a *teacher* that had a ‘knock-on’ effect of the preservice teachers perceiving themselves as teachers. During their year-long immersion the preservice teachers engaged in all aspects of teaching both in the classroom and the general school environment to the point where they were seen not as preservice teachers but more as legitimate teachers by the students. However, as the immersion pathway was not focused on having the preservice teachers actually teach lessons the significant teaching duties which the preservice teachers engaged in were classroom and behaviour management activities. Being able to successfully manage both a whole class and individual students’ behaviour was perceived by the participants as extremely important in contributing to their identities as teachers. Edwards and Protheroe (2004) suggested that preservice teachers learn how to behave as teachers by observing ‘how it is done’ by expert teachers. Observing how to speak with students, using both verbal and non-verbal language, when to intervene to manage behaviour and what strategies to use most appropriately for a given situation through one’s practical application in a school environment can contribute to a preservice teacher’s understanding of the subtle nuances of teaching.

The change in perception of self can be attributed partly to the confidence the preservice teachers developed through their engagement over the year-long immersion. These findings concur with those of the study by Woods et al. (2014) where a long-term association within the school environment changed the way preservice teachers in that study interacted with their students. In the study by Woods et al. the idealised relationship of a warm and caring friendship between students and the teacher evolved into a more professional relationship for the preservice teachers. These preservice teachers came to understand that they had a responsibility to adopt a more professional identity as a teacher when interacting with the students. As indicated above these findings were replicated in the current research.

The extended period of time spent in the school communities contributed to the development of preservice teachers' feelings of social competence in their roles as teachers much in line with Appl and Spenciner's (2008) findings that preservice teachers need to develop an understanding of how their relationships with students affects their students' learning and sense of well-being. Renae, for example, described how at the beginning of the school year her class had to move to a temporary location while building construction was completed at the school and how well the teacher (her supervising teacher) facilitated this move so that it would have as little a negative impact on student learning as possible. Being able to observe first-hand how expert teachers managed the day-to-day practicalities of teaching provided the preservice teachers with not only an understanding of specific teaching practices but also how many other things have an impact on teaching and that these must be managed effectively so as not to compromise classroom interactions. Arrastia et al. (2014) described that preservice teachers who engaged in guided observations and reflections gained a deeper learning of how a teacher works. The preservice teachers in the current study maintained reflections on their immersion at schools and were able to discuss these experiences with peers during class time at university. These kinds of observations and reflections are consistent with Lave and Wenger's (1991) idea of LPP where participants act on the periphery of activities until they have gained enough knowledge, understanding, and confidence to take on the role themselves. Timostsuk and Ugaste (2010) found that teacher identity development, whether it be positive or negative, was significant through the relationships that preservice teachers had with their students, their supervising teachers, and other members of the school community. The current research extends these findings by considering how preservice teachers' beliefs about themselves as teachers have contributed to their developing philosophy of teaching.

7.3 PHILOSOPHY OF TEACHING

Several of the preservice teachers raised the point that they learned that they needed to be flexible in their approach to teaching students and working with supervising teachers. Renae, for example, described that a significant focus of her developing teaching philosophy was the belief that student needs required attention at the group

and individual levels and that students should be respected for their differences. This was a common theme expressed by the preservice teachers in the current research. They perceived that they had a duty toward their students to help facilitate their learning and sense of belonging in the school community. Research has suggested that situated learning greatly influences the development of a professional identity (Day & Kington, 2008) and perceptions are developed through learning experiences as a response to being at different sites (Mutton et al., 2010). Several of the preservice teachers discussed how their experience of being situated in so-called disadvantaged schools had a profound effect on their teaching philosophy and the teachers they imagined they wanted to become. There is little research to be found about the development of preservice teachers' philosophy of teaching in an immersion pathway, but this is an area worth exploring more so that teacher educators can better understand how best to support nascent teacher identity development.

Awareness of their developing philosophy of teaching was significant for the participants in this research as they were required to write an essay on this topic for their teacher registration application so very often it was at the forefront of their thinking, particularly toward the end of their time in the school community. Their philosophy of teaching was strongly connected to their perception of self-as-teachers. The preservice teachers' developing teacher identity was influenced in the year-long immersion pathway through a process of socialisation, similar to that described by Staton (2008) whereby they acquired understanding of values, attitudes, norms, knowledge, and the behaviours of teaching as they perceived them embedded in the practices of the school community. Self-reflection was an important vehicle used by the preservice teachers to help them to discover and comment on their evolving philosophy of teaching. Danielwicz (2001) suggested that observation and analysis through reflection provides a lens for preservice teachers to understand who they are in relation to the multiple roles they engage in and in how others see them in a school-based CoP.

7.4 AGE & PARENTHOOD AS ASPECTS OF IDENTITY DEVELOPMENT

Interesting personal characteristics that the researcher became more keenly aware of during current research was that the six preservice teachers, while all at the same

stage in their teacher education, were divided into two groups based on their age (three in their early twenties and three in their forties) and that the older group of women were also mothers. Although not the focus per se of the current research, age and parenthood appeared to have an impact on relationships that were formed in school communities. The three older women (Roberta, Katherine, and Renae) had a significant chat on the online discussion board about how they drew on their dual roles of parenthood and preservice teacher experiences to develop relationships, particularly with students in their classes. This finding concurs with Bukor's (2015) work which concludes that the life experiences of being a mother can profoundly affect the shaping of teacher identity and feelings of being a competent teacher. This particular bonding of the three women was perceived as somewhat daunting to one of the younger and single preservice teachers in particular, Sabrina who compared herself to Roberta, Katherine, and Renae. Sabrina seemed to have drawn on the older three ladies as role models who inspired her to grow professionally and be more confident. However, being an older and more mature preservice teacher did not guarantee a positive placement in the school and not all of the interactions at a school promoted a sense of belonging. Roberta, for example, was in her forties and a mother but experienced a very negative situation in her first classroom placement. It is unclear from the data but it could have been that the supervising teacher in Roberta's class had expectations of her as a mature-aged preservice teacher that were beyond her capabilities as a preservice teacher; these may have been different to expectations to what may have been expected of younger preservice teachers. Alternatively, because the negative dynamics of interactions were already in place before Roberta's placement, her supervising teacher may have expected Roberta to fit in with these dynamics, which really were not focused on positively supporting her development as a teacher. Iyer and Reese (2013) found that when preservice teachers encountered obstructions to shared understanding and interactions with their supervising teachers and the students in the class the experience resulted in these preservice teachers failing to become members of the community, or becoming marginalised members at best.

There is very little research that focuses on the dual role of being a preservice teacher and being a mother. What research there is tends to focus on the challenges and struggles these women have trying to balance their two roles. White (2008), for example, explored the beliefs, motivations, and attitudes to these dual roles of six

mothers training to be teachers in New Zealand and found that the greatest difficulty for the women was related to childcare. While they were at university or at schools for professional experience they had an additional challenge of juggling the emotional and physical needs of their children. The three women in the current research did not specifically mention these concerns, perhaps because their children were already in school so they were perceived to be in a safe place while their mothers were completing their teacher training. In another study, Duncan (2000) found that the extent to which the women in her study achieved success in their dual roles depended on the coping strategies they constructed to meet the demands of both roles. The three older women in the current research did not comment on the challenges of coping with their dual roles. Instead they drew upon their roles as mothers to provide structure to how they worked with students in their classes. As the current research was not focused on this aspect of the participants' lives in relation to their developing teacher identity there is a gap in our understanding about teacher identity development specifically for women who are mothers that could certainly be pursued in future research. With the changing demographics for teacher education these days, this area of research requires further study.

7.5 CONTRIBUTIONS TO SCHOLARSHIP

The purpose of the current research was to explore preservice teachers' perceptions of the experiences that provided them with insights into the profession and in developing their identity of belonging in the profession. Findings of the research contribute in several significant areas as outlined below:

1. Allowing fourth-year preservice teachers opportunities to participate in student-free days at the beginning of the school year was described by the preservice teachers as highly significant in helping them to identify what it means to be a teacher. The preservice teachers remarked on the importance of their participation during these three days to their teacher identity development repeatedly throughout the year.

2. The research identified that preservice teachers perceived themselves to be positioned differently from their peers who only participated in mandatory professional experience. When they compared their sense of belonging in the school to that of their preservice peers completing their mandatory professional experience in

the same school, the preservice teachers in the immersion pathway described that they were accepted at a much deeper level than their peers because they had been at their school since the beginning of the year rather than only being in a school for the few mandatory weeks of professional experience.

3. A major difference that affected participation for preservice teachers was the element of supervisor assessment for mandatory professional experience placements compared with no supervisor assessment for participation in the immersion pathway. Some of the preservice teachers in the immersion pathway felt pressured to successfully complete a mandatory professional experience placement in the same immersion school because they sought to secure employment at the school for the following year as beginning teachers.

4. There were some differences in approaches and perceptions of teaching taken by the preservice teachers as a consequence of their age and role as a parent. The three preservice teachers who were mothers commented on how they approached working with students by identifying how they worked with their own children to resolve problems such as time management and completing homework. At least one of the younger, single preservice teachers commented on what she perceived as the advantages of having more life experience that comes with age and parenthood in understanding how to work with children.

5. The research found that artefacts and tools were frequently and significantly referenced by the preservice teachers during their engagement in the year-long immersion pathway. A variety of artefacts described by the preservice teachers were connected to the development of their sense of belonging in the school community (for example, school staff photo), teacher identity (for example, whole school prospectus), and professional practice (for example, self-designed lesson activity templates).

6. This year-long longitudinal study explored self-perceptions of preservice teachers about their development of teacher identity and professional practice over a continued period. The study found that preservice teachers' perceptions indicated that they experienced 'real' growth development over that duration.

7. Relationships were an integral element of preservice teachers' formation of teacher identity development. The importance of building relationships was widely discussed by the preservice teachers and several types of relationships emerged during their engagement in the year-long immersion pathway, that is, with the school principal or deputy-principal, their supervising teacher(s), other school staff, fellow preservice teachers not in the immersion pathway, students, and parents.

7.6 LIMITATIONS

There are three limitations to the research that must be considered. First, given that the sample of participants was limited to six individuals, only general conclusions can be drawn from the findings presented in the current study. The findings cannot be viewed as being representative of the experiences of Australia-based preservice teachers in Australian schools, in general. Yin (2010) proffered this point of view as a consequence of case study-based approaches to research where findings can draw generalisations only from a specific case or a limited number of cases. Nonetheless, credibility, in terms of the believability (Saldana, 2011) of data collected, analysed and then presented in the findings of this study, was enhanced by the period of time that the researcher spent on collecting data from the preservice teachers; that is, one year. The credibility was further enhanced with the use of several methods of data collection by way of interviews, an online discussion board, the collection of professional artefacts, and a subsequent quasi-comparative method of analysis.

Second, the research was explored from a sociocultural perspective with particular reference to Lave and Wenger's (1991) situated learning in a CoP. The questions asked of preservice teachers in the research may have drawn different answers to those posed from a different theoretical perspective, with data collected at a different point in time, under different conditions or with a different group of preservice teachers.

Finally, preservice teachers' self-reporting behaviours had the potential to present opportunities for inaccuracies and/or bias to occur during data collection (for example, the question format of social desirability when answering in focus groups or when using an online discussion board). Given this constraint, the researcher utilised semi-structured interviews and allowed the participants a choice of engaging with others in

individual interviews or focus groups in the early, mid-year and final interviews as well as freedom in writing content via the online discussion board either publicly within the group or privately with the researcher which all served to minimise any adverse influences of bias and/or inaccuracies in the preservice teachers' self-reporting behaviours.

Despite these potential limitations, the researcher felt the findings drawn from the current research were soundly founded on candid and comprehensive accounts of experiences shared by the preservice teachers in regard to their engagement in an immersion pathway. Consequently, the accuracy of meaning from preservice teachers' interpretations of those experiences and representation of those interpretations in this research did not appear to the researcher to be adversely affected to any significant degree by the abovementioned limitations.

7.7 RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the findings derived from this study, six recommendations for the education of preservice teachers are presented: namely, the inclusion of a multilayered placement, further research of the following aspects - preservice teacher confidence levels during preservice teachers' engagement in professional experience, the potential impact of preservice teacher characteristics such as age and parenthood, monitoring preservice teachers' identity development over time, the provision of opportunities for extended placements, and the development of preservice teachers' philosophy of teaching in an immersion pathway.

1. Multilayered placement:

Engagement in the immersion pathway included engagement in professional experience practicum block placements (Field Experience) and a final internship placement at the same school. It was found that this multilayered placement structure allowed the preservice teachers to develop relationships with many stakeholders in the school community that their fellow preservice teachers who only completed short mandated professional experience placements at the same school were unable to do to the same extent. Findings from this study lead the researcher to agree with a call by Mayer et al. (2014), in their *Longitudinal Teacher Education and Workforce Study*, for

more research into long-term immersion and internships in ITE programs. Specifically, further research is needed comparing: a) the effects of long-term immersion placements in schools with the shorter termed placements, b) the effects of long-term immersion placements in addition to professional experience placements in the same school, and c) the effects of volunteer placements on professional identity development compared with identity development in mandatory placements.

2. Preservice teacher confidence:

There is little research that compares confidence levels of preservice teachers who have engaged in a long-term immersion pathway styled professional experience with those engaged in shorter professional experience placements in schools. The current research would suggest that there may well be a difference that is worth exploring particularly as some of the preservice teachers in the study struggled on their professional experience and internship placement in comparison to how well they managed their immersion pathway placement.

3. Impact of preservice teacher characteristics (age and parenthood):

The self-perceived impact of age differences among preservice teachers who participate in school-based professional experience warrants further consideration as an area of research as does the dual role of being a parent and a preservice teacher. The preservice teachers in the current research were evenly split: three were single and in their twenties; and three were mothers in their forties. The preservice teachers rarely commented on the aspect of age but the mothers in the group did make significant connections to being a preservice teacher and being a mother in both their language and the behaviour they used with students in their classes. A potential focus of future research lies with the under-explored dynamics of being a preservice teacher who is also a mature-aged mother (or parent).

4. Monitoring of preservice teachers' identity development over time:

The current research has illustrated the value of exploring transitions that preservice teachers experience as they develop professional identity over extended periods of time. Future studies should consider the value of continuing to monitor preservice teachers' professional identity development over time and explore the influence of contextual enablers and constraints on this development.

5. Opportunities for extended placements:

Preservice teachers in the current research communicated their mostly positive perspectives of their participation in an extended school-based immersion pathway. The mostly positive shared experiences of these preservice teachers suggests that teacher educators should continue to provide opportunities for extended placements or immersions to better prepare preservice teachers for assessed placements and first appointments as beginning teachers.

6. Need for further research:

There is little research to be found on the development of preservice teachers' philosophy of teaching in an immersion pathway and this is an area worth exploring more so that a greater understanding of how best to support nascent teacher identity development can be constructed.

7.8 CONCLUSION

The current research explored preservice teachers' sense of belonging and teacher identity development through their participation in a year-long immersion pathway. Key findings suggest that preservice teachers' identity development is strongly related to how they perceive themselves as teachers (Beauchamp & Thomas, 2009; Poulou, 2007) and, equally important, how they believe others perceive them as teachers (Olsen, 2010; Woods et al., 2014) in the school community. The most significant contributing influence on their identity development is the relationships they developed in their school communities, particularly their relationships with their supervising teachers (Broadley & Ledger, 2012; Mueller & Hindin, 2011) and the students (De Jong et al., 2013; De Jong et al., 2014) in their classes. These relationships helped the preservice teachers develop a sense of belonging, not only in these classes but also as members of the teaching community.

The findings of the research suggest that there is merit in having preservice teachers engage with school communities as volunteer participants over an extended period of time. Being immersed in a school for an extended period of time allowed the preservice teachers opportunities to test out the teacher behaviours they observed experienced

teachers enacting (Fenton-O’Creevy, Dimitriadis, & Scobie, 2015; Harlow & Cobb, 2014; Ten Dam & Blom, 2006). These opportunities led the preservice teachers to hone their own teaching skills and to present themselves to others as a teacher rather than as a preservice teacher. Being perceived by others as ‘a teacher’ rather than as a preservice teacher had a positive impact on their developing professional teacher identity and sense of belonging within the school community.

Teacher educators and schools have a responsibility to ensure that preservice teachers have ample prospects to practice teaching in both assessed and unassessed opportunities in school settings (Bond, 2013; Daniel et al., 2013). This would require both parties to develop strong partnerships where both can contribute to shaping how to train preservice teachers to be confident and capable in their roles, that is to say, ‘graduate ready’ beginning teachers (AITSL, 2011; AITSL, 2015; Mayer et al., 2014). The findings of the current research suggest that the immersion pathway, or similar such programing, is such a viable opportunity.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Australian Professional Standards for Teachers (Extract) Graduate Career Stage

PROFESSIONAL KNOWLEDGE		PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE		PROFESSIONAL ENGAGEMENT		
STANDARD 1 - Know students and how they learn	STANDARD 2 - Know the content and how to teach it	STANDARD 3 - Plan for and implement effective teaching and learning	STANDARD 4 - Create and maintain supportive and safe learning environments	STANDARD 5 - Assess, provide feedback and report on student learning	STANDARD 6 - Engage in professional learning	STANDARD 7 - Engage professionally with colleagues, parents/carers and the community
<p>Focus</p> <p>11 - Physical, social and intellectual development and characteristics of students</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate knowledge and understanding of physical, social and intellectual development and characteristics of students and how these may affect learning.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>12 - Understand how students learn</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate knowledge and understanding of research on how students learn and the implications for teaching.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>13 - Students with diverse linguistic, cultural, religious and socioeconomic backgrounds</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate knowledge of learning strategies that are essential to the learning strengths and needs of students from diverse linguistic, cultural, religious and socioeconomic backgrounds.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>14 - Strategies for teaching Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander students</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate broad knowledge and understanding of the impact of culture, cultural identity and linguistic background on the education of students from Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander backgrounds.</p>	<p>Focus</p> <p>15 - Differentiate teaching to meet the specific learning needs of students across the full range of abilities</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate knowledge and understanding of strategies for differentiating teaching to meet the specific learning needs of students across the full range of abilities.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>16 - Strategies to support full participation of students with disability</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate broad knowledge and understanding of legislative requirements and teaching strategies for support participation and learning of students with disability.</p>	<p>Focus</p> <p>17 - Literacy and numeracy</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Know and understand literacy and numeracy teaching strategies and their application in teaching areas.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>18 - Information and Communication Technology (ICT)</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Implement teaching strategies for using ICT to support curriculum learning opportunities for students.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>19 - Use effective classroom communication</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate a range of verbal and non-verbal communication strategies to support student engagement.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>20 - Use ICT safely, responsibly and ethically</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate an understanding of the relevant issues and the strategies available to support the safe, responsible and ethical use of ICT in learning and teaching.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>21 - Report on student achievement</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate understanding of a range of strategies for reporting to students and parents/carers and the purposes of keeping accurate and reliable records of student achievement.</p>	<p>Focus</p> <p>22 - Content selection and organisation</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Organise content into an effective learning and teaching sequence for teaching.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>23 - Curriculum, assessment and reporting</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Use curriculum, assessment and reporting knowledge to design learning sequences and lesson plans.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>24 - Understand and respect Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people to promote reconciliation between Indigenous and non-Indigenous Australians</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate broad knowledge of understanding of and respect for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander histories, cultures and languages.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>25 - Shared and use resources</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate knowledge of a range of resources, including ICT, that engage students in their learning.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>26 - Maintain student safety</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Describe strategies that support students' wellbeing and safety working with school and/or system, curriculum and legislative requirements.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>27 - Interpret student data</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate the capacity to interpret student assessment data to evaluate student learning and modify teaching practice.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>28 - Apply professional learning and improve student learning</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate an understanding of the rationale for continued professional learning and the implications for improved student learning.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>29 - Engage with professional teaching networks and broader communities</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Understand the role of external professionals and community representatives in broadening teachers' professional knowledge and practice.</p>	<p>Focus</p> <p>29 - Plan, structure and sequence learning programs</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Plan lesson sequences using knowledge of student learning, content and effective teaching strategies.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>30 - Use teaching strategies</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Includes a range of teaching strategies.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>31 - Manage classroom activities</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate the capacity to organise classroom activities and provide clear directions.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>32 - Provide feedback to students on their learning</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate an understanding of the purposes of providing timely and appropriate feedback to students about their learning.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>33 - Make consistent and comparable judgments</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate understanding of assessment moderation and its application to support consistent and comparable judgments of student learning.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>34 - Engage in professional learning and improve practice</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Understand the relevant and appropriate sources of professional learning for teachers.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>35 - Engage with colleagues and improve practice</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Seek and apply constructive feedback from supervisors and leaders to improve teaching practice.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>36 - Engage with professional administrative and organisational requirements</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Understand the relevant legislative, administrative and organisational policies and processes required for teachers according to school stage.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>37 - Comply with legislative, administrative and organisational requirements</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Understand strategies for working effectively, sensitively and confidently with parents/carers.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>38 - Engage with the parents/carers</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Understand strategies for working effectively, sensitively and confidently with parents/carers.</p>	<p>Focus</p> <p>31 - Establish challenging learning goals</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Set learning goals that provide achievable challenges for students of varying abilities and characteristics.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>32 - Support student participation</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Identify strategies to support inclusive student participation and engagement in classroom activities.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>33 - Assess student learning</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate understanding of assessment strategies, including formal and formal, diagnostic, formative and summative approaches to assess student learning.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>34 - Identify and plan professional learning needs</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate an understanding of the role of the Australian Professional Standards for Teachers in identifying professional learning needs.</p> <p>Focus</p> <p>35 - Meet professional ethics and responsibilities</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Understand and apply the key principles described in codes of ethics and conduct for the teaching profession.</p>	
<p>Focus</p> <p>37 - Engage parents/carers in the educative process</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Describe a broad range of strategies for involving parents/carers in the educative process.</p>		<p>Focus</p> <p>35 - Evaluate and improve teaching programs</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Demonstrate broad knowledge of strategies that can be used to evaluate teaching programs to improve student learning.</p>		<p>Focus</p> <p>36 - Engage with colleagues and improve practice</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Understand the relevant and appropriate sources of professional learning for teachers.</p>		<p>Focus</p> <p>37 - Comply with legislative, administrative and organisational requirements</p> <p>Descriptor</p> <p>Understand the relevant legislative, administrative and organisational policies and processes required for teachers according to school stage.</p>

Source: Queensland College of Teachers. (n.d.-a). Retrieved from https://www.qct.edu.au/PDF/PSU/APST_GraduateStage.pdf

APPENDIX B

Interview Protocol - First and Second Rounds of Interviews

Participation

Participation involve three online, recorded interviews via Google Hang Outs in our community or on Skype. Each interview will be approximately 45 minutes to 60 minutes in duration.

Participation in this study is voluntary. If you do agree to participate you can withdraw from the study without comment or penalty. If you withdraw, on request your interview data can be destroyed up until the time that the analysis of that data has begun. Your decision to participate or not participate will in no way impact upon your current or future relationship with your university.

All participants are de-identified during the data collection, data analysis, and writing of the final theses document through the use of identifiers, such as, P1, P2, etc.

Questions

1. Please share a story of your engagement so far at your school community (e.g., what surprised you, shocked you, made you think about or question something in particular).
2. Where do you feel your sense of professional identity lies on the continuum below (you can select any point along the continuum):

Not Confident

Confident

Describe why you feel you are at this stage currently (e.g., was there a particular incident/activity/meeting that occurred that you felt either enhanced or hindered your sense of professional identity in the classroom/in the school community).

3. Where do you feel your sense of belonging lies on the continuum below (you can select any point along the continuum):

Not Confident

Confident

Describe why you feel you are at this stage currently (e.g., was there a particular incident/activity/meeting that occurred that you felt either enhanced or hindered your sense of belonging in the classroom/in the school community).

4. In relation to your experiences at your school to this point, describe how any of the following have contributed to your sense of teacher identity or sense of belonging to the school community. Please provide an example for each described:
 - The setting up of the class
 - The organisation of the class
 - Establishing/maintaining class rules and routines
 - Planning (lessons, classroom management etc.)
 - Resources or artefacts that connect with your teacher identity/sense of belonging
 - Working with your class mentor/other staff members
 - Working with students
 - Working with parents/community members
5. Describe your current philosophy of teaching and what has helped to shape your philosophy of teaching.

APPENDIX C

Interview Protocol - Third Round of Interviews

Participation

Participation involve three online, recorded interviews via Google Hang Outs in our community or on Skype. Each interview will be approximately 45 minutes to 60 minutes in duration.

Participation in this study is voluntary. If you do agree to participate you can withdraw from the study without comment or penalty. If you withdraw, on request your interview data can be destroyed up until the time that the analysis of that data has begun. Your decision to participate or not participate will in no way impact upon your current or future relationship with your university.

All participants are de-identified during the data collection, data analysis, and writing of the final theses document through the use of identifiers, such as, P1, P2, etc.

Questions

1. What discussions did you and your supervising teacher have [at any point of your engagement in the immersion pathway] about the actual criteria and/or expectations for your engagement in the pathway? E.g., How did you know what to do at any point throughout the year?
2. How would you describe your professional teacher identity now compared to where you were at the beginning of your professional experience in the immersion pathway this year?
3. What would you describe as the single most significant thing that has contributed to your developing teacher identity this year?
4. What do you perceive were the differences, if any, between being in the immersion pathway and being on prac?
5. What has surprised you most about yourself through your engagement in the immersion pathway that has contributed to your new role as a graduate teacher?
6. How would you sum up the value of completing the immersion pathway for graduating preservice?

APPENDIX D

My Immersion Pathway (MIP) - Google+ Community

Source: Google+. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://plus.google.com/communities/>

APPENDIX E

Moderated Online Discussion Board Code of Conduct

Code of Conduct for Online Discussion Participation

1. All comments and responses will be treated confidentially. All data will be de-identified.
2. Refrain from including information about people's names, school names, images which identify people, and other details that might be deemed as being private.
3. Bring in related prior experience and knowledge (professional experience, prior coursework, readings, etc.).
4. Be constructive with comments about other participants' postings but be considerate and avoid critical or offensive commentary.
5. Build on other participants' responses to create threads.
6. Use proper etiquette (appropriate language, typing, etc.).

